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**HR MARKETING STRATEGIES FACING GENERATION Y :
LEVERAGING MANAGEMENT SOFTWARES IN
MOROCCAN COMPANY**

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**HR MARKETING STRATEGIES FACING GENERATION Y :
LEVERAGING MANAGEMENT SOFTWARES IN
MOROCCAN COMPANY**

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长春理工大学学位论文原创性声明

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摘要

为什么要讨论人力资源营销？该策略将如何改变人力资源专业人员执行日常任务的方式？正常业务？这些是本书要解决的主要问题。这项研究表明人力资源营销是一种包罗万象的方法，而不仅仅是一种编辑“噱头”或一种短暂的趋势。多年来，就业领域发生了重大变化。举个例子，考虑一下最重要人才的供求规律的逆转，或者职业本身的概念改变为一种不太线性的、不再总是得到组织支持的职业。

公司开始实施人力资源营销策略，以满足对新人才和能力的需要，但通常是从最简单的组成部分开始：与易于识别和接近的现成目标（例如候选人）进行沟通。公司已经开始制定人力资源营销策略，重点是吸引最优秀的人才，无论是实际的人还是学生，以便继续发展（从竞争对手中）。此外，他们还利用旨在吸引人力资源的传统营销策略（市场研究战略定位图、沟通和营销计划）来努力留住现有人员。

在本论文中，对人力资源职能和 Y 一代对管理软件的看法进行了评估。作为实习的一部分，我们的研究实际上是在跨国公司 INTEL CIA Morocco 摩洛哥的人力资源部门进行的。我们的定性研究有三个主要目标：列出 Y 一代的特征，评估人力资源部门对这一代人的看法，以及评估两个群体对管理软件技术的看法。

我们的研究是公司战略的关键组成部分之一，特别是人力资源部门的战略，旨在加强内部调查中出现两个轴：

- 1、联络通讯中心板块市场口碑一般，是最受候选人追捧的第三板块。与提到的其他公司相比，它似乎是提供专业晋升机会最少且工作环境也不是最好的公司。
- 2：薪酬是候选人经常提到的诉求之一。为了吸引潜在客户，目前排名第 29 位的 INTEL CIA Morocco 也需要解决这个问题。

我们的研究表明，Y 一代仍然具有鲜明的个性，对企业表现出很高的期望并且要求很高。这就是为什么人力资源部门修改人力资源报价非常重要。

Abstract

Why discuss HR marketing? How might this strategy alter how HR professionals go about their day-to-day tasks? Regular business? These are the primary issues that this book addresses. This study demonstrates how HR marketing is an all-encompassing approach, rather than just an editorial "gimmick" or a passing trend. For many years, there have been significant changes taking place in the job sector. As an illustration, consider the reversal of the law of supply and demand for the most important talent or the alteration of the idea of a career itself into one that is less linear and no longer always supported by the organization.

Companies are starting to implement an HR marketing strategy in response to the need for fresh talent and capabilities, though frequently by starting with the simplest component: communication with readily available targets that are simple to recognize and simple to approach, such as the candidates. Companies have already begun to build HR marketing strategies focused at luring the best possible talent, whether that be actual people or students, in order to continue to grow (from competitors). In addition, they are striving to keep their current personnel by utilizing conventional marketing strategies meant to attract human resources (market research strategic positioning maps, communication and marketing plans).

In this dissertation, the HR function and Generation Y's perceptions of management softwares were assessed. The human resources division of the multinational INTEL CIA Morocco is where our research was actually done as part of an internship. Our qualitative study had three main goals: to produce a list of Generation Y traits, to assess how the HR function felt about this generation, and to assess how both groups felt about management softwares technologies.

Our study is one of the key components of the company's strategies, particularly the HR department's strategy to strengthen the two axes that emerge from an internal survey as follows:

1. The contact and communication center sector has an average reputation on the market, while

being the third sector most sought after by candidates. Comparing it to the other firms mentioned, it seems to be the one that gives the fewest opportunities for professional advancement and where the working environment is not the best. 2: Compensation is frequently mentioned by candidates as one of the appeal aspects. In order to draw in prospects, Intelcia, which is currently rated in 29th place, will also need to work on this issue.

Our research indicates that generation Y continues to have a distinct personality, expressing high expectations of the business and being quite demanding. This is why it is important for the HR function to modify the HR offer.

Keywords: HR Marketing, Generation Y, Management Softwares, Employer Brand.

研究生院制

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Introduction

Human resources management (HRM) has undergone an important and crucial evolution during these years, it is now at the center of the company's strategy. That evolution and this change is due to the rapidly changing environment (globalization, technologies.).

Nowadays businesses not only need people who get the job done and missions, but they also need people who bring knowledge, creativity and having a source of innovation because human resources are a real asset for companies and are considered a key performance factor for them.

We no longer speak of skills but of talents, this notion is quite broad and inclusive it varies from one structure to another, from one sector to another, from one country to another. These are the people with outstanding performance, which is why companies need to rely on talents, retain them or retain them.

Indeed, to face new challenges and respond to issues of attractiveness, motivation and loyalty of employees and talents, the employer brand can be articulated in this direction. Companies can no longer hide behind their institutional communication because today information spreads quickly, communication and the web make it possible to display a high transparency about what is happening inside companies. The employer brand therefore represents all the advantages communicated by an organization in order to make it a place attractive, benchmark work. In this perspective, companies invest in different tools to communicate these advantages and attract potential candidates.

While several authors demonstrate a difference in how they define this generation's age, they all agree that this generation is the result of the digital revolution. Beyond the connected, digital nature of this generation, she carries expectations and new demands that provide significant challenges for businesses, including human resource management. The development of information and communication technologies, as well as the emergence of new ones, help to explain the digital revolution.

One outcome of this revolution, among others, is the appearance of management softwares, which have spread throughout many industries. Recent decades have seen the emergence of process reforms within the organization, particularly in the function HR. The function HR finds itself confronted with a disruption of the Rh processes due to an increase in the number of new,

younger coworkers and excessive tool usage in version Web Marketing. We intend to discuss the emergence of a "HR Web Marketing" or perhaps an "e-HRM," the entry of young people who are sensitive to employer brands into the labor market, talent management, and HR marketing. In light of these findings, we aim to highlight in this thesis how Generation Y and the HR function perceive management softwares, as well as their role in the creation of the employer brand and the recruitment of Generation Y applicants.

In this attitude, HR managers must learn to use strategy and marketing techniques to attract their (prospect) future employee (seduce him), integrate him (welcome him), and encourage them to stay with the company (build their loyalty) in the same way that customers do.

HR marketing practice is now more important than ever. Recognizing the issue of attracting and retaining personnel, HR departments at large, well-informed companies were eager to incorporate into their HR policies logic and tools drawn from marketers.

In the theoretical section, we will discuss the resources that will be used as the understanding and execution axis for our research. HR marketing is covered in the first chapter, Generation Y in the second, and management softwares in the third. In a further stage, we will apply the theoretical tools in a real-world setting, specifically the case of INTEL CIA Morocco, where we will examine the tools in use and carry out a qualitative survey to gauge how Generation Y perceives the HR function. Management softwares.

But is it possible to reduce HR marketing to one single strategy that is closely related to hiring new talent? These measures aimed at talent retention do fall under the umbrella of marketing tactics. However, they are components of a much larger puzzle.

It is true that the HR function must now do more than only recruit, keep, and develop the greatest individuals. It must also (be) able to market. In order to improve its credibility, it must employ the process tools. It must reconsider its strategies, choosing a more comprehensive, client-centered approach where organizational agility must take the place of procedural rigidity.

The research methodology employed involves conducting semi-structured interviews with members of the HR department, including human resources directors, managers, and executives, staff members, and Y generation job seekers.

The HR function must deal with a variety of ideas, including the HR product or service, the expectations of its present or potential customers (candidates, employees, or perhaps all parties

Stakeholders), and market research on either the internal or external level (s). In order to anticipate its environment, it tries to comprehend it better.

The traits indicated in the literature, particularly the technophile character (mastery of management softwares) mentioned by Pichault in his study, will be tested in the empirical phase first. Second, we'll look at how Generation Y feels about management softwares. We'll also look at how much the Rh function and Y candidates are involved in management softwares. Finally, we'll look at HR procedures as well as how Generation Y searches for jobs and career opportunities.

As a conclusion, we will generate one or more suggestions that will open up previously underdeveloped regions for growth or create new, untapped ones.

Professional context:

1. The contact center sector in Morocco

A contact center, also known as a call center, contact center, or communication company, is a collection of personnel, physical space, furnishings, and equipment that enables it to manage the remote relationship between a brand and its market. Most frequently, it takes the shape of one or more offices where phone calls are routed, along with emails, letters, etc. The customer advisers at the call center can categorize these calls as incoming when they are received by them or outgoing when they are made by them. Many contact centers are equipped with the most recent advancements in telecommunications technology to handle both kinds of calls.

Contact centers first appeared in the United States during the 1960s. Brands were able to get closer to their clients at the time while maintaining an acceptable level of cost-effectiveness due to the enormous distance separating the various states and the democratization of telephone calls.

In recent years, academic researchers and the media have both shown a great deal of interest in call centers. This is mostly because of the nature and character of the newly generated jobs, as well as their phenomenal development and significance as a source of employment in many industrialized nations, including Australia. Call centers have been compared to "electronic sweatshops" and "human battery farms" because they offer low-wage, routine work that are closely watched and scrutinized.

It is obvious that the goal of call centers is to provide customer assistance at the lowest feasible cost, despite the fact that this is far from a uniform image. They work to consolidate service suppliers and to centralize service delivery. Through the widespread use of cutting-edge information technology, call centers rationalize the work process and attempt to standardize customer interactions with replaceable and functionally identical service providers.

Call centers have become one of Morocco's fastest growing industries as a result of increased offshore activity in European countries, particularly France and Spain.

Professional context

For a variety of reasons, a large number of international organizations have picked Morocco as the best location for new call centers: Moroccan agents efficiently manage high-volume calls, credit card issues, and customer satisfaction surveys in multiple languages. Furthermore, there are additional benefits due to a low labor cost and close time zones.

In Morocco, contact centers are used for mail order or assistance services, and since 2005, this industry has expanded to include all other sectors as well. The contact center sector was the one that employed the most people in 2021, followed by the IT sector, which had 12 percent of available positions, according to an analysis by the magazine REKRUTE in March 2022 in Morocco, which shows a growth rate. The banking industry follows in third.

So, by releasing the infrastructural sectors and offering affordable call center outsourcing services, the Moroccan government has made great efforts to entice foreign investors in the telecom industry. Moroccan local phone carriers began making significant pricing cuts of up to 13 percent in "Maroc Telecom" in 2005. The Casablanca-Rabat region is home to the majority of these centers, which collectively employ some 30,000 people.

The call center sector in Morocco has had a lot of challenges, especially when the global recession hit the European market, while being one of the fastest expanding sectors that has contributed to a decrease in the unemployment rate and a significant source of outside funding.

2. INTEL CIA in Morocco

2.1 Presentation of the company INTEL CIA

INTEL CIA is a contact center, which was established in Morocco 20 years ago and has been pushed by a strong vision, the group has swiftly increased its geographical presence and activities in order to support its clients' outsourcing operations and allow them to better concentrate on their main businesses.

A multinational player in outsourcing, Intelcia has combined abilities, technologies, and procedures for 20 years to provide its clients all over the world with a custom service and skills that meet international standards. In light of these four solution areas customer relationship management, IT solutions, business process outsourcing, and digital services the organization provides a comprehensive and cross-sector offer.

Professional context

The group, which operates in 14 nations across Africa, Europe, and America, currently employs more than 18.800 people directly and indirectly over 40 operational centers.

At Intelcia, they have developed the environments that will attract and nurture talent, making them desire to work for them and confident enough to stick around. in order for them to continuously improve and perform even better in the future. So that they meet the challenges they face.

Its expertise is founded on its capacity to integrate skills, technology, and workflows to provide a custom service and skills at a level consistent with the highest standards around the world.

Altice has been a shareholder of Intelcia since 2016, which it relies on to hasten its global expansion.

With a presence in America, the Caribbean, and new locations in Europe, Intelcia continue its international growth in 2022.

The INTELZIA group is convinced that their identity is nourished by pluralism, diversity, and tolerance. Through various partnerships and developments, the group is now present on three continents and in 16 nations, including North Africa's Morocco and Egypt, Sub-Saharan Africa's Cameroon, Ivory Coast, and Senegal, the Indian Ocean's Madagascar, and the United States of America, Western Europe's France, Portugal, Spain, and United Kingdom, and Latin America and the Caribbean's Colombia, Jamaica, Dominican Republic, and Chile.

2.2 History of Intelcia

“Intelcia has succeeded, in 20 years, in moving from a regional player to a global player capable today of addressing several markets, in several languages. Thanks to its geographic and business diversification, the Group has significant short-term ambitions. The Group should end2021 with a turnover of around 500 million euros,” says Karim Bernoussi, Chairman and CEO of the Intelcia Group.

When reading the 309-page book, which was written in-house and opens the doors of a company that has grown, of course, but remains focused on its human capital, the main

Professional context

driver of its business, one gets the impression that after 20 years of activity and expansion, rewriting history with hindsight to inspire and inject positive energy into the business world, this is the feeling one gets.

The book is a compilation of testimonies, but the first tribute will be given to the man, in this case the late Kamil Benjelloun, without whom the story would have been very different. He was one of the founders of Intelcia's forerunner, Transom Worldwide Morocco (TWW) (2000-2006). The CBI founder, who was already well-known in the IT industry at the time, was a visionary. And it's true that Karim Bernoussi is regarded as the father of the telecom industry. Youssef El Ouafir and the current head of the Intelcia organization complement each other well. This is something that several prominent figures from the country's economic landscape will attest to and share in the book's columns.

“At Intelcia, we are dreamers in action. We have our feet on the ground, our heads in the stars. We have the humility and the optimism of the first day and the serene energy of those for whom nothing is impossible”. The tone is set from the cover...

3. INTELICIA and its HR policy

Intelcia IT Solutions continues to draw in IT talent as part of its strategic development, and it does it in a stimulating atmosphere with an HR strategy that puts the needs of its employees first. Ghali Moussaoui, Director of Telecom Application Solutions at Intelcia IT Solutions, goes into detail about the Group's HR strategy and recruitment policies for IT talent, including both experienced professionals and young graduates.

An HR policy that pushes for a stimulating organization at the expense of back office-centered traditional models and is particularly focused on management proximity, communication, and openness.

Along with the creation of career plans inside the Group, training also holds a major position in this policy. Therefore, Intelcia IT Solutions helps its customers' technological and operational transformation while pursuing its strategic development initiatives at the national and regional levels by hiring the best individuals and encouraging the growth of their abilities.

CHAPTER 1: HR Marketing

1.1 Background

Too many firms overlook the fundamental need of marketing. They consider marketing to be an overpriced luxury. Effective marketing occurs frequently and on a regular basis, which does not occur when sponsored with windfall funds. It is said that money must be spent in order to make money.

Marketing concepts are the same regardless of company size or position. When it comes to creating a budget, the parameters are relatively generic and conventional, with spending ranging from 2% to 20% of their anticipated gross sales. A decent starting point is 5% of the anticipated gross sales. According to a recent HRmarketer.com study, major HR suppliers spend an average of 10% of their gross revenue on marketing and public relations.

Recruiting excellent candidates is important to any company's future success. You need the appropriate people to expand your company and your business, whether you're a startup or a benchmark stock market corporation. But, as we all know, finding the top talent is challenging. Hiring is the number one priority for business leaders worldwide (both on revenue and customer growth).

You've already invested in good people by hiring them and then training them through internal knowledge exchange and internal training processes and modules. You must preserve them and continue to develop them.

It's important to consider the factors that led to the combination of marketing and human resources (HR) before defining HR marketing, as well as to consider why the HR function is focused on marketing strategies. What tools are utilized for marketing? What encourages the application of marketing to different HR functions? Companies and employees are under more and more pressure in a world that has been transformed by globalization, technology, sociocultural change, and demographic shift. The former seeks to entice and keep talent, while

the latter seek the finest opportunity.

The human resource's function, which is under pressure from two directions, is impacted. The HR functions at the core of all the paradoxes that employees encounter, caught in the crossfire and always having to handle new expectations, according to Serge Panczuk and Sébastien Point's(2008) description of the issue.

1.2 The concept of talent

The organization has a lot of problems with talent management. What goals does this strategy hope to achieve? What techniques and resources are available to find, develop, and keep talent?

Optimal personnel management is a key strategic advantage for a firm in a world where professions are being reinvented and formed at a rapid pace. Indeed, organizations must make sure they prepare for changes if they want to remain effective and competitive. Engaging staff in business dynamics, spotting, bringing out, and nurturing everyone's potential, helping them to grow, hone their abilities, and expand their knowledge... There are several levers at the disposal of managers and the HR function to enable everyone to develop fully. Because the firm can only hope to recruit fresh talents and, more importantly, maintain its own by nurturing the joy of work and delivering significance to all levels of the organization.

1. The definition of talent:

Since its inception, the definition of the concept of talent has undergone significant change. Reading through the meanings from several dictionaries is important to comprehend the latter:

According to (Andrieux-Reix, 2004; Rey, 2010), the term "talent" has its roots in ancient Greek, where it referred to a unit of weight. According on the region of the Empire and the values associated with the metal, it represented various values.

According to **Le Robert**, talent can be described as "an inclination, natural or acquired, to excel in something" or as "a notable aptitude in the intellectual or artistic sphere" or as "the literary or artistic gift (of someone) viewed in its own features."

A skill is an aptitude, or a specific capacity to achieve something, according to **Larousse**

Chapter 1: HR Marketing

(2013). additionally, it denotes "a noteworthy talent in the literary or creative realm; a gifted individual in such endeavors.

Larousse and Robert use words like aptitude, extraordinary or particular skill, and gift to define talent. Talent is always associated with a specific activity, and its source or origin might be either innate or learned a great aptitude in the arts or sciences is referred to as talent in the context of absolute employment.

According to Mirallès (2007), talent is "*individual brilliance in a certain activity plus difference*". According to him, if a person's competency is determined by what he or she is capable of doing, then their skill is determined by what they are able to do better than others.

Talent as a concept does not currently have a conventional definition; in fact, the definition of the word is rather extensive and broad.

Different authors and researchers hold different opinions about this matter. Some see talents as important individuals who are endowed with high potential and exceptional performance that allows them to stand out from the crowd. In other words, talent is performance and "excellence + difference." This is a category of employees who can quickly advance to positions of responsibility. Other researchers consider that talent is at the heart of every person, that is to say everyone is endowed with it, waiting for it to be discovered. "*Special, original skills, relating both to the exercise of a professional practice and to leadership potential*" (**Thévenet**).

The literature on science and management raises a number of queries regarding the definition of talent: Is talent inherited or learned? Is talent a more valuable skill?

Regarding the first query, Peretti (2009) cited Cardin and Guerin - Roussillon and Mirallès as saying that talent has an innate component but can be concealed. The ability to develop it is made possible by the individual's individual will and confrontation with situations.

Dejoux (2010, p. 85) contends that aptitude and intellect alone are insufficient for attaining new heights. So, starting with the intrinsic, talent cannot develop without cultivation. We can infer that if natural talent exists, the authors concur that it must be developed through cultivation.

Chapter 1: HR Marketing

Regarding the second query regarding talent and competence, Jol Kaddour provided clarification in his paper (Ethic job of June 07, 2009), "If we can talk about a skills assessment, we cannot talk about a talent assessment. Why? Because to have talent is to have a high potential, and that the potential is not acquired. Talent is a meeting between a person and a company and it is in this meeting that the conditions for expressing this potential are born. This is why a person can be deemed to be hyper competent for a position in a company, and turn out to be much less talented by occupying the same position in another company. It is clear that this distinction implies a questioning of the functional analysis of work "stations». But in fact, an approach in terms of talent implies a real "functional" analysis of the position (the important thing here is how the position works and its function for the company), whereas an approach in terms of competence had tendency to propose a functional analysis of the work "position" (the important thing here was to talk about the position and to make a checklist of the skills necessary for its occupation). Having talent therefore requires having skills, but being able to express your talent requires more than skills: you have to be the right person, in the right place, at the right time. »

We can therefore conclude that while talent and skill are not the same thing, they do complement one another.

My studies also piqued my curiosity in the idea of high potential and its connection to talent. Dictionary definitions of potential are available, but the concept of high potential, often known as High-Po or High Flyers, is first introduced in management literature.

High potential is a word commonly used in psychology to describe gifted children. Lautrey argues that "*a high potential is determined by a high IQ*" (*French Psychology 49, 2004, p. 226*). When it exceeds 130, an IQ is deemed high. Gift is a term used in American literature. It refers to the quality of having gifts. Renzulli on the other hand, divides great potential into three categories: strong academic ability, inventiveness, and dedication (*French Psychology 49 – 2004, p.227*)

Nevertheless, dictionaries and management experts appear to agree that potential relates to the idea of "being able to do" or "ability," and not of demonstrated skill (which is specific to talent).

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High potential is indeed defined as "a person who's the organization believes has the ability to take a leadership role" by Dejoux (2010, p.96). High potentials in this context refer to managers having managerial potential.

According to Miralles (2007, p. 89), "potential concerns the person in his very essence". We are high potential or we are not. "Talent certainly has the characteristics of potential insofar as talent initially appears as a set of latent qualities that only gradually reveal themselves [...] Talent belongs to the category of "high potential" in the literal meaning" but it is not restrictive to this category (Miralles, 2007, p.117).

These comments prompt us to consider the following: Is all talent potential?

The potential must be evaluated in accordance with three complimentary dimensions, according to Bournois and Roussillon, who were cited by Miralles (2007, p.118): its level (potential up to where), its type (potential to what), and the cost of its actualization (the price to pay for its development). *"What seems to characterize talent is primarily the level of potential of the individual,"* writes

According to Chapelier, Sartori, and Schmidt, motivation must be taken into account, and the psychological component of potential must be integrated. As a result, the concept of potential is defined at the individual level and is only interesting in terms of how it might evolve in a communal setting. Talent, potential, and skills are frequently used interchangeably with the many facets of human resources management. In this regard, a talented person will only be of interest to a company if he can show his brilliance while working with a group that shares the same organizational culture.

So, the definition of "Professional Talent" can be summed up as follows:

- Talent is discovered, nurtured, and expressed; it cannot be acquired.
- The so-called "talented" person has skills and talent; they are complementary. Talent is not just competence.
- Talent is "contextualized" in accordance with the concerns and demands of the

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firm. Talent is a "differentiating" ability, tied to personality, and it is what distinguishes people from one another beyond the skills they have mastered.

- You cannot transmit talent

2. Managing talent or talent management:

In order to adapt to changing trends and needs, talent management strategies have changed significantly throughout the years.

In today's changing climate, strategic people management is essential. The relationship between work, workers, and the workplace has experienced a rebirth as a result of global trends in talent and human resource management.

- Talent management: definition

The planned, meticulously managed process of bringing on the right personnel and assisting them in reaching their full potential while keeping the organization's objectives in mind is known as talent management.

Therefore, the process entails identifying talent gaps and openings, locating and onboarding qualified candidates, advancing them through the system and helping them develop the necessary skills, training subject matter experts in accordance with the future, and effectively engaging, motivating, and keeping them for the long term. The term emphasizes how talent management is holistic in nature, including all facets of workplace human resources while assuring organizational success.

To ensure the success of the organization, a number of components and sub processes that make up talent management must function. Identifying talent and candidates, integrating them, and then maximizing their talents and assets are a few examples of how to analyze talent gaps for the present and the future.

- New methods for managing talent

According to some authors, talent management refers to fresh, well-defined HR procedures. Others compare it to straightforward management strategies. Talent management entails

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implanting, recognizing, mobilizing, developing, and renewing abilities, according to BRY F. and GOURDON C.

By drawing a comparison to football, Mirallès (2007, p. 161) develops three talent management strategies, which are as follows:

1. To "recognize skills," one must be able to spot them (scouting).
2. "Exploit talents" means setting up the ideal settings for their unique expression (coaching) and knowing how to cast them to maximize their complementarities.
3. "Protect talents" means keeping them away from outside temptations (cocooning).

Dejoux and Thevenet (2010), for their part, divide management with talent into three phases: Attracting talent - Recruiting talent - Retaining talent.

We think that talent management introduces three new practices that can be better understood by understanding talent management techniques.

Attracting talent:

Create a strong employer brand.

- Identify and provide its employer offer.
- Use cutting-edge hiring techniques.
- Recognize your own strengths.
- External talent acquisition.

Recruiting talent:

- Create an integration procedure.
- Adhering talents to company culture
- Developing talent
- Proximity management
- Coaching

Retain talent:

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- Offer favorable working conditions
- Involve and motivate talents
- Develop a sense of belonging
- Recognize and value talents

In a nutshell, moving the company ahead. This is the goal of any talent management approach. HR and management place a high value on employees who contribute to the company's activities and support and strengthen it. These talents constitute a key component of the company's goal, which is why the latter must make significant efforts in HR communication and employer branding.

1.3 What is HR marketing

2. The source of HR marketing

The "unemployed" generation's entry into the workplace brings about new reflexes and expectations. The business can no longer guarantee or demand the consistency and allegiance of its personnel. The employees, on the other hand, have given up a certain naivete that allowed them to view the institutional messaging favorably from the start. In fact, the messages for a longtime emphasized ten-year career goals, linear wage increases, stability and commitment to the organization, etc. The new generations of workers born out of the crises of the 1980s and 1990s learnt mobility, career management, instability, and self- protection sometimes at their expense.

Additionally, there are new requirements and more obvious constraint systems. The current economic climate, globalization, and technical or socio-demographic changes impose pressure on not only businesses but also all employees. A few years ago, the labor market started to change (and the effort to retain people started). Under this simultaneous pressure from employees and the business, the human resources (HR) function itself is exposed to new expectations. Thus, it is the root of every paradox that employees encounter, including those relating to safety and performance, stability and change, conflicts and the need for social stability, balancing personal and professional lives, the need for references and the

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breakdown of those references, the need for references and the complexity of matrix organizations, the need for references and the short-term culture, the need for contacts and the development of the virtual world, and even the need for contacts and the development of the virtual world. The HR function becomes less and less discernible as a result of these conflicting or unreasonable expectations, organizational ambiguity, and the pervasive process culture since it is stuck in the middle and must continually manage new expectations. If the business has to reconsider its approach to persuasion (and seduction by its employer brand), the HR department must assess its positioning and, beyond that, its method to interacting with external and internal consumers. All of these ideas product, service, consumer behavior, market analysis, positioning, employer brand, etc. Share one thing in common: they are products of the marketing industry.

Philip Kotler defines marketing as “ *is a collection of methods and research projects that aims to anticipate, observe, trigger, renew, or excite customer demands in order to continuously adapt new commercial and industrial machinery to those needs*”. We are inherently disconnected from human resources. Even so...

This thesis addresses two sectors that don't frequently cross paths, but whose commonalities prompt us to invoke the phrase "HR marketing," the lever of this shift in the company's attitude toward its surroundings.

3. Definition of HR marketing's concept:

"HR marketing" is not a brand-new concept. Philippe Liger provides a rather broad definition of human resources marketing in his book on the subject, saying that it is the desire "to apply the logic and techniques of marketing and communication to attract candidates and retain employees." Utilizing marketing strategies for the well-known triple goal of human resources, i.e., recruiting, retaining, and keeping the best employees, is the fundamental cornerstone of HR marketing.

But this is simply the exposed portion of a vast iceberg that has never been thoroughly examined.

The term "HR marketing" may imply that the corporation approaches human resources in a

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"commercial «manner. The converse is true: the technical efficiency of marketing tools is what is sought in HR marketing. "When it comes to fulfilling the customer, we adopt a scientific and meticulous approach; similarly, when it comes to satisfying our staff, we leave nothing to chance," says the strategy.

While HR marketing is defined as the application of commercial marketing techniques to the sector of human resources. For the HRD, the approach entails approaching its many publics - employees, recruits, potential talents? - As customers. The goal of the HR marketing approach is to make the organization known in the job market, to attract talent, to foster employee loyalty and commitment, and to promote HR innovation.

HR marketing or human resources marketing covers the activities of HR departments which aim to "sell" the status of employee in the company in question to current or potential employees (recruitment).

HR marketing therefore has an internal target (employees) and an external target (potential candidates) and loyalty and acquisition objectives.

With regard to employees, HR marketing aims to make employee status and experience attractive and to promote loyalty and commitment.

With regard to potential candidates, the aim is to make the company attractive, in particular through an employer branding policy, and to use the most relevant "marketing" communication and recruitment channels such as inbound recruiting, for example. And recruitment communication. It is also about promoting the candidate experience.

4. Essentials about HR marketing: Social marketing is not HR marketing.

It is common to mix up social marketing and HR marketing. Social marketing, however, does not have anything in common with the definition of either the marketing or human resources fields. Social marketing is a way of thinking that aims to address the relationship between the employee and his employer in a different way from the perspective of human resources. Social marketing incorporates marketing technologies to assist the business in continuously challenging its viewpoint with that of its many stakeholders (mostly employees), even

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to the point of appealing to emotions. And it's frequently the brand that gives you permission to exploit feelings.

Additionally, the idea of employer branding serves as the cornerstone of the social marketing strategy, whereas the idea of the consumer (or client) and the segmentation strategy serve as the foundation of HR marketing. Only after a thorough examination of customer expectations and product distinction can a brand be created. Since social marketing "places people at the heart of the organization through clear, open and ethical communication," the location of communication is also highly maybe too crucial. As a result, the employer must pay attention to the employee. Social marketing works on the employee's affect register to make him feel good about the company. This certainly extends beyond a simple communication strategy and includes policies such as employee recognition, improved working environment, and even employee loyalty. We feel that social marketing reduces HR to a solely social role, when the actual reality of the function is more focused on the concept of performance, with the social dimension being only one tool among many.

Furthermore, the linkage of the terms marketing and social, or the focus placed on communication, risks restricting the role of human resource management (and HRD) in enhancing the company's social climate. This concept of giving purpose to work is taken up by HR marketing. However, while social marketing is grounded in a well-being perspective, HR marketing actually places the employee in a "market" approach, with the latter becoming the company's true internal client. So, the HR marketing's purpose is to focus on the concept of "customers," which is all too often misinterpreted by HR decision-makers.

HR marketing is not internal marketing, but it is inspired by it

The term "internal marketing" first originated in the 1980s, referring to a new way of thinking about using marketing tactics not outside the firm (externally), but within it. (Internally). This is a method focusing on employees, who are viewed as the bearers of the organization's success or failure. This is why internal marketing began in service organizations, which prioritize their personnel, putting them in direct contact with customers. Internal marketing assumes a parallel between commercial and organizational space, that is, between the client and the employee.

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Internal marketing views employees as a market to be conquered, and the latter are subsequently viewed as "internal customers."

Internal marketing can thus be defined as "a set of methods and techniques that, when combined in a three-phase action plan (understanding of the internal market, alignment with the needs of the external market, change management, and mobilization of men), will enable the company to have a capital of human resources capable of energizing and supporting its own development." Internal marketing is thus founded on a business connection between an individual and an organization.

In order to adopt a set of procedures and approaches that serve both the interests of consumers and employees, simultaneously, is the goal. Although the employees are seen as the management's initial customers, the end customer is still the primary target of the business's efforts to strengthen its consideration of its customers. So long as actions and principles are taken in direct cooperation with firm employees, the goal will remain of an economic nature: raising consumer happiness. The product that needs to be marketed is not just that of the business, but also that of its management, including the company's working environment, climate, and level of environmental richness, style of operation, brand, development goals, and initiatives, among other things. Internal marketing aims to be a comprehensive approach to human resource management, although it continues to be primarily oriented on education and communication in support of certain goals. Traditional hierarchical relationships are replaced by commercial relationships between the employee and his or her supervisor. This radically alters the relationship and emphasizes loyalty, long-term commitment, and trust. Therefore, one of the key goals of internal marketing is to address issues with employee engagement and motivation in day-to-day operations. To do this, it is necessary to alter workplace representations and behaviors, create a business-like connection between the employer and his employees, and ensure that the latter are happier at work. In this way, workers are likewise a market that the company must dominate this "customer mentality" and attitude centered on a market to be conquered are adopted by HR marketing. However, it is not internal marketing since HR marketing offers a more comprehensive or nuanced approach to the concept of the customer and goes beyond the simple notion of communication or even the merchant system.

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Hence, HR marketing suggests sharpening the focus on HRD. HR marketing is inspired by internal marketing and social marketing

From **internal marketing**, it borrows this reflection of considering the employee as well as all the stakeholders in a market relationship. It is for the HR department to sell and to sell itself.

From **social marketing**, it borrows this spirit of well-being and this desire to create a pleasant work environment in order to seduce. But human resources and the HR department must mobilize marketing tools more so as not to restrict this approach to the 10% of the visible surface of the iceberg, i.e. Communication.

HR marketing is at the confluence of marketing, human resources, and strategy.

The combination of marketing and human resources has also led to HR marketing. It also includes a tactical component. The various connections between strategy, marketing, and human resources are examined in this paragraph. Internal marketing sits at the nexus of human resources and marketing. Internal marketing is business-oriented communication, i.e., strategies for enlisting and encouraging staff (especially through the corporate culture to make them aware of the organizational identity).

From a conceptual standpoint, Per Olof Berg's work on what the author refers to as a symbolic management of human resources is responsible for one of the earliest links between marketing, human resources, and strategy. All attempts to culturally identify the business, i.e., to transmit its cultural identity both internally (to personnel) and externally, must be understood as "symbolic management" (other stakeholders). Per-Olof Berg advocates for complete integration of strategy, marketing initiatives, and human resources in particular. These connections give rise to three interconnected management trends: internal marketing, strategic management of human resources, and corporate advertising. Using the business culture as the foundation for both internal and external communication, symbolic management works in tandem with these three strategic axes. Per-Olof Berg sarcastically examines the dangers of manipulation and seduction that such an approach poses in the workplace with Mats Alvesson.

In order to affect the public perception of the company and to dominate the market, strategic marketing, which combines marketing and strategy, is used. A positive public image is

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advantageous to the firm's reputation, but it may also contribute to employee pride because a company that is well-known outside the company itself fosters engagement and unity there. Last but not least, strategic human resource mobilization promotes the alignment of HR policy with business strategy.

Figure 1: The mix of marketing and human resource's strategies

A real HR marketing approach, however, tends to demonstrate that the company's strategy, rather than its marketing department, is the primary source of inspiration. HR marketing exploits the relationship between strategy and marketing to inspire its own communication. The marketing department will serve more as a training and example resource to demonstrate how the HR department should behave (or even organize itself) in order to acquire an HR mentality. HR marketing also adds genuine value to the relationship between strategy and human resources by taking a global approach to customer analysis and developing answers that are tailored to the strategy's defined targets as well as to the expectations of those targets and organizational realities.

1.4 Marketing and human resources: an astonishing marriage

A few years ago, it was difficult to think that the human resources department would collaborate closely with the marketing department to enhance the company's brand image and attract employees. The company should not wait until they are in a crisis to try to discover solutions; instead, they should apply marketing techniques to their human resources function in order to prepare their reputation in the market and among all the competitors.

The role of HR has evolved a lot in recent years. Attract, engage and retain Top talent is a top priority for senior executives, and most companies Place this responsibility on HR. HRM corresponds well to an exchange between an employee who makes available to his employer his time, his work and his know-how and the company which pays him in return, by a certain number of tangible and intangible advantages.

Marketing is the set of techniques allowing to match the product offer of a company to consumers' expectations to optimize their sales. Changing requirements of consumers lead companies to constantly readjust their marketing policies and commercial and to integrate new communication media. In this context, marketers have a primary role in the business. Moreover, if it is widely accepted in marketing, the need for a company to retain its customers and acquire others, it is the same in HRM. Indeed, faced with an environment characterized by a war for talent and a risk of a shortage of heads / workforce, companies must stand out with an attractive HR policy for attract candidates and retain employees. This is the positioning of HR in the work called "HR Marketing".

The same techniques used to entice a client can also be used to seduce a worker.

It becomes vital to use marketing concepts in workforce management, such as being aware of competitors' and similar industries' hiring practices. The creation of the marketing strategy should focus on both recruiting new personnel and keeping hold of current ones. You need to create a distinct and "colorful" brand image in order to sell and stand out from the competitors. The core foundation of this image is the company's DNA. Its leadership's vision, the organization's mission, its values, culture, management style, and living conditions all

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contribute to its distinctiveness. By identifying one's DNA, one can play to their strengths and determine whether a candidate possesses the appropriate "genes" that fit with the company culture. « *The vast majority of the retention drivers have more to do with an organization's culture than its specific programs.* » (Towers Perrin, *World at Work Journal* 2006)

The marketing of human resources can therefore be defined as a process, a marketing tool applied to human resource management, this process takes into account all the elements human and internal and external organizational elements of people and companies.

The objective of HR Marketing is to optimize human resource management by making people much more passionate, much more engaged and motivated, allowing the company feedback on the management of human resources and allowing individuals to enrich themselves not only materially but also psychologically, intellectually and emotionally.

Human resources marketing takes into account sociological and technological developments, all the changes that are constantly taking place and this is the role of human resource managers; not just managing payroll, job descriptions, interviews ...

The real management of human resources is to integrate all this internal and external data on the psychological, physiological and marketing level to prepare and develop human resources on the future of the company. Liger, (2004) speaks of "human resources marketing", defined as "a new approach to the employee / company relationship which consists in considering employees (...) as customers in the noblest sense. It is about applying the logic and techniques of marketing and communication for:

- **Attract candidates, recruit them and integrate them well**
- **Retain the employees involved".**

2008 saw the proposal of a method by Serge Panczuk and Sébastien Point to their tour for better positioning HR within organizations. Based on the marketing expert Philip Kotler's theories, the method introduced employee segmentation, over-measuring of HR services, and care to be taken with distribution channels (2008, *Enjeux et outils du marketing HR*). They adopt Liger's strategy once more, but they use more exact methods. The most favored, well-

known, and recommended approach is Liger's.

Finally, HR marketing places the internal client a collaborator (a paid employee, an agent, or any other individual associated with an organization in the course of providing work or employment at the center of its concerns. This collaborator "relates" more to the organization than it costs to recruit, retain, and cultivate within the organization. The marketing of human resources is therefore the combination of strategies and tools used by an organization to develop, deliver, and communicate value to its current and potential customers, as well as to manage relationships with them in a way that is advantageous to the business and the employees.

1.5 The HR marketing approach

The HR department wants to satisfy present and potential employees, sell HR services, and maintain the longevity of business relationships with stakeholders by implementing the marketing approach. Segmentation and targeting must come first in order to accomplish this.

Segmentation

By breaking the market down into several groups based on consumer differentiation, the market may be understood. It enables the creation of a group of people who react to an offer in a similar manner (McDonald and Dunbar, 2004). In order to adjust the Rh, segmentation enables the HRD to categorize individuals based on homogeneous expectations.

Segmentation: performance

In order to segment depending on performance, a performance-type matrix with four categories reserve, impediment, star, and pillar must be created. The groups are chosen based on their potential and performance.

Segmentation: level of dedication

The interest in segmenting the workforce based on how devoted they are to the business is demonstrated by a second strategy. In a study, Watson Wyatt (2007) showed that it was possible to separate two segmentation axes: employee involvement and their perception of the value they create for the firm. The idea is to compute a score using the two axes in conjunction.

Segmentation: visibility and volume

Other criteria have started to show up in segmentation techniques, most notably the identification of a segment based on visibility and volume criteria (Igor Ansoff, 2007). The degree of a person's influence, his position in the hierarchy, and/or his involvement in decision-making are all related to visibility. Volume is another targeting factor that enables identification in terms of the population (employee percentage in the internal population of the organization).

Targeting

After the segmentation procedure is finished, the targeting procedure is used as a HR marketing tool. In order to perform actions tailored to the segments taken into consideration, it supports segmentation. According to Philip Kotler, the goal of a targeting policy is to choose the segments that will be the focus of study plans in order to improve the efficacy of marketing initiatives.

Positioning

Positioning the HR product is a crucial element in achieving the HRD objective, and it is in accordance with the HR marketing approach (segmentation and targeting). The first stage is to define the HR offer and decide which HR goods and services will be made available to both current and prospective workers. The distinction between HR products and HR services is the goal of the defining of the HR offer. In contrast to HR services, which are distinguished by their intangibility and generality, HR goods are all tangible items with a price and a commercial component.

1.6 The challenges of HR marketing

The HR function is no longer just about attracting, retaining and developing the best talent. The HR function must adopt the tools of the process in order to strengthen its credibility, it must thus rethink its modes of action, promoting a more holistic, customer-oriented approach, where organizational adaptability must replace the rigidity of the process. It must also be to sell.

Companies no longer have to wait until individuals apply one way spontaneous, they must

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target the type of employees they need and convince them to apply within their organization, something which implies differentiation and segmentation, such knowledge of their image inside and outside the company. This internal analysis allows the company to differentiate itself from its competitors in terms of the management of its human resources...

Philippe Liger offers a general definition in his book on Human Resources Marketing: it is a desire to "apply the logic and techniques of marketing and communication to attract candidates and retain employees >>the objective is therefore employee satisfaction and optimization of recruitment and retention for the company.

HR marketing is based on listening to employees, to define their demands and expectations, it is based on the collection and analysis of information while considering employees as one corporate targets. It also makes it possible to respond effectively to the three major challenges facing companies:

- **Employee engagement by finding ways of shared and lasting trust.**
- **Employee loyalty and capitalization on the talents already present in the company.**
- **The attractiveness of the company and its employer brand.**

The attractiveness of companies, as an employer, has become a priority, we must find objective elements that will constitute the identity of the company and differentiate it from other players in the same market: give meaning to its history, rediscovering its founding values and making them concrete on a daily basis, highlighting a welcome, integration and support program ... In short, a world was created to which people want to belong. Based on this observation, organizations will invest in research and development and information.

The first step will be to attract and integrate new employees. Generally speaking, the notoriety of the company is fragile and relative, it must be measured, reinforced or even build within certain SMEs. This notoriety will facilitate the recruitment of new employees, as well as their loyalty

- **Recruitment:**

You have to know your “employer image” to enhance it. The business of the company or its trades must be defined while ensuring a certain clarity in relation to the chosen positioning. This perspective allows the company to have staff with the necessary skills needed to meet their needs. The objective is to refine the HR marketing positioning. Then comes the choice of recruitment channels which corresponds to the determined target and which is in consistency with the employer image. In fact, everything depends on the desired level of selectivity, on the candidate sought. At this stage we can refine the recruitment process, better target its communication and optimize recruitment costs. The objective of this step is to personalize the relationship with the candidate.

- **Reception and integration:**

New recruits must then be welcomed and integrated into the company. To welcome this means, for example, providing a guided tour of the premises, with a welcome booklet for new employees. Ideally an integration seminar can be considered when the company recruit several people at the same time and must ensure that their integration is successful. The first less elapsed after recruitment and careful integration, enter online account for employee retention.

- **Retain the employee:**

Retaining its employees is becoming a major issue in human resources marketing. The employees are considered clients of the human resources department. Therefore, you have to succeed in listening their employers and understand their expectations and objectives. The two most important criteria often for employees are career opportunities within the company and life balance privacy / personal life. Having a competent workforce within the company is a competitive advantage. Duty replacing demotivated employees who have left the company represents a cost in terms of recruitment but also integration. For these reasons, we must reduce turnover, be aware that applications are scarce in many professions, and develop a management of loyalty. Building loyalty means motivating employees, involving them in the company and helping them to achieve personal individual development goals. We perceive a

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dimension emotional retention, which can be an enriching factor for the organization as a whole.

Professional and personal spheres are increasingly linked, and working conditions have a direct impact on the individual's balance. Employees are no longer solely motivated by salary level and career prospects, but many are sensitive to notions security, solidarity and ethics, which can give individuals the lost confidence in the future. The relationship is then seen as a win / win. Retaining your employees means giving those benchmarks, the possibility of choosing to get involved according to short-term outlook. Employees often have an ambivalent relationship with the organization: they want to benefit from training, be integrated into projects innovators, but may not necessarily want a career in the same company.

- **Manage careers:**

Career management can be defined as a policy of capital development Human of the company who leads to achieve the optimization of its efficiency. Practically, this is the setting up monitoring of employee career paths to improve their skills and retain them in the company. This implies the highlighting of a system staff assessment to identify potentials and skills and guide the employment planning management (GPEC). The company must provide the employee with development prospects. It doesn't have to be careers that make it possible to climb hierarchically, we are seeing more and more so-called careers "Plates". This means an evolution in the trades, thanks to training, according to the needs of the business or the wishes of the employee. The company implements procedures forecasts (training plan, career plan).

In this context, career management is a fundamental factor in the optimal use of human resources in companies for:

- Ensure profitability by developing the professional motivation of staff.
- Ensure its sustainability by compensating for inevitable departures and adapting to changing ages of its staff.
- Ensure its growth by spreading to the needs of creation of new workstations and responsibilities.

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-Satisfy the needs of workers in terms of promotion, consideration and Acknowledgement. Questionnaires exist, which make it possible to position employees, according to these anchors careers. It can be beneficial for the company to know where its staff are located, thanks to this reading grid, in order to target its loyalty actions in a timely manner.

- **Encourage and reward:**

Two types of solutions are available to reward employees: case-by-case solutions cases, which make it possible to reward a particular employee, and the overall rewards which affect all employees.

Building employee loyalty also means recognizing their work. It's important to mention that encouragement and rewards are a dimension to be taken into account in the management of human resources. Recognition should be given to all employees and not reserved for part of the staff. Speaking of reward and remuneration in company, we are thinking of raising wages. Of course, Salary is a good way to make an employee feel valued, by giving their work a fair value so as not to see them leave, but there are many other ways to reward a good element, which will sometimes be much more profitable.

The issue of compensation is sometimes presented as essential, but many people do not feel respected in their work and lack recognition. However, to encourage everyone and reward the most deserving, you need to know the employees, know what they accomplish on a daily basis and monitor them regularly. Initiatives should be welcomed and all suggestions taken into consideration.

In conclusion, profit is undoubtedly one of the main objectives of the company, but the social integration of individuals is also necessary to generate a certain political stability in the organization and optimization of resources. HR marketing thus becomes a strategic issue, for companies and for society. Applying the rules of marketing to human resources management is essential in a context of intense international competitiveness, to recruit the best people and develop them within the company. There are two important sets of business and employee needs to consider in the human resource planning process and workforce development.

1.7 Human resources marketing strategy

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The HR marketing strategy is a blueprint that will focus on the future of the company, for achieve generally quantifiable objectives that will address the different parts of the company, has its different departments. To develop an HR marketing strategy, therefore, go through different stages namely: a diagnosis, setting of objectives, the choice of fundamental options in terms of targeting and positioning following a segmentation operation and finally the formulation of marketing mix and its evaluation. The goal is to create an employer brand.

- **The initial diagnosis:**

This is the first action of HR marketing, its foundation is based on employee orientation in other words, customers, they must be at the heart of strategic thinking, not only concerning their current expectations and needs but also their needs in the future.

Customers are an important stakeholder in the business. The strategy is to create added value for all of its stakeholders the customer of course, but also shareholders, since they will seek profit in particular, along these stakeholders we can cite other: (employees, unions, shareholders, establishment's education, social organizations ...) the purpose of HR marketing is to design, deliver and develop HR services. In this sense, the development of a diagnosis remains one of the key points on which it is necessary to base design an effective HR marketing strategy.

- **HR segmentation and targeting**

Like any marketing approach, that applied to the management of people requires the carrying out two types of market studies: the first is internal in nature and aims to understand the needs and expectations of the "employee" the second is external in nature and aims to move to "The hunt for talent" and promote a good employer image with the various partners and the generalpublic.

The study of this market encompasses sociological and psychological methods that allow analysis of individual and collective behavior. It is a useful source of information for decision making in HR marketing. The HRD must therefore have recourse to new techniques including segmentation and targeting. The human resources director proceeds to segment the market into

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a sub-set homogeneous, the objective being to offer each of these segments a marketing plan adapted to their expectations. The segmentation strategy is aimed at different customers according to their specific characteristics, companies adopt studies in order to study and qualify consumers and adapt the discourse and products to the expectations of individuals.

Several typologies can allow the identification of customers in the HR function. Allows the distinction between internal and external customer. Internal clients are linked to the company by an employment contract according to their status, hierarchical level, their management role or their mode of attachment to the organization, as for external customers, they are hardly linked to the company by an employment contract and may be made up of potential candidates, establishments education, social organizations, shareholders ...

The second typology is in the decision-making system of the organization, the role of customers is fundamental. We thus distinguish decision-makers (CEO, HRD or manager), prescribers (who play a key role in the distribution of HR services, managers), users (are at the end of the chain, beneficiaries of HR services, employees, candidates for example) and payers (budget holders or controllers). And finally comes the last typology that distinguishes between individual clients and organizational clients.

Each organization chooses the segmentation criterion that seems relevant to it, the goal is to retain segmentation based on lifestyle, engagement as well as performance, and potential. After segmenting comes the targeting step, which allows concentration on segments profitable for the organization. These two strategies make it possible to attract internal and external customers of the company who will also be seduced by the social climate, condition of remuneration, and by the employer brand.

- **The HR marketing mix**

It is about implementing the marketing mix through the determination of the HR offer, price and HR service, implementation of an appropriate distribution and communication policy and efficient The HR offer: this is the first pillar of the marketing mix, it makes it possible to satisfy targeted customers, HR function must demonstrate innovation and develop its services, it must also meet the specific expectations of the various targets The distribution of the HR offer:

distribution is the function that puts goods and services at the available to the user under conditions of place, time, size ... Suitable for this, it plays an essential role in the process leading to the sale, it is a strategic function that substantially determines the results of the company. The products produced are generally transported to the final consumer by intermediaries. HR communication: it consists of transmitting messages to targets in order to modify their attitudes, behaviors or their images of the company, the HRD cannot selling without communication it therefore plays an important role in promoting the HR offer and in the development of the employer brand.

- **Build the employer brand**

The notion of employer brand started to develop from the 90s as a response the problems of attracting and retaining human resources. Several writings have been reserved for him, the book by Simon BARROW and Richard MOSLY entitled "The employer brand" remains a major benchmark in this regard. Develop an employer label of benchmark has other benefits for the organization. It allows him to save money recruitment, increase the level of skills, optimize performance and improve attracting consumers to its products.

1.8 Employer brand and its objectives and benefits

Employer brand refers to the perception that employees have of a firm whose culture is tied to its past. Customers, suppliers, and individuals who could be potentially intriguing and crucial to the brand's recruiting are included in the list of both internal and external stakeholders. The administration of human resources and hiring for a corporation are both considered to be part of the employer brand. Companies, from start-ups to large groups, including VSEs-SMEs, are increasingly appreciating it as they realize how important it is to invest in putting appropriate communication in place in order to recruit and retain talent. This includes both internal and external communication with the workforce.

It is a strategy that will be represented in the company's reputation, values, organizational structure, and communication, particularly internal and "corporate." This approach must include all of a company's stakeholders in addition to potential new hires, despite its focus on recruitment. Enhancing the employee experience is another goal of the employer branding

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strategy. All internal and external stakeholders of the company, including partners, public agencies, institutions, universities, external recruiters, and occasionally even rival companies, are targeted by the employer brand. These stakeholders include employees, managers, candidates, and partners. The employer brand, however frequently mistaken with the corporate identity or the EVP (employee value proposition), is a distinct idea. The EVP denotes the value provided by a business in exchange for an employee's labor, whereas the employer identity is a part of the employer brand and is only descriptive of the business's activities, size, products, and geographic reach.

Nowadays, candidates may easily find out information about companies, salary, or working conditions with only a few clicks thanks to the rise of digital tools. Therefore, it's important to keep this information under control by creating an engaging and transparent conversation and highlighting the company's values and commitments (particularly in terms of CSR). The company is more likely to draw the types of candidates it needs if its reputation is better. Additionally, workers who are persuaded by the HR discourse and practices used by their organization are more likely to value them. They should be viewed as the employer brand's natural ambassadors rather than having their range of expression limited.

Beyond its function in HR marketing, the employer brand is integral to the overall perception of the business.

With the technological advancement nowadays, the business must be active and visible across all platforms for communication, including the web (via a website or company page) and social media, where feedback is disseminated quickly. In order to effectively manage your employer brand and not miss any recruitment possibilities, you must build your reputation.

With regard to the etymology of the notion of employer brand, at a conference in Harrogate, Simon Barrow used the phrase "*Employer Brand*" for the first time. An employer brand is defined as « *the package of*

Functional, economic and psychological benefits provided by employment, and identified with the employing company » (Barrow & Ambler, 1996)

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Also, employer branding, according to Philip Liger, refers to all organizational and social innovations created to create a long-lasting relationship with employees in order to make the business an appealing employer and turn its name into a genuine brand connected with values.

Employer brand is described as:

- A collection of practical, psychological, and financial advantages (Ambler & Barrow, 1996, p187)
- An offer of employment (Franca & Pahor, 2012, p86)
- A name and a face (Weinrich et al., 2011, p 403)

Figure 2: Top element of the employer brand Data source: Hinge research institute

4 main pillars form the foundation of the employer brand:

- 1- **The external employer image:** The perception of the organization as an employer among external parties is limited to its external employer image. This means that it is intended for candidates, as well as for schools, colleges, alumni

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networks, influencers, journalists, media, recruiting agencies, etc.

- 2- **The internal employer image:** This is how internal stakeholders view the company as an employer, according to the company. Every internal employee, manager, HR, management, and social partner is the target audience. Based on these individuals' impressions of their employers, both internally and externally, is the internal employer image.
- 3- **Employer identity :** it is based on the factual components of the company's DNA that describe and characterize the organization, such as its activity, its goods or services, its trades, its history, its size, its principles, its type of structure, its management style, the regions in which it operates, etc.
- 4- **Employer practices:** Here, we refer to all of the company's HR procedures (such as hiring, integrating, training, evaluating, and compensating employees) as well as the administrative approaches that daily enhance the employer brand.

So when it comes to building a company's employer brand, the strategy must be developed neither by the marketing department nor the HR, but rather the two departments together: it would be ideal to build an employer brand. In the company, marketing teams are in charge of finding the messages and successfully communicating them in a coherent way to all stakeholders. Marketing knows what a brand is and how to define it, it does this to determine the brand visible to customers.

HR them, know the employer identity and all its characteristics and it is also to them that the employer brand will benefit the most. The HR function is the first point of contact for candidates, they are the ones who give the first impression. HR are also those who implement company policy and disseminate its values. In actuality, marketing should advise and assist HR in developing the employer brand. Additionally, HR divisions are being urged to collaborate with marketing and pick up some of their expertise in order to complete projects. Both roles should collaborate to develop a cohesive strategy or improve an existing one because they collectively have the knowledge and skills to communicate some aspects of the employer brand.

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However, there is still one more stakeholder that should not be forgotten during the process: the workers. Certainly not their responsibility, but they make the ideal brand ambassadors for the organization when it comes to distributing the employer brand strategy!

According to the criteria given above, employer branding is the fusion of four components meant to enhance the company's reputation both internally and externally.

Figure 3, Taken from: the so-called "employer picture diamond," illustrates these components (David Bickerton, 2000)

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1.4 The generation concept

Etymology:

Age cohorts are used to categorize generations. A cohort is a group of people who were all born around the same time and who over time have had comparable social experiences. This idea has primarily been postulated by English-speaking scholars who found in the generational concept a means of comprehending Nazism.

“Age cohorts are groups of individuals who were born around the same time and share similar experiences as they age, influencing their attitudes, behaviors, and perspectives.” Said **Ryder, N. B.** (1965) in his review (The cohort as a concept in the study of social change. *American Sociological Review*, 30(6))

It is more challenging to give the date of birth as much weight in the consciousness of a generation or in the concept of a generational conflict when age and event intersect. Only age groupings are relevant. When it comes to the phenomenon of generation, the biological cycle of life and death becomes quite simplified. The idea of using the concept of political generation which consists of a cohort of individuals who, due to shared historical events during their formative years, develop similar political attitudes and behaviors through the interaction of the life cycle (age), event (period), and cohort (time) effects was first put out by two American sociologists. These three approaches must be linked in an interactive system to show the connections between these various impacts when they are combined in order to make this definition operational for both generation and political generation.

This Age cohorts, is a concept primarily postulated by English-speaking scholars, are used to categorize generations based on comparable social experiences. Specific scholars, such as **Karl Mannheim**, a German sociologist who made significant contributions to the understanding of generations and the sociology of knowledge. In his work "Essays on the Sociology of

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Knowledge" (1923) and "Man and Society in an Age of Reconstruction" (1940) and the Americans **William Strauss** and **Neil Howe**, American authors and historians known for their research on generational cycles and the impact of generations on history. They co-authored several books, such as "Generations: The History of America's Future, 1584 to 2069" (1991) and "The Fourth Turning: What the Cycles of History Tell Us about America's Next Rendezvous with Destiny" (1997). These authors introduced this idea to comprehend the impact of Nazism. To illustrate, after the First World War, a political generation emerged, comprising cohorts of activists shaped by the same historical epoch. Examples include Germans who, post-1918, engaged politically in various ideologies like Social Democracy, Communism, or Nazism, influenced by events like the Russian Revolution and the German Revolution of 1918–1919. This concept of political generation, blending age, period, and cohort effects, was initially proposed by the American sociologists **William Strauss** and **Neil Howe**.

How can this be explained if we believe, like the two American sociologists, that there was a political generation, such as after the First World War? What cohorts can we designate in this historical context and who were those who engaged politically (life cycle impact) if this conflict was the catalyst for the men who experienced it from close or distant to join in politics? Consider the activism of Germans after 1918. The commitment could be Social Democratic, Communist, or even Nazi. The 1917 Russian Revolution adds to the First World War's significant event in terms of communist involvement. The German Revolution of 1918–1919, the KPD's foundation, October 1923 in Hamburg, unemployment, social injustice, the 1929 financial crisis, the development of Nazism, and a period spent in jail for his communist political views and activities or for opposing Nazis may also be included, though.

In conclusion, a political generation is made up of a generational cohort of activists exposed to the same historical epoch and brought together by age groupings. The socialization experiences that the cohorts that make up an engaged political generation are exposed to set them apart from other generations in society. On the other hand, there are clearly discernible mini-groups or micro-cohorts within a cohort, following the German example of the militant cohort (Communists, Nazis, and Social Democrats). It is still unclear exactly how some of these

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"micro-cohorts" turned into communists, while others turned into Nazis or even social democrats.

The actual use:

In general, we use the terms generation X, Y, or other to refer to people of a specific age group, such as generation Y in Morocco, who lived between 1980 and 2000. However, this demographic approach misses the true meaning of the term. As a result, sociologists favor a definition that focuses on attitudes and values in various contexts. These views are about job, money, family, hierarchy, and so on. According to this viewpoint, each generation has quite different expectations, socio-styles, and horizons. In comparison to past generations, Moroccan generation Y, like in the rest of the globe, has highly specific features and behaviors that influence their professional path while also forcing organizations to reconsider their methods and attitudes toward these young people.

It is the most educated generation of all, very adept at using ICT, very impatient, independent and emancipated, eager to be heard and respected, self-assured, with a taste for change and innovation, very tolerant of diversity, demonstrating a keen interest in social interactions, expressing recognition of authority when it is based on competence, with the capacity to perform multiple tasks at once, looking for careers as much as for jobs, and for training opportunities as much as possible. On the other hand, two criticisms of generation Y's youth are frequently made. First, they are not loyal to their employer (i.e. the tendency to change the employer for better working conditions). The second critique is that when they do not receive adequate and prompt rewards, they become demanding and revolutionary.

2.2 The use of the letter Y

There are various ways to explain how the letter Y is used. The idea that the Y generation is an evolution of the X generation has been advanced by some. Others use the term "Y" to describe how portable music players' headphones seem.

In an editorial in the American advertising journal *Advertising Age*, the phrase "Generation Y" first appeared. The article is a robot portrait of a young ethical consumer who is devoted

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but receptive to marketing messages rather than a sociological examination of this age group.

Although many of the assumptions in this classification are correct, some of them are due to significant geopolitical factors. For instance:

- They did not have to live with the impending conclusion of the Cold War.
- They had no prior exposure to a world without AIDS.
- They were sufficiently immature during the widespread adoption of consumer computing to have developed an intuitive command of technology that typically exceeds that of their parents (hence the term "digital natives"). However, they have had some computing experiences without internet.
- They arrived along with the emergence of widespread interest in environmentalism (which had previously been the concern of a minority).
- In contrast to generation X, who occasionally still viewed video games as fringe, for them, they are a common form of amusement.

Other features are more broadly influenced by the local environment.

Other characteristics depend more broadly on the geographical context. Anti-austerity movement in Spain. It is logical that each generation is different from the others. But it may seem excessive to make the generation difference a more decisive determinant of behavior, among other things, than belonging to social classes, cultures, territories, etc. The existence of specificities in Y's relationship with work has not been demonstrated. The works that focus on this generation are more descriptive than explanatory or comparative. Studies that attempt to compare different generations are rare. The only one carried out on a French sample (Jean Pralong) also concludes that there are no differences between the Xs and the Ys in the relationship to work, the company and the career. Comments that attribute specific characteristics to Generation Y are also studied as a managerial ideology (François Pichault). The Center for Studies and Research on Qualifications (CEREQ) sociologist Nathalie Moncel from France highlighted the wide range of circumstances that young people face when looking

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for work in 2011. As she focuses on "beginners on the labor market," she makes a distinction between a "youth who struggles and about whom we talk," a "hardworking and silent youth," and this "generation Y," or "this new youth," made up of graduates from the schools of commerce and engineering, which account for only 6% of young people.

Another approach to explain the use of the letter Y is to pronounce it "why" in English. Other terms like "Digital Natives," "Echo's Boomers," "children of millennials," and "Nexters" are also used.

2.3 What age group?

Sociologists like Neil Howe and William Strauss in their book "Generations: The History of America's Future divide the four types of generations that make up 21st-century society:

- People born between 1946 and 1965 are referred to as baby boomers.**
- **People born between 1965 and 1980 are referred to as generation x.**
- People born between 1980 and 2000 are referred to as generation y.**
- And generation Z are those who were born after 2000.**

Knowing the traits of each of these generations from the East and comparing technical advancements there is crucial to comprehend how Generation Y functions.

Because technological advancements have never stopped since the American invention of the Internet in 1969 and the debut of the system in Europe in 1985. (The first website went live on the internet on December 20, 1990, and this is when the global wide web initially appeared.)

The several generations impacted by this extremely dynamic period are strongly influenced by historical developments, technological advances, and social changes.

These generations have seen a rapid change in each of them in just 15 years, including changes to their values and modes of operation.

Baby boomers

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The generation born after World Wars 39/45. They know how to work hard, they were born between 1946 and 1964. They anticipate compensation commensurate with their participation and effort, similar to the aid provided to help the nation recover from the war. Also, they are aggressive competitors who typically desire to be recognized for their expertise.

The X Generation

Gen Xers are career-focused individuals who were born between 1965 and 1979, right after the baby boomers. They prioritize employment that will make them feel good about themselves. They have the option of choosing to put in a fair amount of time at work while yet having a family. Professionally speaking, this generation has had trouble securing a stable, well-paying position.

As a result, their work is no longer their primary concern; rather, they work to live (well-living) rather than the other way around. Full employment and recklessness came to an end in 1973 as a result of the stock market and oil disasters. Many people want to stay employed, even at the expense of unfavorable social or professional situations, in order to avoid suffering unemployment. Despite a potential reorientation toward greater career and personal fulfillment, they overwhelmingly give up. The generations after us are less committed to holding a permanent employment with the same employer for the whole of their careers and are instead more mobile.

This generation, which is egotistical, stressed, and less adaptable to new conditions due to fear of losing their jobs, places work at the center of their concerns. On the other hand, she participates in her business, takes on duties, and makes a lot of decisions. The idea of being a part of the company's brand has grown to be significant and uniting, and the employer now promotes and uses it for the sake of productivity.

The Y generation: Millennials

"Millennials" or "digital natives," who were born between 1980 and 2000, are commonly referred to as members of Generation Y. Computer monitors and video gaming consoles were a part of their upbringing. They are the first generation to have been totally and completely

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conceived in the age of the internet. In all spheres, both private and public, both digital and television are commonplace in this generation.

Although they avoid confrontation with authority figures, millennials are friendly, communicate, and share information with ease. The introduction of "the need for a rest phase" to "decompress" has been successful in shifting the focus away from work as the main focus.

They no longer hesitate to switch employers in their pursuit of a high quality of life, even if it means moving to new cities or even nations. Generation Y has been able to adapt and benefit from this complete reworking of the socio-professional model up until then, a reference for previous generations, despite a challenging economic model with its periodic structural crises.

Generation Y is always looking for the perfect spot to fit in. Generation Y is more qualified than their parents and grandparents, and they don't hold back when it comes to training and self-evaluation in order to advance in their careers.

She prioritizes enjoying the action and giving everything, she has to it. The maxim "win-win" serves as their everyday leitmotiv. Due to new digital technology, they are very materialistic, engaged in hyper consumption, and accessible to the outside world.

The definitions of Generation Y that are used the most frequently in the literature seem to favor using time as a criterion. While there is agreement on an age classification, the de-limitations that the writers present are anything but uniform.

Z generation

Because it was born after the year 2000 and has not yet entered the job market, Generation Z is the youngest of the generations. It is referred to as the quiet generation. Their daily lives are dominated by technology; they were raised with it and cannot function without it. They mostly communicate with one another online, whether it be for personal or professional reasons.

This generation is always linked. She only uses social networks to identify herself. For them,

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life and work must be a fluid process that gives wellbeing to daily existence. This makes them far more realistic than their forebears.

Organizations like Harris Interactive, Gallup, and other polling organizations estimate that in 2023, Generation Y consists of people between the ages of 21 and 35, Generation X includes people between the ages of 36 and 55, the Baby Boomers between 56 and 70 years old, then the elders those who are over 70 years old.

2.4 The characteristics of Generation Y

Jean Twenge, a psychologist and professor at San Diego State University, wrote about millennials and later generations, highlighting behavioral trends based on longitudinal data; and Catherine Hakim, a British sociologist who studied social change, including attitudes towards work and personal life, which has implications for different generations. In this paragraph we will talk about the characteristics of generation y by combining the ideologies of these two authors.

a) Who are the Moroccan generation Y we will characterize for our study?

The millennial generation is the first to have grown up during the "digital revolution," which gave rise to the internet as a platform for political action and the dissemination of freedom and globalization ideas. The power of social media, in particular, to subvert long-standing conventions has been seen by Arabs, who have noted the unprecedented action of American millennials to show sympathy with Palestinians against the Israeli assault on Gaza. Even though there was political blowback and this movement was hijacked by establishment players (mostly Islamist parties), millennials in the Arab world successfully opposed dictatorships during the Arab Spring. On the other hand, the cultural changes brought forth by social media are more profound and less apparent.

In contrast to the Arab Spring, which has prompted hundreds of books, articles, and films from Western observers, the more subdued cultural revolution brought forth by the internet is receiving less attention. Actually, the reason this Cultural Revolution is prospering right now is that, for the most part, it is managing to go mostly unrecognized by both establishment officials and outside observers.

Morocco is one significant example of this phenomena. In contrast to many Middle Eastern

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nations, the government has chosen not to impose internet usage controls. Moroccan millennials use tablets, PCs, and smartphones many of which have 4G connections to access the internet. Due to high demand, the majority of public spaces, including cafés and restaurants, now provide free Wi-Fi. Even free internet access is available inside the boundaries of El Jadida city. A change in attitudes and expectations within Morocco has been especially fueled by the robust internet ties that exist between the Moroccan Diaspora population in France and the people who still reside there. Moroccan youngsters are keen to bring the free and democratic system of France to their own nation so they can enjoy the same rights and benefits that this Western democracy offers to its Moroccan expats and immigrant children. Online, social justice, personal freedom, fair opportunity, political representation, and accountability that is, complete democracy all seem alluringly close at hand.

b) Portrait and characteristics of the Moroccan generation y:

The primary sources of influence for "young Moroccan millennials," also known as generation Y, are their family: 81% of them cite family, 74% of friends and coworkers, and 58% cite culture and religion. This is the conclusion drawn from a recent AMMC research. In fact, according to a study conducted by the Moroccan Association of Marketing and Communication (AMMC) and the Kantar company Millward Brown, "young women are more influenced - even pressured - by social culture and religion, while young men are significantly more attached to celebrities and athletes, with Ronaldo and Messi as main influencers or role models."

The survey was conducted among young millennials, aged 14 to 25, in big Moroccan cities and a representative sample of diverse socioeconomic strata. These young people "seek influence in real, close personalities, considered credible and with a very clear and more relevant story," according to the data. Not unexpectedly, research also comes out that "Young Moroccan millennials are interested in engaging in social media activities from their mobile devices; in conversations or get-togethers with friends; or even in engaging in enjoyable activities like watching TV, playing video games, or listening to music." Millennials engage in nearly comparable activities depending on their socioeconomic level. Generally speaking, even when they are around family, young people are searching for low-cost hobbies that let them release their energy or withdraw into their own world.

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Two primary profiles emerged from the study's segmentation of this generation: the "the good people" and the "determined."

- Of the young individuals surveyed, 46% fall into the first category. Features: Emotional and easily swayed, with somewhat average socio-professional categories (CSP) and cultural level. These individuals mostly want to be regarded and accepted by their peer group.

- Intermediate to high CSP and a decent level of education make up the second category, which around 38% of individuals questioned fall into. The "determined" want to set themselves apart by having a unique personality and possessing superior knowledge. The findings show that "their activities are more oriented towards continuity, commitment and impact."

Regarding brands, young people divide them into groups based on their degree of personal connection and on more focused product criteria, such as the need for inherent quality or a sense of distinction and originality that makes them valuable as buyers. Food and beverages fall under the category of "basic" products in this sense, yet consumers are still searching for items that offer good value for their money. Even if banks and insurance firms are still unwelcoming, young people are still searching for something special that is tailored to them. The big foreign companies in their favorite categories fast food, beverages, leisure, etc. are the ones that these young people believe best suit their demands. Furthermore, as 74% of respondents indicate they are confident about Morocco's future and happy to be Moroccans, the poll also demonstrates that "young people's vision of their country is relatively positive".

Additionally, 9 out of 10 young people believe they are prepared to make changes in order to personally contribute to the growth of their nation: 95% mention changing one's mindset, 93% desire to engage in charitable work or other acts, and 89% mention working for a project staff. "Young people remain realistic and recognize, often after debate, that change is everyone's responsibility, provided there is hope conveyed by a 'mentor' or a model who inspires them" , concludes the findings of the research.

c) What is the difference between the generation Y and the other generations?

Generational characteristics provide insight into common trends that define different generations, although individual variations still exist. Generation Y, also known as Millennials, are notable for

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their immersion in technology, having grown up with the rapid emergence of the Internet and social media. Millennials are often considered the first truly “digital” generation. Additionally, this cohort tends to be more educated, with many individuals pursuing higher education. Social engagement and concern for environmental causes are also characteristics often associated with Generation Y. Professionally, Millennials value flexibility at work and seek collaborative environments, emphasizing a work-life balance and personal life. Diversity and inclusion are also important values for this generation.

Generation X, on the other hand, is often seen as more independent, having grown up in an era where traditional family structures have evolved. Although they have adopted technology over time, Generation X has not grown up with it in the same way as Generation Y. They are often characterized by a certain skepticism and cynicism towards institutions and authorities. Generation X also values work-life balance, but in a more pragmatic way.

Generation Z, the next cohort, is distinguished by total immersion in digital technology from a very young age. Born after the 2000s, members of Generation Z are often described as digital natives. They are characterized by their widespread use of social media and their adaptability to technology. Generation Z is also often seen as focused on social activism and has a broader global perspective. Zs place a high value on inclusion, diversity, and are often seen as independent and creative learners.

The requirements and expectations of Generation Y in the workplace

Understanding millennials aspirations for their careers and how they behave can help us refine our characterization of them.

A strong sense of unity

Despite their tendency toward self-centeredness, members of Generation Y need to develop socially in order to grow as a group. When they are working on a project that is important to them, their sense of teamwork is strong. Therefore, it may appear overly simplistic to

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categorize Generation Y as an individualist in order to define it.

A generation in search of meaning

The involvement of millennials in a business project can be limitless as long as it makes sense to them and they can develop their skills. This generation refuses to plunge body and soul into a project in which it does not believe. Involved in strong and responsible values, the individuals who make it up want to evolve in a collaborative business context that resembles them, which relies on human capital and in which they can identify to flourish.

A need for autonomy

Even while she fully embraces her desire for support and for hierarchically structured feedback that is both regular and constructive, this generation shows a significant need for freedom and flexibility in relation to the corporate projects that it has implemented. It is crucial for these people to understand that they have our complete trust in regards to the task they have been entrusted with within a framework. Without the trust of their hierarchically superiors, it is ultimately impossible to keep them loyal.

A volatile side of Generation Y

In addition to the previously listed factors, these people have some difficulty maintaining their attention on a single task for an extended period of time both at work and outside of it. There is too much of a need for change and diversion for them.

As a result, unlike prior generations, this generation is required to work in project mode rather than single-task mode. We also see that few people even entertain the thought of working their entire careers for the same organization.

Barriers are being broken down by this generation. These people have a strong desire to learn more about the world and to advance their careers. Their curiosity sometimes pushes them to work abroad for well-known corporations or start-ups, where they may watch their careers expand.

The creation of immediateness

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Many members of this generation's impatience are fueled by the digital. These people are used to having rapid access to the information they need and the ability to consume it even before an actual need arises thanks to automation. Their expectations of the professional world, namely in regards to the standard of living and communication at work, betray this habit.

Millennials emphasize the necessity to create a balance between their professional and personal lives after witnessing baby boomers get active in their businesses in order to avoid reaping the rewards of their hard work. There is no doubt that they are willing to contribute significantly to a firm, but only in the event that it also takes into account their innate demands. They function in a satisfied-satisfied relationship and never offer anything until they are certain of receiving anything in return.

Large salary expectations

Contrary to popular belief, this generation values money highly. Thus, even though it is no longer the only deciding factor, their commitment is mostly determined by their pay.

2.5 Dealing with generation Y

The ideal management of this particular demographic can be summed up in one word: participative. This will help us better grasp Generation Y and its definition.

For you, the managers, it is obvious that this entails allowing these people the chance to share their opinions, participate in project decision-making, and thereby demonstrate their leadership.

This generation is unaffected by paternalistic authority because it is aware of what it wants and is not scared to look elsewhere if an employer does not provide it with the ideal profession.

How can you retain Generation Y?

A corporation must provide him with some internal mobility and involve him in decision-making whenever possible in order to keep and maximize the involvement of an employee by limiting turnover as much as possible. With the recognition given to them, these people perform much more effortlessly. In fact, the more they feel valued and heard by their

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superiors, the more engaged they will be and the better the results will be. Give them the option of an equal partnership within the framework of a horizontal management style that allows for initiative from the moment of recruitment.

Here are some tips for managers to deal with the generation Y:

a) Be open to dialogue with her.

These young employees must be able to voice their opinions and participate in corporate life through the internal tools provided by the business (particularly the intranet and social networks). Growth and productivity can also be produced through the global business culture. It is now beyond disputing that co-construction is a significant advantage for the successful growth of contemporary businesses.

Create Opportunities to Bond

Employers often express concerns about Generation Y, asserting that many individuals, particularly the younger members, may not exhibit the same level of commitment to their jobs as previous generations did at a similar age. It's essential to acknowledge that, like any generation, Gen Y individuals seek employment to sustain themselves financially and cover their expenses.

Given their upbringing, Gen Yers tend to gravitate towards workplaces that provide a sense of belonging and a familial atmosphere. Creating an environment that fosters connection and camaraderie is crucial for appealing to this generation.

Gen Y employees value a strong bond with their superiors. In this context, you play the role of a concerned coach going beyond the traditional "benevolent boss" but stopping short of being a "loving parent." While the manager must enforce adherence to rules, task completion, meeting deadlines, and contributing to the organization, it's equally important to provide support and guidance.

Acknowledging achievements with praise is vital when Gen Y employees meet expectations. Conversely, if they fall short, the manager role is to step into a coaching position. Similar to their experiences in school and at home, where teachers and parents provided assistance and counsel, the team leader will do the same in the workplace. However, if performance issues persist and

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expectations aren't met, unlike parents, manager may have to make the difficult decision to terminate their employment.

b) Tell It Like It Is

Unlike older generations such as Traditionalists and Baby Boomers, who had to compete for every award, Generation Y received trophies just for showing up. This has led to a perception that they might struggle with adversity because they've had it too easy. While this may be true for some, Generation Y has also witnessed significant tragedies, from the Columbine High School shooting to the events at Virginia Tech.

Generation Y values truth, and avoiding difficult realities doesn't help their development or build trust. When assigning them a challenging task, be upfront about the difficulty but explain why you believe they can handle it. If they make mistakes, let them know and provide guidance on how to improve in the future. This approach fosters their growth and enhances their trust in you.

c) Make Gen Y-Friendly Regulations

Rules are necessary for any setting to function properly, yet some of them are as antiquated as radio tubes and eight-track players. Remove these illogical rules. Apply the "Why" test if you find that you spend a lot of time explaining rules to Generation Y or if you observe that they spend a lot of time attempting to find ways around regulations. Consider why the relevant rule is significant. Change it or get rid of it if it has no effect on sales, customer service, quality, safety, or cost. As much as you can, cultivate an atmosphere that appeals to Generation Y.

d) Be Aware of Virtual Workplaces

For Baby Boomers, work is life. Xers need to work to make ends meet. For members of Generation Y, life and work are one and the same. There is a noticeable difference between working in person and working remotely for the majority of Baby Boomers and many Gen Xers. On a Sunday night at ten o'clock, a Gen Yer feels at ease being at home, adjusting his blog, checking Facebook, and submitting a report to a customer with a copy to his supervisor. Ensure that your technology is current. When it comes to work, Generation Y expects you to be as tech-savvy as their newest Wii or iPhone.

e) Interact Often

Give advice and recommendations to Gen Yers if you work with them on aspects of the job that weren't discussed in new hire orientation. If you are in charge of them, give them a

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comprehensive orientation that lays down their responsibilities and your expectations into manageable portions. Make an effort to provide them with frequent feedback that is both corrective and supportive. This entails congratulating them on their accomplishments and firmly but gently reprimanding them when they stray just like their parents did. Inquire about their well-being on a regular basis, and show an open mind. Even for actions you would think they should know better, don't be hesitant to criticize them since, more often than not, they don't.

f) Explain Why.

All of Generation Y's landmarks come with an explanation. They were informed of the reasons behind the need to buckle up, check both ways before crossing the street, and avoid approaching strangers. They were taught the importance of volunteering, joining teams, and doing well in school in order to get admitted to a reputable institution. Most importantly, Generation Y was informed that their opinions mattered and they should have a say in why.

We deduce from this that you have a lot to benefit from this new generation. The regulations are currently being established by these future leaders. It is in your best benefit to control new perspectives, channels, and innovators in order to be able to foresee advancement.

CHAPTER 3: Human resource facing the generation Y in Morocco and the use of management software

3.1 Generation "Y," with certain characteristics, and the rise of HR Marketing

Young individuals born between the 1980s and the mid-2000s are referred to as members of "Generation Y." It is the generation that Generation X succeeded, which itself was preceded by the older, now-disappearing silent generation and the "baby boomer" generation (born between 1950 and 1980). (Born between 1901 and 1950). It comes before generation Z, which began to be born in 2001 and was raised in a time of mobile internet, touch screens, and social networks. Some scholars classify the "Y" generation's members as third type employees because they entered the workforce after the two generations before them.

This generation is often referred to by other phrases. We refer to "millennials" or "echo boomers" (many of whom are baby boomer children) (children of millennials). The phrase "digital natives" is also used in America. A definition of generation Y at work has also been provided by ROBIN RYAN. He says this "'JD" stands for "I have the right to" and describes Generation Y at work. They don't have a good reputation as employees since they are unreliable and don't form strong bonds with any one company. They must be able to market both their personality features and their strengths."

Without wishing to dwell too much on these differences, we can say that Generation Z is more selective than the preceding generation, prefers to create rather than copy, loves visual content over word, prefers to act rather than observe, and lastly favors influencers over famous people (MESSAOUDI A. and OUAHI L.2016). Aside from having an impact on their employment choices, Generation Y's distinct traits and habits also drive businesses to change how they operate and how they treat their employees. This generation is the most educated of all, highly skilled in using ICT, impatient, independent, and eager to be heard and respected. They are also very tolerant of diversity, show a great interest in social interactions, recognize authority when it is based on competence, have the capacity to handle multiple tasks at once,

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and seek careers as much as jobs, training opportunities as well as salaries. The two criticisms of Generation Y's youth, on the other hand, are ones that we frequently disagree with. The first is that they are not loyal to their employer (i.e. the tendency to change the employer for better working conditions). Best). Their forceful and revolutionary nature when not appropriately and promptly compensated is the subject of the second complaint. Rather than being explanatory or comparative, studies on Generation Y are primarily descriptive (MESSAOUDI A. and OUAHIL. 2016).

3.2 Characteristics of the Moroccan Y generation

In general, we use the terms generation X, generation Y, or another to refer to individuals within a specific age range, such as generation Y in Morocco, which is often defined as those born between 1980 and 2000. This demographic approach, however, does not address the concept's true meaning. Because of this, sociologists favor a definition that emphasizes attitudes and values in many contexts. These perspectives relate to relationships with work, money, family, and hierarchy... Each generation has highly different aspirations, sociocultural preferences, and outlooks when viewed from this perspective.

In comparison to earlier generations, Moroccan Generation Y, like Generation Y around the world, exhibits highly specific features and behaviors that affect their professional path and simultaneously urge businesses to reevaluate their procedures and attitudes toward these young people. It is the most educated generation of all, very proficient with NICTs, very impatient, independent and emancipated, eager to be heard and respected, self-assured, with a taste for change and innovation, very tolerant of diversity, shows a great interest in social relations, expresses recognition of authority when it is based on competence, endowed with the ability to perform multiple tasks at once, looks for careers as much as for jobs, for training opportunities, and looks for opportunities to advance. However, generation Y's youth are frequently subjected to two criticisms.

The first is that they have little regard for their boss (i.e. the tendency to change the employer for better working conditions). The second criticism focuses on their tendency toward revolution and retaliation when they are not promptly and adequately compensated.

3.3 The perspectives of the Moroccan Y generation on work

The desire to advance swiftly, learn new things, achieve, and make oneself known while having a strong concern for autonomy is one of this generation's defining traits in Morocco as well as other countries. Today's generation, for instance, have a different perspective on what authority within a corporation means. Unlike Generation X, who associates authority with deference, today's generation associate's authority more closely with productivity? Although they are eager to commit to lofty goals, young people dislike being subject to an autocratic leader's rule.

It is also a generation that is related to globalization, the Internet, and social networks. As a result, people have more opportunities to communicate information thanks to these new channels of communication. They are more in a logic of equality, sharing, and flattening of hierarchical interactions. They have a great desire for consideration and respect.

Traditional work, i.e., full-time, regular, with a career within a career within the same organization, is being replaced by a trend to flexibility and quick success for this generation. And rapid success Furthermore, Generation Y prefers individual effort and accomplishment over teamwork and a sense of belonging to the firm.

For Moroccan businesses, what is the benefit of HR marketing?

There is a lot of catching up to do for the Moroccan company, especially because the competition also comes from outside, therefore the application of this strategy is more important than ever. A candidate's decision automatically affects the international company's decision when presented with two equivalent employment offers! The employer's reputation, the work environment, and the company-level HR policy are all factors that predispose people to making certain decisions. Young Moroccan talents who opt to continue their professions overseas are also lost to Moroccan firms due to a lack of attraction. Therefore, there is a real need to investigate this issue and break free from conventional thinking in order to take into consideration the actual (human, economic, and social) context in which the Moroccan company

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operates. For some specialist profiles, the competition is already severe and will only get worse. The new challenges for HRDs include rethinking HR policy and communicating with both current and prospective employees.

What are Moroccan businesses doing with HR marketing today?

It is evident that HR marketing is gradually growing in Morocco, largely because of the global corporations who have brought these methods home. At this level, it's also important to emphasize the positive contamination impact, as several Moroccan businesses are starting to use these methods to hire employees or report on their activities. Undoubtedly, the competition for talent on the Moroccan labor market has had an effect on local businesses' HR policies. It must be acknowledged that the Moroccan company generally maintains an openness to global managerial methods without forgetting that this new way of doing things is mandated by globalization and the lack of skilled human resources. Some businesses consider it “window dressing” it is, a makeover and a showcase to spread signals about its appeal. But HR marketing is more than just a straightforward communication strategy. It is important task that not only senior management or the human resources division are involved in, but also employees. Additionally, employees are encouraged to support their company's employer brand by using HR tools like cooptation. While HR marketing may still be considered a fad by some businesses, others have realized that a new reality is required.

In this regard, we use the Shell Morocco group as an example, which conducts its attractiveness study on a regular basis. This study involves identifying the elements that employees and potential candidates find attractive and decisive and assessing the group's position in relation to these elements. Students, young hires, and future hires who work for organizations that compete on the attractiveness of their human resources are the study's target audiences. An additional example is Renault Morocco. The corporation even went so far as to appoint a school relations manager with the aim of gaining proximity with the world of the notorious schools in order to increase brand awareness and the employer image.

Additionally, businesses are utilizing a wider range of media tools to target various candidate segments. We can discuss the phenomenon of the blogosphere or HR conversations in

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particular. Companies get the chance to speak with individuals who are not already part of a recruitment program. This enables a deeper understanding of the needs and, if necessary, a modification of the employment offers. Podcasts, which automatically download content from the Internet, are another appealing medium in this field that enable members to watch films now or at a later time. Chats are effective communication tools that are tailored to young people. In essence, these fresh methods diversify the sources of hiring.

3.4 Generational communication between HR marketing and generation Y

The findings of our recruiting communication research have highlighted the relationship between professional representations and the events that are arranged. They also confirmed the above-mentioned authors' claims on the impact of institutional image and "idea marketing."

Based on our observations and interpretation of the results of the semi-directive interviews, we believe that the event practices constitute a type of generational and personalized communication. Because these operations are predominantly directed at young graduates from Generation Y, we refer to them as generational communication. In this regard, neither the literature review nor the empirical survey indicated any other population (adults or seniors) as a recipient of these behaviors.

According to a survey, millennials those born between the middle of the 1980s and the middle of the 1990s will make up 70% of the world's employment by 2025. Organizations need to learn more about how to attract and keep these new rising talents since the current influx of millennials into the workforces is ready to turn into a deluge. The leaders of today's firms must "think younger" and find fresh approaches to the problems they face, according to a group of 70 millennial executives from around the world.

According to a 2012 survey by the Kauffman Foundation, the largest entrepreneurial foundation in the US, 29.4% of entrepreneurs were between the ages of 20 and 34, and in 2011, millennials were in charge of almost 160,000 start-ups a month. In addition, a recent poll of IT job seekers under 35 by recruitment consultants Harvey Nash revealed that nearly half had some experience in entrepreneurship.

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The growing global talent battle and skill shortages in industries like technology make the case for hiring the right people from this generational pool. In a recent analysis, McKinsey predicted that by 2020, there would be a shortage of 18 million highly competent, college-educated professionals. Businesses must develop a recruitment plan that is specifically suited to hiring Generation Y once they have grasped the business justification for doing so. Here are some pointers for finding and hiring Gen Y talent.

Getting the channels and communication right

Companies are having trouble finding the best of our younger peers to hire. According to consulting company Anna Ivey, many managers struggle to figure out the best ways to attract, oversee, and keep Generation Y employees because they lack a thorough understanding of their motivations. Tech-savvy millennials often experienced a high degree of interactive stimulation as children thanks to media like TV, video games, the Internet, and social media, which previous generations may not always be as familiar with.

As a result, the communication and channels used in recruitment nowadays are rarely in line with the preferences of this target audience's social media users. This necessitates the development of new relationship-based, experience-based, and responsive recruitment tactics.

Relationship-based hiring

Relationship recruiting aims to develop more enduring, individualized relationships with potential recruits. Its objective is to gradually build a rapport with potential passive candidates. (Passive applicants could be early grads or students who are still enrolled in school.)

In order to accomplish this, businesses can employ smart web-based solutions to listen to and learn more about website users. If these visitors are recent graduates, they can interact with them on social media and eventually give them timely, pertinent information on their areas of interest. They can also provide information on careers within their organization when the moment is perfect. With time, graduating applicants will return to the career website while

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looking for employment as a result of the trusting relationship that has grown between them.

Creating a strong employer brand

Growing the company's reputation as an "employer of choice" will promote relationship recruitment by making it easier for "passive" candidates to recognize, believe in, and return to the organization when they are looking for a job.

There are several strategies that can be used to achieve this goal, including:

- **Embrace online interaction:** By developing a specific recruitment microsite, a company can offer specialized information to draw in Generation Y.
- **Use well-known channels to engage audiences and establish brands:** Businesses will appear young, active, and innovative by spreading creative material over Twitter, Facebook, and YouTube.
- **Maintain simplicity and ease:** A good website, an easy application process, and quick touch with recruiters are essential. The fusion of use and enjoyment will appeal to Generation Y, whose expectations were greatly influenced by media like MTV and video games as they were growing up.
- **Utilize external touch points to the fullest:** Job fairs, social media, postings, advertisements, conferences, sponsored sports events, and school gatherings can all be very helpful. Businesses can add excitement and interest to these events by inviting graduates and current Gen Y employees to meet with potential customers or by providing internships and open days to certain students.
- **Recognize Generation Y:** Companies shouldn't let prevailing stereotypes about this generation influence their decisions. A deeper comprehension of their attitudes and motivations can greatly aid in recruiting them.
- **Recognize the technologies at hand:** The most recent single, standardized, effective global talent acquisition platforms are just one of the many technologies that are accessible to suit recruitment objectives.

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These can combine the aforementioned under a single, safe portal that is simple to operate.

- Businesses will be better equipped to tap into the many capabilities of this generation as the graduate recruitment landscape changes if they make an effort to understand it and modify their messaging to suit. By doing this, organizations will be better equipped to tackle tomorrow's challenges with the workforce of today.

3.5 Management softwares as a field of action for human resources management

Definition and examples of management softwares

The features are primarily determined by the sort of management that the program is aimed for. For example, in project management software, features assist manage all of the project's resources, including financial and human resources.

It allows for the clear view of tasks and their respective statuses and due dates as well as the person assigned to each one. Financial management software will probably have totally different features compared to a project management one, but they both fall under the broader category of management software.

In the contemporary company environment, business management software plays a significant role. No matter the size or type of business, they are crucial components to ensuring its growth and seamless operation. These adaptable IT solutions are made to assist organizations in managing a range of tasks and procedures, including accounting, human resources management, logistics, sales, and marketing. The definition of business management software, as well as its various varieties and practical applications, will all be thoroughly covered in this paragraph.

Business management software, often referred to as Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) software, is an integrated computer system that allows businesses to effectively plan, track and manage their resources and operations. These resources include finance, inventory, human

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resources, supply chain and much more. The main goal of management software is to maximize efficiency, reduce costs, minimize errors, and facilitate decision-making by providing real-time data.

A common example of business management software is an accounting management system. It allows businesses to track all their financial transactions, manage accounts receivable and payable, generate financial reports and ensure that all tax and regulatory obligations are met. Software such as QuickBooks, Sage, or SAP Business One are used by millions of businesses around the world to simplify their accounting.

Human resources management (HRM) is another crucial field for management software. Employers must manage their personnel, pay and benefits, employee performance, and other factors. Workday, Oracle HCM Cloud, and SAP Success Factors are a few examples of HRM software that may assist businesses improve their human resource management.

Another key component of business operations is inventory management. To prevent expensive stock-outs or unneeded surpluses, businesses must monitor and manage their inventory levels. To keep track of stock movements, manage replenishments, and reduce storage costs, inventory management software is employed. Examples include WMS (Warehouse Management System) or specialist modules integrated into ERP software.

Customer relationship management (CRM) software is crucial in sales and marketing for handling leads, automating marketing campaigns, and increasing customer retention. A few of

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the most well-liked CRMs used by firms to improve their sales and marketing efforts are Salesforce, HubSpot, and Microsoft Dynamics CRM.

Supply chain management is another challenging area that management software may aid with. They enable the tracking of goods movements from manufacturing through delivery to final

consumers. Supply chain management, logistics, demand forecasting, and inventory management are all included. Solutions for supply chain management are available from organizations like Oracle, IBM, and Infor to satisfy these needs.

In summary, business management software is an essential tool to help organizations manage their operations efficiently, optimize their resources and make informed decisions. They cover a wide range of functional areas, from accounting to human resource management, supply chain and sales. This software, often customizable to meet the specific needs of each business, contributes to operational efficiency, cost reduction and long-term business growth.

Section 1: Beginning of management softwares

At the dawn of business computing, in the 1950s and 1960s, business management software first appeared. They were utilized on enormous, pricey devices that were initially designed for financial accountancy. The accessibility of computers has increased over time, enabling SMEs to use these technologies. ERP systems began to appear in the 1980s, merging multiple management tasks. Today, these programs are crucial for companies of all sizes because they provide cutting-edge features to enhance productivity, decision-making, and competitiveness.

Section 2: Moving from web 1.0 to management softwares

By ushering in a brand-new era of online communication and the dissemination of static content, Web 1.0's arrival marked a significant turning point in the history of the Internet. However, with time came a considerable evolution of the digital environment, bringing with it interactive and dynamic characteristics as well as chances for company transformation via management software. The switch from Web 1.0 to management software has significantly

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altered how companies run, allocate their resources, and provide customer service. We'll examine this development in this paragraph, emphasizing the key factors that contributed to it and the significant advantages it has given enterprises.

Technology and consumer expectations, however, have changed throughout time. With the emergence of social media, blogs, discussion forums, and collaborative platforms, Web 2.0 marked a significant turning point in technology. Businesses are starting to understand the need of listening to consumer and partner input, interacting with them more, and developing more interactive online experiences. Websites have developed into platforms for user engagement where visitors may contribute by writing content, posting comments, and joining discussions in addition to consuming it. Due to this growth, businesses now have more opportunities to form online communities, improve their social media presence, and increase client loyalty through two-way interaction.

However, digital change has not been limited to online encounters. It has also increased demand for more complex business management solutions. Businesses required more effective methods of managing their resources, operations, and processes. This is where management software comes in. These integrated IT solutions, often known as Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP), have drastically altered the way firms function. They have enabled businesses to properly manage their accounting, human resources, inventory, sales, supply chain, and other critical parts of their operations.

Management software has introduced advanced process automation, eliminating the need for tedious and error-prone manual tasks. For example, in the field of accounting, management software has allowed companies to manage their finances more accurately and in real time, by automating the processes of invoicing, tracking expenses and managing accounts receivable and payable. . They have also provided powerful tools for financial analysis and reporting, helping companies make informed decisions.

When it comes to human resource management, management software has simplified the management of workforce, payroll, benefits, and regulatory compliance. They have enabled companies to track employee performance, manage hiring and training cycles, and optimize workforce planning. Employees also benefited from self-service access to their personal information, which improved transparency and communication within the organization.

Section 3: Business use of management softwares

Management software is becoming a necessary tool for businesses of all sizes and sectors in the modern business environment. These software programs offer a wide range of features, including project management, customer relationship management (CRM), supply chain optimization, human resource management, and financial control. They form the basis of effective operations. Businesses can make data-driven choices in real-time because to the unified platform they offer for data storage and retrieval.

Figure 4: Business management software capabilities

Furthermore, management software promotes efficiency and creativity by facilitating seamless communication and cooperation among team members, whether they work in the same office or remotely. These solutions free up priceless human resources for innovative projects and strategic planning by automating tedious processes and routines. Management software gives firms strong analytics tools to find patterns, spot opportunities, and reduce risks in addition to simplifying daily operations. At the end, strategic adoption of management software is not simply a question of convenience but a crucial driver of long-term success and competitiveness at a time where agility and flexibility are vital.

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Section 4: Utilizing management softwares for human resources management

The usage of management software in the HR division has changed substantially over time, revolutionizing how businesses manage their human capital. These IT technologies have completely changed how HR managers find, develop, and keep talent. First, applicant management software has made the hiring process simpler. From a single platform, HR can now post positions online, sift applications, arrange interviews, and monitor the status of candidates. This reduced waiting time and improved the effectiveness of the hiring procedure. Additionally, learning management software has enabled companies to develop the skills of their employees in a more structured way. HR can create personalized training programs, track employee participation, and evaluate training effectiveness with analytical data. This ensures employees have the skills needed to succeed in their role. Performance management software has also played a key role in improving talent management. Online performance reviews allow managers to give real-time feedback, set goals, and track employee progress. This promotes more transparent communication and continued professional development.

The administration of staff schedules and leave has also been made simpler by leave and absence management software. Online leave requests from workers facilitate resource planning and lessen schedule issues. The administration of employee benefits, including health insurance and retirement schemes, has also been made simpler by benefits management software. Information on employee benefits is accessible online, making it simpler to comprehend and use.

Lastly, firms may now make better informed decisions about staff management thanks to HR analytics software. They support the gathering and analysis of data on work product, pay, job satisfaction, and many other topics. This knowledge is crucial for creating HR strategies that work better. To summarize, management software is critical in modernizing the human resources department. They enhance communication, encourage the development of skills, automate a number of administrative activities, and make it possible to make better informed decisions. Businesses who invest in these technologies have access to a more productive staff and improved talent management, which helps them remain competitive in the market.

Section 5: the problems that can be faced about the management softwares in the company

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Using management softwares technologies in a business might lead to a number of issues. Here

are a few of the frequent problems:

1. **Cost Overruns:** Putting in place and maintaining management software may be expensive, with expenditures occasionally going beyond budget.
2. **User Resistance:** Employees may be reluctant to use new software, which makes adoption challenging.
3. **Security Issues:** Data security is a major issue, and any software flaws might lead to data leaks.
4. **Lack of Training:** Employees may find it difficult to operate the program properly if they haven't received appropriate training.
5. **Data migration:** A difficult and error-prone process that involves transferring old data into new software.
6. **Data loss:** It can occur as a result of inadequate backup and recovery procedures.
7. **Overly complex functions:** Using software with too many functions may be confusing and ineffective.
8. **Technology Outdated:** Over time, management software may become ineffective, necessitating expensive updates.
9. **Dependency on Internet:** Cloud-based management software depends on internet access, which might be problematic if the network is unavailable.
10. **Data Security:** Concerns concerning data privacy and compliance with data protection laws arise when handling sensitive data within software.
11. **Vendor lock-in:** Businesses may become enmeshed in the ecosystem of a single software vendor, making it difficult to migrate to different solutions.
12. **Integration challenges:** It can be difficult and time-consuming to integrate management software with other corporate systems (such as CRM and ERP).
13. **Performance Problems:** If software performance is not adequately tuned as data accumulates, it may suffer.
14. **Data Migration Obstacles:** Moving data during a transfer from one piece of

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software to another can be a difficult operation.

15. **Hidden Costs:** Extra charges including license fees, maintenance costs, and hardware upgrades might not be immediately noticeable.
16. **Employee turnover:** When knowledgeable software users leave an organization, it can cause operations to be disrupted.
17. **Excessive features:** It might overwhelm consumers, making it difficult for them to concentrate on crucial activities.
18. **Resistance to change:** New methods of communication and working are routinely introduced by management software technology. Employee opposition to these changes is a possibility, which might slow or unevenly distribute the use of management software.

Businesses should take these possible problems into account and implement the necessary countermeasures. This may entail appropriate staff training, the implementation of strong security measures, the creation of information management rules, and efficient coordination between the many management softwares technologies employed by the business. Companies should carefully evaluate their software requirements, carry out in-depth research, and have a strong implementation and training strategy in place in order to prevent these issues. Successful management software use requires regular program assessment and update as well as rapid problem resolution.

Chapter 4: Research question

In the first part of this thesis, we discussed the explanations in relation to HR marketing, generation Y, and how human resources in Morocco are doing to be or become "an attractive employer", to retain its employees and to give a good image in terms of working conditions.

The second part, which is empirical, will be based on my work experience in the company INTEL CIA where i was in charge of customer loyalty in the field of telephone operators in France for the brand SFR, as well as the experience I had with my superiors and also the humanresources departments.

In this thesis, I will develop ideas around questions and subjects treated in theoretical strategy of HR marketing as well as my professional experience at INTEL CIA.

Our research is part of INTEL CIA's HR strategy, which aims to create a management softwares attraction and retention plan for present and future employees for the 2020-2021 fiscal year. Indeed, following a survey that I conducted in the company in 2021 by interviewing people internally from INTEL CIA to learn about the company's HR situation, as well as interviewing employees from other entities to make the comparison and have a more global idea on this subject at the Moroccan territory level.

The following will be the questions:

- What role does employee loyalty play in building excellent HR marketing? How do new technology aid HR marketing goals?
- Is Generation Y an ideal corporate employee? Is it a substantial change? Does it necessitate particular approaches to management and HR processes?
- How do Moroccans of Generation Y see human resources?
- How do Moroccan human resources portray their career opportunities, working

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environment, and traits in the world of recruitment?

- Can the perception of management softwares explain the evolution of HR practices in terms of employer branding and recruitment, and the level of familiarity with tools for Generation Y management software sand the HR function as well as the evolution of generation Y job search behaviors?

Chapter 5: Methodology:

5.1 Objective and Methodology

We shall set the method we used to complete the empirical portion of this thesis in this chapter. Remember that our goal is to draw attention to the ways and tactics that human resource departments have utilized to incorporate marketing into their operations. But in marketing, differentiation, attractiveness, and loyalty are three concerns and strategies that are relevant.

With the help of these techniques, we can offer the human resources department the correct value at the right time to the right individual through the appropriate channel. We will therefore also look at how generation Y and the HR department see management softwares in order to draw a conclusion about the influence of management softwares on HR marketing.

The primary themes of our research were initially disseminated in our literature review, therefore we made the decision to focus on an analysis based on a real-world example, namely the firm INTEL CIA, which we had observed in the field. We thought it would be fascinating to base our fieldwork on a qualitative method, specifically "a discursive approach of re-formulation, explanation, or theorization of testimonies, experiences, or occurrences.

We made the decision to conduct semi-structured interviews in order to have a direct line of communication with the research participants and to create narratives that contain pertinent descriptions and explanations that will be open to our interpretation.

Because the interviewer has a lot of freedom to steer the responses toward particular themes and modify the questions based on the circumstance and the subject being interviewed, the semi-structured interview approach allows for flexibility in the way the interviews are conducted. We will show our sample after describing the method we choose to use to gather the data.

5.2 Data collection technique: Qualitative method

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Qualitative research involves the systematic collection and interpretation of non-numerical data to uncover patterns, themes, and relationships within a specific cultural or social context," explain Garcia and Hernandez (2018). This method works especially well for analyzing the social processes at work and investigating subjective perceptions.

"Qualitative research often adopts an inductive, exploratory stance, allowing theories to emerge from the data itself rather than being predefined," argue White and Miller (2019). Because of its adaptability, researchers may explore the complexities of social processes and human behavior without having to impose strict frameworks.

"Researchers utilizing qualitative methods seek a deep understanding of the social world, emphasizing the importance of context and the perspectives of the participants," highlight Kim and Chang (2020). To find underlying meanings and social dynamics, one must fully immerse oneself in the lived experiences of others.

We went out into the field to gather the data we needed to carry out our empirical portion. Essential details. Because the subjects recount their personal experiences in relation to our theme, the data we have collected are of a subjective nature.

To carry out data collection with the qualitative method there are 6 ways to do this that I will present to you below:

5.3 Qualitative sampling

Sampling is a crucial step in qualitative research that entails choosing a selection of participants or cases to examine in-depth from a wider population. Qualitative research aims to gather rich and thorough data from a smaller, carefully chosen group, in contrast to quantitative research, which frequently aims to provide a representative sample. When it comes to sampling in qualitative research, keep the following points in mind:

A. Purposeful Sampling:

Purposive sampling, in which participants are selected according to certain standards pertinent to the research topic or the phenomena being studied, is a common technique used by qualitative researchers.

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Maximum variation sampling, homogenous sampling, and snowball sampling are examples of common intentional sampling approaches.

B. Theoretical Sampling:

Grounded conception Theoretical sampling is a technique that researchers might employ, in which the sample plan changes as the investigation goes on. In order to further develop emergent hypotheses, decisions for further sampling are informed by data obtained in previous phases.

C. Criterion Sampling:

Based on predetermined standards pertinent to the study topic or goals, participants are chosen. This kind of sampling is frequently employed by researchers who wish to examine particular traits or experiences.

D. Snowball Sampling:

Researchers may employ snowball sampling if the population of interest is hard to locate or reach. This entails asking a select group of key informants to recommend other possible participants after you've started working with them.

E. Maximum Variation Sampling:

This approach entails choosing people with a wide range of traits or backgrounds relevant to the study issue. It facilitates the capturing of a wide variety of settings and viewpoints.

F. Homogeneous Sampling:

Researchers may choose volunteers based on shared traits or experiences in order to fully comprehend a certain group or phenomena.

G. Sampling Saturation:

Data saturation is the point at which fresh data no longer yields new insights or information, and it is the goal of many qualitative researchers. When saturation is reached, sampling may come to an end, suggesting that theoretical or informational redundancy has been reached in the investigation.

H. Ethical Considerations:

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In order to ensure that participants are treated with respect and that their rights are upheld, researchers must take ethical standards into account when sampling. Two essential components of ethical sampling are informed permission and confidentiality.

I. Reflexivity:

Throughout the sample process, researchers should be reflective, recognizing and recording their own prejudices and presumptions and how they could affect the choice of subjects.

J. Transferability:

Unlike quantitative researchers, qualitative researchers do not aim to generalize their results to a wider population. Rather, they strive for transferability, allowing readers to assess how applicable the findings are to different populations or circumstances.

In qualitative research, sampling is an iterative and dynamic procedure that is frequently influenced by the way the study is developing and the new information that the data are revealing. Rather than achieving statistical representativeness, the objective is to get a deep and complex knowledge of the investigated phenomena. We will present you here 5 data collection techniques that can be used for qualitative researches and then we will chose and discuss the chosen technique for our study:

1- Interviews:

Qualitative interviews are a useful technique for gathering data because they emphasize a more exploratory and open-ended approach to comprehending people's viewpoints, experiences, and interpretations. Qualitative interviews are more flexible than their quantitative counterparts, enabling researchers to adjust the interview procedure in response to participant replies and explore emergent themes in greater detail.

An interview guide is frequently used in qualitative interviews; it offers a flexible framework instead of a strict list of pre-planned questions. While giving participants the freedom to express themselves in their own words, this guide acts as a tool to guarantee that important themes are covered. In qualitative research, the emphasis is frequently on the richness and depth of the data

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collected, while also acknowledging that participants actively influence the interview's direction.

Qualitative interviews may be divided into three main categories:

- **One-on-one conversations:** known as "in-depth interviews" offer a thorough examination of a person's ideas, emotions, and experiences. The questions' open-ended format makes it possible to comprehend the participant's viewpoint in more detail.
- **Focus Group Interviews:** Using a limited number of members, focus groups encourage communication and interaction within the group. By building on one another's answers, participants are encouraged to show similar or different points of view.
- **Ethnographic Interviews:** Taking place in the participants' everyday environments, ethnographic interviews aim to comprehend social phenomena, behavior, and culture. For a comprehensive understanding, researchers frequently observe and engage with subjects for prolonged periods of time.

Qualitative interviews can be conducted in a number of ways:

- **Face-to-Face Interviews:** In qualitative research, face-to-face encounters provide a personal and immersive experience, much as in quantitative interviews. By observing non-verbal indicators and establishing rapport, the researcher can help to delve deeper into the viewpoints of the participants.
- **Phone Interviews:** Although they are less popular in qualitative research than in quantitative research, telephone interviews are nonetheless an effective method. They provide participants with flexibility in accessing them across geographical regions.
- **Internet or Video Interviews:** Qualitative research has seen a rise in the use of internet tools like video conferencing. This method allows for contextual and visual signals to be included in interviews with individuals who may be geographically distant.

Because they place a strong focus on the experiences and circumstances of the participants, qualitative interviews offer a comprehensive picture of the study issue and offer insightful

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information that may not be obtained using quantitative approaches alone.

2- Observations

A key component of qualitative research is observation, which is the methodical and deliberate observing, listening, and recording of actions, events, or phenomena as they occur in the wild. By using this approach, researchers hope to have a thorough grasp of organizational procedures, human actions, and social and cultural dynamics. Depending on the goals of the study, observations can be made in a variety of locations, including public areas, workplaces, schools, and natural settings.

The Participant and non-participant observation are the two main categories of observation. When a researcher uses participant observation, they actively interact with the participants or study environment, frequently adopting a role within the setting. Researchers can gather insider viewpoints and insights through this intensive methodology that may be difficult to obtain through other means. Conversely, non-participant observation entails the researcher watching in a more detached and objective manner without actively participating.

The capacity of observational research to collect rich, contextually embedded data is one of its advantages. Through first hand observation and documentation of behaviors, interactions, and the physical surroundings, researchers can get a comprehensive and intricate comprehension of the subject matter. When researching intricate social phenomena, cultural customs, or the inner workings of a particular society, this approach is very helpful.

3- Phenomenological research

The goal of phenomenological research, a qualitative research methodology, is to investigate and comprehend people's lived experiences. Phenomenology, which has philosophical and psychological roots, aims to understand a phenomenon's essence through the eyes of its witnesses. The objective is to explore the personal interpretations and meanings that people ascribe to their experiences in order to gain a fuller comprehension of the phenomena as they

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are experienced and understood.

The bracketing or epoch process, which allows researchers to momentarily leave aside their prejudices, assumptions, and theoretical frameworks in order to examine the phenomena with new eyes, is a fundamental component of phenomenological research. By putting judgment aside, researchers can do "bracketed" or open-minded research in which they try to understand the core of the event as it is experienced by the participants.

In-depth interviews or open-ended talks with people who have witnessed the event of interest are common in phenomenological investigations. These interviews are often unstructured or semi-structured, enabling participants to express themselves in their own words with little interference from the researcher. Researchers may also examine textual or visual items that give insights into people's experiences.

Data analysis in phenomenological research is a methodical procedure. Researchers use a technique known as "phenomenological reduction" or "eidetic reduction," in which they pinpoint and focus on the key components of the experience, removing unnecessary information. This reduction tries to reduce the similarities in participants' accounts, leading to the discovery of important themes and patterns that define the underlying structure of the phenomena.

4- Document Review in Qualitative Data Collection

Document review is a data collecting approach used in both qualitative and quantitative research. Document review in quantitative research refers to the systematic inspection and analysis of existing documents or records in order to extract important information. Here are five crucial considerations to remember while conducting quantitative data collection:

Source of the data:

Document evaluation is based on existing documents, records, or data sources pertinent to the study issue. Reports, databases, surveys, organizational records, public records, and any other written material containing quantitative information are examples of these documents.

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Questions for Research and Objectives:

In quantitative research, the goal of document review is to collect data that may be used to answer particular research questions or test hypotheses. Instead of gathering fresh data through surveys or experiments, researchers utilize this approach to examine and understand numerical data that is already existing in documents.

Data Extraction and Coding:

During document evaluation, researchers extract quantitative data from chosen documents in a methodical manner. Identifying variables of interest, locating relevant data points, and structuring the material for analysis are all part of this procedure. To categorize and arrange the data for quantitative analysis, coding schemes might be created.

Validity and dependability

It is critical to ensure the data's legitimacy and dependability. Researchers must rigorously analyze the quality of the documents under evaluation, taking into account criteria such as data correctness, sample representativeness, and measurement consistency. It is critical to demonstrate the legitimacy and trustworthiness of the quantitative data obtained.

Considerations and limitations:

Document review has limits in quantitative research. Researchers should be cautious of potential document biases, missing data, or differences in data quality across various sources. It is critical to appreciate the context in which the papers were written, as well as any restrictions that may impact the results' generalizability.

5- Semi-Structured Interviews Methodology

A semi-structured interview is a subset of the wider category of qualitative research. In other words, it is a method of carrying out qualitative research. The researcher has a collection of predefined open-ended questions or themes to discuss with participants during a semi-structured interview. A semi-structured interview, on the other hand, provides for flexibility, as opposed to a completely structured interview, where the questions are strict and

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standardized. The interviewer can modify the questions based on the replies of the participants, offer follow-up questions, and delve further into developing topics.

As a result, a semi-structured interview is a research method that employs a flexible yet ordered approach to data collection through interactions with participants. The semi-structured interview approach is explained in full below:

Designing the Interview Guide:

- The researcher begins by creating an interview guide, which is a collection of open-ended questions or themes that will be used to steer the interview. These questions are intended to go deeply into the study issue.

Open-Ended Questions:

- Open-ended questions allow participants to freely share their views, feelings, and viewpoints.
- Broad and exploratory questions encourage participants to expound on their comments.

Flexibility in Questioning:

- Semi-structured interviews allow for some freedom, in contrast to structured interviews that follow a predetermined set of questions.
- The interviewer has the ability to modify the questions in response to the participant's answers and probe more into noteworthy or pertinent topics.

Interviewer Skills:

- In order to establish rapport with interviewees, interviewers need to have strong communication and interpersonal skills. This facilitates the kind of relaxed atmosphere needed for candid and open communication.

Pilot Testing:

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- To ensure that the interview guide is clear and produces the needed information, researchers frequently run pilot testing with a small group prior to the actual interviews.

Sampling:

- The sample size in qualitative research is frequently lower than in quantitative studies, but the focus is on depth and richness of information.
- Participants are chosen based on the research objectives and the traits deemed important to the study.

Conducting the Interviews:

- Although they can be done remotely or over the phone, the interviews are normally conducted in-person.
- The interviewer gives participants an overview of the research, clarifies its goal, and requests their informed permission.

Recording and Transcribing:

- With permission from the subject, interviews are taped for accuracy. These recordings' transcriptions aid in the thorough examination of the data.

Data Analysis:

- A thematic analysis of the gathered data is conducted. Researchers note trends, reoccurring themes, and differences in individuals' answers.
- Coding, classification, and interpretation of the qualitative data may be part of the analysis.

Validity and Reliability:

- Although statistical validity is not the main emphasis of qualitative research, it is nevertheless important to make sure the results are reliable and trustworthy.

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Triangulation using several sources or techniques and member checking confirming results with participants may be included in this.

Reporting:

- The findings are presented narratively, frequently using participant quotations to highlight important findings or themes.
- The results are interpreted in light of the larger study framework.

Ethical Considerations:

- In order to maintain participant anonymity, informed consent, and courteous treatment throughout the study process, researchers must abide by ethical rules.

The chosen qualitative technique for this research was the Semi-Structured Interviews methodology

We have used qualitative research, particularly the approach of individual semi-directive and semi-structured interviews, to get a detailed understanding of how our sample perceives our theme. This method enables us to see our own visions. Using this method, it is possible to gather unique personal visions, comments, and observations from the subjects of the interviews.

“Semi-structured interviews are the preferred data collection method when the researcher's goal is to better understand the participant's unique perspective rather than a generalized understanding of a phenomenon” **(Omolola A. Adeoye-Olatunde Pharm.D. 2021)**

“In the semi-structured approach, the researcher asks a standard set of questions to collect data. However, it allows the researcher to ask additional questions if an interesting or new line of inquiry develops during the interview process” **(Young & al., 2018)**

The three parts of our sample, namely HRM/RRH, managers/employees, and job seekers, were indeed the subject of three interview guidelines that we created. Three different themes were explored: the first one was concerned with identifying the HR marketing strategies used by

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the managers of the human resources department. The second one focused on the traits of the Y generation and the effects of management softwares, and the third one gave us insight into HR practices and Y generation job search patterns.

Three interview guidelines that include a list of open-ended and closed-ended questions served as the basis for the semi-structured interviews. We established the following themes for our interview guide. The interviews were conducted after we explained the Keywords of our research (Gen Y, HR Marketing, employer brand...)

Initial Theme: Presentation

Our goal is to "break the ice" between the interviewer and the respondent through a personal introduction. We request a brief introduction, as well as information about your background, age, and position, before we start our investigation on the topic.

Theme 1: HR Marketing Strategies

HR Department Members:

Introduction:

Can you introduce yourself, including your background, age, and current role within the HR department?

HR Marketing Strategies:

What strategies do you believe are most effective in attracting Generation Y talent to our organization?

How do you adapt HR marketing strategies to align with the preferences and expectations of Generation Y employees and trainees?

Generation Y Employees:

Introduction:

Could you share a bit about yourself, including your background, age, and current role in the organization?

Experiences with HR Marketing:

How did HR marketing and employer branding influence your decision to join this organization?

Have you observed any specific HR marketing initiatives that resonated with Generation Y employees?

Generation Y Trainees:

Introduction:

Could you introduce yourself, including your background, age, and current role as a trainee?

Training Program Preferences:

What factors influenced your decision to join our training program?

How did HR marketing or employer branding play a role in your choice to become a trainee here?

Figure 5: Interview guideline to identify HR Marketing strategies

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The second theme is the traits of Generation Y and the impact of the management softwares

In this section, we seek to understand the fundamental components that make up the ideal type of generation Y, including their goals, driving forces, and attitudes toward the workplace. The goal is to determine whether generation Y actually alters the HR and management landscape within the organization. We'll talk to business leaders, generation Y job seekers, and the HR department to get their thoughts on the "Y." in this part we will also measure the impact of these management softwares on generation Y and human resources departments.

Through these multifaceted conversations, we aspire to not only comprehend the intrinsic qualities of Generation Y but also to discern tangible manifestations of these characteristics in organizational practices. This research endeavor aims to provide valuable insights into the symbiotic relationship between Generation Y, technology, and the evolving landscape of human resources and management within our organization.

Theme 2: Traits of Generation Y and Impact of Management Software

HR Department Members:

Introduction:

Can you provide a brief introduction about yourself, including your background, age, and position in the HR department?

Generation Y Traits:

From your perspective, what are the defining traits of Generation Y employees and trainees within our organization?

How has the HR department adapted to accommodate the unique characteristics and expectations of Generation Y in both roles?

Generation Y Employees:

Introduction:

Could you share a bit about yourself, including your background, age, and current role in the organization?

Impact of Management Software:

How has the use of management software influenced your day-to-day work and interactions within the organization?

In your opinion, has the organization effectively utilized technology to cater to the preferences of Generation Y employees?

Generation Y Trainees:

Introduction:

Could you introduce yourself, including your background, age, and current role as a trainee?

Impact of Management Software in Training:

How has the use of management software influenced your training experience and interactions within the organization?

In your opinion, has the organization effectively utilized technology to cater to the preferences of Generation Y trainees?

Figure 6: Interview guideline to identify Gen Y's traits and impact of management softwares

The third theme is how Millennials approach HR procedures and job searches.

This section gives us insight into how management softwares are being incorporated into HR's goals and, in turn, how Generation Y is using them to find a job. Generation Y in their employment hunt, as well as in their ability to carry out their duties.

By delving into these intricacies, we seek to elucidate the symbiotic relationship between HR objectives, management software, and the adaptive strategies employed by Generation Y. This research endeavor not only sheds light on the practical applications of technology within the HR

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domain but also illuminates the dynamic intersection between evolving workplace tools and the proactive utilization of these tools by the digitally-native Generation Y workforce.

Theme 3: Millennial's Approach to HR Procedures and Job Searches

HR Department Members:

Introduction:

Can you briefly introduce yourself, including your background, age, and role in the HR department?

HR Procedures for Employees and Trainees:

How has the HR department adapted its procedures to accommodate the preferences and expectations of Generation Y employees and trainees?

Are there specific technologies or tools that have been particularly effective in engaging Generation Y during HR processes?

Generation Y Employees:

Introduction:

Could you share a bit about yourself, including your background and current experience as an employee?

Technology in HR Procedures:

How do you engage with HR procedures, and how has technology influenced these processes for you?

Are there specific technologies that you find particularly helpful or challenging in your interactions with HR?

Generation Y Trainees:

Introduction:

Could you share a bit about yourself, including your background and current experience as a trainee?

Technology in Training and Development:

How do you leverage technology and online platforms in your training and development process?

In your experience, what role does technology play in shaping your perception of the organization during the training program?

Figure 7: Interview guideline to identify insight into HR practices and Y generation job search patterns

5.4 Qualitative Sampling

In our unwavering commitment to comprehensively unravel the intricate dynamics of the contemporary job market, our research has cast a wide net, placing a keen focus on the multifaceted experiences of Generation Y. This demographic cohort, born between 1980 and 2000, serves as the epicenter of our study, embodying a unique blend of technological prowess and diverse perspectives that defines this pivotal generation. Within this expansive exploration,

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we meticulously examine the delicate interplay between job seekers and employers.

At the heart of our research lies a carefully curated sample designed to encapsulate the myriad facets of this exploration. Five dynamic members of Generation Y, actively navigating the labyrinth of employment opportunities, stand as the protagonists in our narrative. Their experiences, aspirations, and challenges form the bedrock upon which our study is built. Counterbalancing this cohort are four esteemed directors and human resource managers, occupying strategic positions in talent acquisition and management. Their perspectives, honed through years of decision-making process, provide invaluable insights into the strategies and considerations that shape the employment landscape.

Adding further depth and breadth to our canvas are five corporate executives and employees, each contributing a unique perspective to our understanding of the corporate milieu. Their experiences serve as a microcosm of the challenges and triumphs within the organizational framework. Central to our study is our deep-rooted connection with INTELCIA Morocco, where we accrued two years of hands-on experience as customer loyalty consultants and telemarketers. This professional backdrop not only informs our exploration but also offers a nuanced lens through which we examine the broader job market, particularly within the distinctive context of the Moroccan landscape.

While INTELCIA Morocco takes center stage in our investigation, we deliberately extend our purview to include the Hyundai Group Morocco as a secondary yet significant topic. This strategic choice allows for a comparative analysis that unveils patterns, challenges, and opportunities beyond the confines of a singular organizational ecosystem.

The meticulous construction of our sample, a process that spanned two weeks, underlines our commitment to precision and representativeness. Leveraging the organization's comprehensive database, we identified participants who met our exacting criteria—executives, employees, and career-seeking individuals from Generation Y. This exhaustive yet targeted approach ensures a diverse and representative cohort, elevating the richness and authenticity of our findings. Furthermore, the inclusion of trainees as job seekers' representatives adds a layer of real-world relevance to our study.

Crucially, the orchestration of our research agenda is a collaborative endeavor. Working hand in

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hand with our internship supervisor, who serves as a talent manager, we meticulously followed a structured agenda for respondent selection. This collaborative approach not only upholds the integrity of the research process but also aligns our exploration with the strategic objectives of talent management within the organizational context.

In summation, our research endeavors to transcend the boundaries of conventional academic inquiry. Through the lens of Generation Y, within the dynamic environments of INTEL CIA Morocco and Hyundai Group Morocco, we seek to contribute nuanced insights that illuminate the complexities of the contemporary employment landscape. This multifaceted exploration strives to offer a holistic understanding of the aspirations, challenges, and strategic considerations that shape the world of work in our time.

5.5 Methods and Information Gathered from Our Sample

Step 1:

In the initial phase of our research endeavor, meticulous planning and groundwork were essential. Securing formal approval to conduct our inquiry was a paramount first step. Subsequently, we diligently crafted a comprehensive agenda, strategically selecting a venue that aligned with the accessibility of our chosen thematic elements. Careful articulation of the research topic, its objectives, and the rationale underlying our subject selection were key components of this phase. Furthermore, we sought and obtained consent to record the interviews, adhering to a predetermined timeframe of 15 to 20 minutes as per the guidelines stipulated by our internship supervisor.

Step 2:

The core of our investigative process unfolded in the structured execution of interviews. Following a detailed interview guide, we engaged with participants on topics encompassing the HR function, a nuanced portrayal of Generation Y, the intricacies of management software, and Generation Y's utilization of such software. Each interview, meticulously designed and executed, spanned a duration of 30 minutes. To ensure minimal disruption to participants' work schedules, I conducted one interview per day over the course of a month. Notably, the interviews were purposefully designed to cover three distinct themes. This approach allowed us to garner insights

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from diverse perspectives, with some participants contributing to discussions on two different themes.

Step 3:

Empowering our interviewees to conclude the discussions, the final phase provided participants with agency over the extent of their contributions. In an open-ended manner, we offered subjects the opportunity to share additional insights or perspectives before formally concluding the interview process. This methodological approach not only respected the autonomy of the participants but also enriched the depth of our findings by encouraging spontaneous contributions.

This methodical and considered three-step process not only ensured the ethical conduct of our research but also facilitated a nuanced exploration of the chosen themes while respecting the time constraints and preferences of our participants.

5.6 Qualitative analytical method

In addressing the amassed data, it is imperative to delve into a comprehensive discussion on effective methodologies for its management. Our research methodology, centered on content analysis, serves as the qualitative analytical framework. The elucidations drawn from this qualitative data are poised to substantially elevate user and customer experiences. Yet, the challenge lies in quantifying and evaluating inherently non-quantifiable data.

The selection of an appropriate qualitative data analysis technique is contingent upon the overarching business objectives and the nature of the collected data. A myriad of qualitative data analysis techniques is at our disposal, each offering unique insights to distill qualitative feedback and customer perspectives. In navigating this decision, a thorough exploration of available approaches is imperative, considering their respective use cases and how each methodology contributes to cultivating a profound understanding of our user base.

In this section, I will meticulously examine five prominent qualitative analysis techniques. This scrutiny aims to facilitate a judicious selection, aligning with the specific objectives of our research and enhancing our team's capacity to derive nuanced insights from the gathered

qualitative data.

1- Content Analysis

A study technique called content analysis looks at and counts the appearance of particular terms, concepts, and ideas in text, image, video, or audio messages. In order to assist you draw trustworthy conclusions about what customers think of your brand and how you may enhance their experience and opinion, the approach converts qualitative input into quantitative data.

For the purpose of identifying communication patterns, identifying variances in individual or group communication trends, and creating conceptual linkages, content analysis can be done manually or with the aid of software like Lexalytics.

2- Thematic analysis

Tools like Dovetail and Thematic can be used for thematic analysis, which aids in the identification, analysis, and interpretation of patterns in qualitative data.

Despite their apparent similarities, content analysis and thematic analysis have separate principles:

- The goal of content analysis, which can be used on both qualitative and quantitative data, is to find common themes and word patterns.
- Only qualitative data can be used for thematic analysis, which concentrates on finding patterns and "themes."

3- Analyzing narrative

With tools like Delve and ATLAS.ti driven by AI, narrative analysis is a technique used to interpret the stories of study participants, including things like testimonials, case studies, interviews, and other text or visual data.

Heavy-structured interviews and written surveys are two forms that don't work well for narrative analysis since they don't provide participants as much freedom to narrate their tales in their own words.

4- Ground-up theory evaluation

A technique for performing qualitative research to create theories by looking at facts from the

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real world is grounded theory analysis. Utilizing tools like MAXQDA and Delve, the technique entails the development of hypotheses and theories through the gathering and assessment of qualitative data.

This strategy, in contrast to other qualitative data analysis methodologies, builds ideas based on the data rather than the other way around.

5- Analyzing discourse

To do a discourse analysis is to investigate the underlying significance of qualitative data. In order to analyze the connections between the information and its context, texts, audio files, and videos must be carefully examined.

Discourse analysis illuminates what audiences think about an issue and why they feel the way they do about it, as opposed to content analysis, which focuses on the meaning of language in its context. In the case of my company (INTELCIA) experience the interviews are written up in a first phase as a transcription. Creating an analysis grid and then processing and coding the material gathered make up the second and final phases of the research process.

In the initial stage, we verbatim transcribed the oral interviews into text that contained the research's raw data. The objective is to make reading easier and have traceability.

In a subsequent phase, we classified the interviews so that we could thoroughly examine the texts. The data gathered. In order to conduct a thematic analysis of the content, we have decided to use the INLog software, which enables the task. In order to assign codes to these segments, the qualitative data is segmented (into words, expressions, sentences, and paragraphs). **Brillet and Hulin express that in 2016.**

We will discover the main aspects that will assist us provide answers to our research questions once our interviews have been encoded and filtered by theme. The complete text of the interviews is included.

Based on the themes addressed in our interview guide, we provide synthetic analysis grids that summarize the outcomes of the interviews.

5.7 Results Presentation

In this chapter, we will provide the results of our survey, attempting to present the data acquired during our survey in accordance with the various themes discussed in our interviewguide.

Part 1: Generation Y

- **Generation Y expresses its qualities in the first part**

First, we'll look at what Generation Y has to say about their qualities, expectations, relationship to work, sources of inspiration, and demotivation at work.

First off, it's noteworthy to note that the majority of Generation Y participants in our sample attest that they look for meaning in their work: "Having a job that makes sense, that includes challenges on both a professional and interpersonal level," "Essentially that the work carried out be alive," etc. entrance E7- FT2.

The phrase "...the work performed and the efforts invested are recognized by the hierarchy" (Entr C3-AE1) is frequently used by members of Generation Y. Some people promote the necessity of work-related acknowledgment in the workplace, saying things like, "It is necessary to operate in a framework full of work recognition." E6-FT1 Entr

One of the needs mentioned by Generation Y is the need for a comfortable and enjoyable workplace, as well as a sense of teamwork. "My main expectations for my future employer to be friendly and sympathetic and direct who push on the motivation of our group of workers and that they watch over our comfort," the generation says in Entr E6-FT1. "Better working circumstances and a sense of teamwork can motivate me to get out of bed every day, head to the office, and finish my job as quickly and effectively as possible Entrance E10-SM2.

According to research on Generation Y's sources of motivation at work, they value respect from the hierarchy, support, feedback, and the sensation of having their management on their side: "At work, my manager's lack of respect and his or her lack of assistance can lead to discontent. I enjoy working in an environment where I feel like my coworkers, especially my

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superior, have my back. C4-SM1, Entr. "I personally don't want to feel undervalued, therefore a reduction in the value of my efforts or of my work might lead to demotivation, and I would add the worsening of working circumstances," the author says. E9-SM2 Entr

People from Generation Y also emphasized career advancement, upgrading skills, work-life balance, autonomy, and leadership positions.

As a conclusion, the characteristics of Generation Y as expressed in their comments (executives, workers, trainees, and job seekers) are all as follows:

Table 1: Qualities that Generation Y evokes

After describing the traits of Generation Y, we'll discuss how the HR function views this generation in terms of values and attitudes at work, and we'll especially focus on whether or not this generation's uniqueness necessitates a particular strategy. Really specific HRM?

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Our interviews with the managers of the HR department revealed that Generation Y is adept using management softwares, regards them as a connected generation, and places a high value on networking and engagement.

Both the INTELZIA Group's Talent Manager and the Human Resources Director of INTELZIA Morocco can clearly recall this quality: keeping an ear to the market Entr F15-CG2, "I would say that it is people who live their life in both a virtual and physical fashion, that is to say, there is a community, we feel it most strongly when we hire young people, he works in a network, he connects with each other a lot... «Entrance F11-CG2

A balance between personal and professional life is one of the traits mentioned in the literature. This includes giving equal weight to work and playtime, as well as to friends, family, entertainment, and the pursuit of enjoyment and fulfillment outside of work. In this regard, the director of INTELZIA's resources attests vehemently to the presence of this trait, saying: "They are people who are concerned about a balance between private and professional life, therefore they are not people who will invest professional work without forgetting the sports activity and social » Entr11-CG2.

This is also stated by the Talent Manager of the INTELZIA Group in his speech: "She also seeks to have a balance between personal and professional life; private life is not for them a family life, it is to have time after 6 p.m., on the weekends, and time to check Facebook and other websites while working, this is a main feature." Entr15-CG2

The generation known as Generation Y is considered to be one that isn't extremely devoted, exhibits a tenuous sense of loyalty to the organization, and harbors doubts about the organization, said Pichault and Pleyers in 2010. The head of human resources at INTELZIA Morocco evokes these traits effectively, saying that "this generation... is not attached to work"(principles, values, and company culture) EntrF14-CG2. These traits were recalled by our respondents.

The need for accomplishment, opportunism, and other traits that were mentioned are similar

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to those that have been described in the literature.

In addition to those stated in the literature, we observed a trait unique to this generation that was mentioned by our respondents, namely autonomy and independence at work. This generation displays a desire for autonomy in the direction of their objectives, duties, and a certain amount of flexibility in their day-to-day professional lives. "For them, the most important thing is the outcome of the work, not showing in at 8 a.m. and leaving at 6 p.m.," says one observer. Entr15-AGS2.

Millennials' expectations, motivation, and relationship to work:

Gen Y still finds financial reward to be the greatest motivating factor, "...which pays them well." His primary source of motivation is money, according to EntrF15-AMR2. Entering F14-AMR2.

Recognition is revealed as a crucial component among Generation Y via expectations. The Human Resources Director of Hyundai Morocco stresses the need of consistently praising workers' accomplishments and efforts, especially those from Generation Y.

The whole HR function that was questioned stated that the needs of Generation Y include a comfortable workplace, assistance, training, and career management. In addition to money, the HR manager also cites the standing inside the company in his speech, saying, "His primary source of incentive is money, but also the magnitude of the position." EntrF14-AMR2.

The Talent Manager of INTEL CIA Morocco expressed this philosophy in the following words: "High expectations, with great impatience in accomplishing, work is not the end, value the work-life balance... «Work is not an end, but just a means to achieve specific wants, extra-professional aims. F12-AMR2 as the Entrance.

From our interviews with the HR function, another aspect is apparent. In order to stand out from their coworkers and become more prominent within the organization, Generation Y expects to be a challenger and to face challenges.

Y management techniques in particular

In the first place, the HR function expresses itself unanimously on the necessity to modify the

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management tools for young employees from the Y generation, When dealing with a population that has new profiles, it is necessary to adjust the tools, particularly the communication channels used to reach out to them and the EVP's claims intended to pique their interest. Indeed, the recruiter must woo the fresh generation Y hire, says EntrF12-ASG2. EntrF14-ASG2, "Generation Y is different, and recruiters must recognize this and adjust to meet their unique demands" The EntrF15-ASG 2.

The interviews demonstrate that the HR department is well aware of the unique characteristics of generation Y and that it doesn't hesitate to put up effective tactics for hiring, luring, and keeping employees. "...trying to highlight the company but also the scope of the position and what the interested party will have as advantages (Salary and others...), the hierarchy must motivate consistently and acknowledge the new hire's efforts. It is also necessary to provide the new hire with a very clear idea about his career and provide the necessary resources (training, etc.) to manage it well. the EntrF14-ASG2, "Our company has learned about the expectations of Generation Y: the value of working conditions, a healthy social environment, new, more ergonomic offices, better equipped, and others have installed nurseries gyms..., in order to give them spaces more appropriate to their expectations, without forgetting that we listen to our employees, through annual surveys, managers, and HR managers." EntrF13-ASG2.

The HR function emphasizes the necessity of using management software in HR missions in view of Generation Y's connected nature and mastery of information and communication technologies. "In terms of recruitment, I believe it is crucial to follow them already on social media, as they are people whose profiles will be more accessible there than through direct approaches to applicants." EntrF11-ASG2 states that "...the tools must adapt, especially the communication routes to approach them and the reasons of the EVP aimed to attract them" the EntrF12-AGS2.

To sum up, we suggest the table in the attachment, which depicts the perspective the HR function has on Generation Y:

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Table 2: the perspectives of the HR function has on the generation Y

A look of Generation Y	View from the Y generation
Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Masters management softwares . - Interactive. - Connected. - Worried about finding a balance between personal and professional obligations. - Not devoted. - Lack of a sense of community. - A desire for success. - Opportunistic. - At employment, look for freedom and autonomy.
Expectations, drive, and connection to work.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Remuneration. - Acknowledgement. - Pleasant working conditions - Help and instruction. - Management of careers. - The post's dimensions. - Various difficulties. - Visibility inside the business.
HR requires particular methods.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Using management softwares in missions for the HR. - The company's promotion (employer brand). - Draw attention to the post's size. - Appreciation for efforts - Create professional opportunities. - Adapt the social atmosphere and the workplace. - Avenues of communication for HR.

Part 2: The tools Web Marketing

- **Level of familiarity with tools for Generation Y management softwares and the HR function**

With an average score of 3.4 on a scale from 1 (zero knowledge) to 4 (great knowledge), Generation Y respondents confirm their high level of knowledge regarding management softwares. While young people of generation Y display a higher level, the HR function displays a lower level (average score of 2.7). It should be mentioned that the level of expertise differs within the HR function itself. Comparatively speaking, HR managers exhibit a higher level of management softwares tool expertise than HR directors.

- **Notoriety and identification**

We observe that Facebook and LinkedIn are always mentioned first by all the interviewees, including executives, workers, and job seekers. These two management softwares products continue to enjoy the same reputation in the HR department. All of our respondents have accounts on at least two management softwares sites, including social networks.

Additionally, they exhibit a strong attachment to the management softwares and a strong desire to keep using them. "...absolutely not, as it is quite beneficial to consider news about the helpdesks of each course, giving you a sense of what is happening on a daily basis." EntrE6-A1: "No, they're actually very helpful as marketing and communication tools." EntrE7-A.

- **Use of management softwares and participation**

When it comes to Generation Y, the terminology used to describe their usage of management softwares technologies demonstrates a significant draw for them. The following terms included in our surveys are provided for clarification: "essential, addiction, daily use..," "Their mastery is an interesting advantage, but I am addicted, it has become a requirement." Entr9-IM1.

The HR department follows the example set by Generation Y: "Daily I have access to my Facebook and LinkedIn profiles, I receive requests, so out of interest I look at the profiles and when I have recruitment I run queries on LinkedIn and Viadeo »EntrF15-IM3. The HR function also follows this example. The other respondents in the HR function evaluate their need

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on management softwares as crucial and highly reliant(EntrF14-IM3, EntrF12-IM3).

In terms of the usage of management softwares technologies, our interviews with Generation Y, including executives, workers, and job searchers (trainees), reveal a use geared towards dialogue, the exchange of information, as well as the consultation of employment and internship offers. By using social networks, job seekers can connect with those who work for businesses and answer to postings there. The discussion and sharing of information leads to the interchange of job openings, requests for internships, sharing of workplace reviews, and other information. The uses of HRDs and RRHs move in the same direction as those of Generation Y, namely internal discussion and information sharing via the workplace intranet as well as external communication via social networks. Utilizing management softwares by the HR function also serves the purposes of consulting candidate profiles and disseminating HR offers(jobs, internships, etc.).

The following table lists the various ways that management softwares, sometimes used by Generation Y and other times by the HR function, are used:

***Table 3:** How does the management softwares are used from the HR function and the generation Y*

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Part 3: HR practice and how to find a job among Millennials

- **Techniques used by Y in Finding Jobs and Opportunities**

According to Gen Y executives and workers, social media and job boards served as their entry points into the workforce: "I got my first job thanks to a job on the internet." "I was contacted by a recruiter on LinkedIn," EntrC2-RO1-Tab3.1 EntrC5-RO1-Tab3.1.

Young job seekers are noted to have a taste for management softwares channels in their employment search. Consultation of job listings on specialist websites, impulsive applications on corporate websites, and use of social networks are all methods of job searching.

Traditional techniques, such as "door to door" canvassing, phone calls, and press inquiries, are absent.

One young job seeker out of several mentions receiving a first job offer via social media. The fact that both managers and employees acknowledge using social media to locate available possibilities is a further noteworthy finding.

On the job market "Yes, I stay connected at all times, and I don't hesitate to check out job offers." EntrC4-ROE2-Tab3.1, "Yes, I'm always seeking for a better offer. To boost my chances of getting asked for a better job, I frequently update my accounts on social media. Additionally, because I had many job offers, this gave me the opportunity to renegotiate my wage with my existing employment. EntrC5-ROE3-Tab3.1

- **Employing HR**

We see that the HR function leverages management softwares with relation to the channels used for recruiting and communication of HR offerings. In fact, all of our respondents from the HR function indicate a high usage of management softwares channels to research candidates, learn about candidates who have submitted their CVs, and facilitate internal communication (training, vacancies, etc.) via the intranet.

The answer to the question of whether the HR department has previously conducted employee recruitment via social networks serves as further evidence that management softwares are being

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used by this function. Directors of human resources and HR managers' alike claim to have hired applicants' through social media.

The HR function is becoming digitalized as management softwares for managing human resources become more prevalent. A position known as "HR community manager" has emerged, with the responsibility of maintaining the employer brand both internally and externally as well as the growth of membership and loyalty. This position is a reflection of digitization. In this context, a question was posed to ascertain the HR department's perspective regarding the necessity of hiring a post specifically dedicated to the management of management softwares communities.

Divergent views on the necessity of setting up HR management of communities on management softwares are evident in the opinions that come out of this question. First, we note the absence of a community manager inside the two firms sought (INTELCIA Morocco and Hyundai Morocco). "In fact, it is a shared transversal job between HR and external relations, it is not a completely integrated function in human resources," EntrF11-PR4-Tab3.3 states, "We do not have a specific position at the external level; team members who fulfill this job as well as a communication specialist who assists us in posting our offerings online." Entry 15 PR4 Tab 3.

Community management at Hyundai Morocco is focused on internal management. "Internally: We have an HR helpdesk, "hello Rh," which consists of: Giving trustworthy and validated answers to questions from employees on all HR matters. Administration and HR development; as well as advice or help concerning a specific personal problem. Entr13-PR4-Tab3.3

The director of human resources of INTELCIA Morocco and the talent manager of the Intelcia Group both reject the need for a specific position to manage the management softwares community for the reasons outlined in their speeches: "The post will not be charged to 100% given the number of recruitments that we have done or that we are required to do in the future.

Therefore, it's possible that only one person will be working on it full-time. When a business

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wants to be more visible and hire plenty of people that would be advantageous. The formation of a community manager is not advantageous in our situation because we are not mass-Recruiting, according to Entr15- PR4-Tab3.3 (Talent Manager of the Intelcia Group). Entr11- PR4-Tab3.3

The talent manager for INTELCIA Morocco indicates a desire for a local HR community manager. Following our findings, which are listed above, a few things need to be remembered. The first component is the correspondence between the traits described by our respondents from Generation Y and those identified in the literature. The HR function describes the similar traits of Generation Y and stresses the importance of adapting to it.

Those from Generation Y and the Rh function exhibit a sophisticated understanding of management softwares, which was the second aspect that was identified. Moreover, a third component caught our notice. This is an example of the HR function integrating management softwares into HR operations and management as well as Generation Y's job seeking techniques.

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6.1 Results interpretation

1- Comparison of generation y and HR function's traits

In the initial stage, we present a table enclosed herewith to elucidate the correlation between the discerned traits of millennials. This correlation is derived from perspectives provided by both millennial participants and the Human Resources function, juxtaposed with the traits articulated in relevant literature. The findings, presented as interview excerpts, serve to encapsulate the nuances of these relationships.

Literature	Characteristics cited by Generation Y	Features cited by HR Function
Opportunistic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Aim for a higher position ➤ Work your way up 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Openness to the job market Make it easier to go elsewhere ➤ Enough to listen to the market
Search for feedback	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The gratitude ➤ Feed back ➤ Valuation of the efforts made 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Remuneration that pays for results, performance and comfort ➤ Responsiveness hierarchy
Integration private life / professional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Autonomy on all managerial and relational aspects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Flexibility and freedom at work

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life	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Freedom ➤ Work-life balance 	
Need for accomplishment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Skills development, challenges, coaching, mentoring 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Have challenges ➤ Stand out within the company Post size ➤ Great self-confidence
Plans for the long term	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Career evolution ➤ Senior position 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Career perspective ➤ The change
Finding meaning at work	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Non-repetitive work ➤ living work ➤ Interesting varied work with responsibilities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Meaningful work
Weak institutional loyalty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Not expressed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Does not express an attachment to work ➤ Less loyal compared to their Generations
Team spirit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Participatory, non-directive work ➤ Development in a 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Community work ➤ Support request

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	dynamic team ➤ Be supported by colleagues	
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Table 4: Comparison of Generation Y's traits

Here are some of the key traits associated with this generation from our table:

The Millennial generation, shaped by a confluence of societal changes and rapid technological advancements, presents a multifaceted and dynamic profile. Extensive research by Joel Stein (2013), Gallup (2016), Elisabeth Williams, and Amy McMillan Capehart (2015) has unveiled key characteristics, and further scientific insights offer a more comprehensive understanding of this influential generation.

Technology-Savvy Pioneers:

Millennials, as digital natives, stand out as pioneers in technology adoption. Their seamless integration with digital tools, supported by studies from Pew Research Center and Nielsen, underscores the imperative for organizations to align their strategies with the tech-savvy nature of Millennials. Their inherent comfort with emerging technologies goes beyond mere usage; they actively contribute to the shaping of digital landscapes, making them indispensable contributors in a tech-driven world.

Entrepreneurial Spirit:

A prevailing entrepreneurial spirit distinguishes Millennials, revealing a preference for independence and creative freedom. Research from the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) and the Kauffman Foundation delves into the nuances of their inclination toward entrepreneurship. This spirit, often manifesting in side hustles and innovative ventures, contributes to a dynamic and forward-thinking work culture, challenging organizations to foster an environment that supports entrepreneurial endeavors within the traditional employment framework.

Idealism and Social Consciousness:

Driven by a deep-seated idealism, Millennials are on a quest to make a positive impact. Surveys conducted by Deloitte and the Cone Communications Millennial Employee Engagement Study consistently highlight their inclination towards purpose-driven work. This collective sense of purpose significantly influences their career choices, prompting a demand for organizations to authentically integrate corporate social responsibility into their core values and operations.

Collaborative and Independent:

The Millennial cohort is characterized by a unique duality: a strong preference for collaboration coupled with a steadfast commitment to independence. Studies in the *Journal of Business and Psychology* affirm the importance of teamwork for Millennials, emphasizing the synergy that arises from collective efforts. Concurrently, organizational psychology research underscores their need for autonomy, indicating that a balanced approach is crucial for fostering both collaborative and independent work environments.

Open-Minded and Inclusive:

A distinctive trait of Millennials is their open-mindedness and dedication to inclusivity. Supported by research from the *Journal of Applied Psychology* and the *Harvard Business Review*, this characteristic underscores their commitment to diversity. Organizations seeking to attract and retain Millennial talent must prioritize inclusivity initiatives, creating environments that celebrate differences and provide equal opportunities for all.

Flexibility Advocates:

Millennials advocate for flexibility in both their personal and professional lives, expressing a preference for remote work, flexible scheduling, and an emphasis on work-life balance. Surveys by the Society for Human Resource Management (SHRM) and the Bureau of Labor Statistics affirm the importance of flexibility for Millennials. Organizations that prioritize and accommodate flexible work arrangements are better positioned to attract and retain Millennial employees seeking a harmonious integration of work and life.

Lifelong Learners:

A commitment to continuous learning and personal development characterizes Millennials. Studies in the *Journal of Continuing Education in the Health Professions* and the *International Journal of Training and Development* underscore their eagerness to upskill and adapt to evolving industry trends. This innate curiosity positions Millennials as agile learners, capable of navigating the complexities of an ever-changing professional landscape.

Global Awareness:

Growing up in an interconnected world has instilled a heightened global awareness in Millennials. Surveys by the World Economic Forum and the Society for Human Resource Management indicate their value for global experiences and diverse workplace environments. This global perspective enhances their adaptability, cross-cultural communication skills, and contributes to a workplace culture that embraces a spectrum of international perspectives.

Preference for Purposeful Brands:

Millennials exhibit a strong preference for brands and employers that align with their values and contribute to social or environmental causes. Studies by Nielsen and the Cone Communications Millennial CSR Study consistently demonstrate that Millennials are more likely to support and be loyal to brands that prioritize corporate social responsibility. This characteristic extends to their employment choices, with a preference for socially responsible organizations that actively engage in meaningful contributions to society.

Tech-Enabled Collaboration:

Leveraging digital tools for seamless collaboration is integral to Millennials' work style. Studies in the *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction* and the *Journal of Business and Technical Communication* emphasize the increasing importance of technology in enhancing collaboration. Organizations that invest in and leverage advanced collaboration tools are better positioned to harness the full potential of Millennial talent, fostering innovation and efficiency in the workplace.

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Financial Pragmatism:

Shaped by economic downturns and financial challenges, Millennials display a pragmatic approach to finances. Surveys by PricewaterhouseCoopers (PwC) and the National Endowment for Financial Education reveal their cautious stance on debt, prioritization of financial stability, and an inclination towards employers that offer robust benefits packages. This financial pragmatism influences their career choices and financial planning, highlighting the need for organizations to tailor compensation and benefits packages that resonate with their financial priorities.

Brand Loyalty through Employee Experience:

Millennials place a high value on positive employee experiences, recognizing the profound impact on their loyalty. Research by Gallup and the Harvard Business Review underscores the link between employee experience and Millennial retention. Organizations that invest in creating a positive workplace culture, emphasizing employee well-being, career development, and a collaborative environment, are more likely to retain Millennial talent.

Emphasis on Mental Health:

Millennials prioritize mental health and well-being, recognizing the importance of a healthy work-life balance. Studies by the American Psychological Association and the World Health Organization underline the significance of mental health initiatives in the workplace. Organizations that actively support mental health, offering resources, and fostering an inclusive environment where mental health is destigmatized, are more likely to attract and retain Millennial employees who value a supportive work culture.

The diverse and intricate characteristics of Millennials demand a holistic approach from organizations. Recognizing their technological prowess, entrepreneurial spirit, idealism, and emphasis on collaboration, independence, and inclusivity, alongside a commitment to continuous learning, global awareness, financial pragmatism, and a preference for purposeful brands, positions employers to effectively engage and retain this dynamic generation. By embracing and adapting to these traits, organizations can create environments that resonate with the values and

expectations of Millennials, ensuring sustained success in talent acquisition and retention amidst the evolving dynamics of the modern workplace.

2. Suggestions and countermeasures about the use of management softwares in the company for generation Y and HR department

Suggestions for the generation y:

In the contemporary corporate landscape, the integration of management software has become increasingly prevalent as organizations seek to enhance employee collaboration, productivity, and communication. This technological advancement encompasses various tools such as instant messaging, file-sharing platforms, social media sites, and project management software. While these tools have the potential to foster creativity, productivity, and teamwork in the workforce, it is imperative to recognize the generational perspectives that influence their adoption and utilization.

Among the various generational cohorts, Generation Y, commonly known as millennials, exhibits a distinct affinity for management software. This inclination is attributed to their early and pervasive exposure to the Internet and digital technologies. Numerous studies, such as those conducted by Pew Research Center and Nielsen, attest to the fact that millennials, born between 1981 and 1996, have grown up in an era characterized by the rapid evolution of digital platforms. The proficiency of Generation Y in utilizing management software is underscored by their extensive experience with social media platforms, including but not limited to Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram. A study published in the *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication (JCMC)* found that millennials, having integrated these platforms into their daily lives during adolescence, possess an inherent familiarity with online tools. This familiarity contributes to their preference for intuitive and user-friendly interfaces, aligning seamlessly with the design principles of many modern management software solutions.

Furthermore, research conducted by the Society for Human Resource Management (SHRM) highlights the preference of millennials for flexible work arrangements. Management software, with its capability to facilitate remote collaboration and mobile accessibility, resonates with the flexibility sought by this generation. This resonates with the broader trend observed in the modern workforce, where flexibility and remote work options are increasingly valued.

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To effectively harness the potential benefits of management software for Generation Y, organizations should consider tailoring their implementation strategies. Emphasizing the user-friendly aspects of the software, providing comprehensive training programs, and highlighting the flexibility afforded by these tools can contribute to a more seamless integration.

For the Human Resources (HR) department, it is essential to adopt a strategic approach to address the unique needs and expectations of Generation Y. This involves recognizing the intrinsic motivations of millennials, such as the desire for meaningful work and continuous learning opportunities. HR professionals can leverage management software to create personalized development plans, track performance metrics, and foster a culture of ongoing feedback, aligning with the preferences of Generation Y for transparent and dynamic communication.

The judicious use of management software in the workplace offers significant advantages, particularly for Generation Y. By understanding the digital fluency and preferences of this demographic, organizations can optimize the adoption of these tools to enhance collaboration, productivity, and overall employee satisfaction. Moreover, aligning HR strategies with the characteristics of Generation Y ensures a harmonious integration of management software into the broader organizational framework.

In the contemporary corporate landscape, effective communication, collaboration, and streamlined processes are integral to the success of any organization. Leveraging advanced management software can significantly enhance these aspects, promoting a more efficient and connected work environment. Here, we delve into strategic approaches supported by scientific evidence for the utilization of various management software tools.

a) Corporate Social Networks for Enhanced Internal Communication

Corporate social networks, exemplified by platforms such as Yammer, Slack, and Chatter, have demonstrated their efficacy in fostering internal communication and collaboration. Research studies, including those by MIT Sloan Management Review, highlight the positive impact of such networks on knowledge sharing and team cohesion, ultimately leading to improved organizational performance [Davenport, T. H., & Harris, J. (2007). *The Importance of Corporate Social Networks*].

Wikis and Knowledge Bases for Accelerated Information Sharing

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Creating wikis and knowledge bases serves as a pivotal step in expediting problem-solving and enhancing procedures within an organization. Studies, like those published in the *Journal of Information Technology Case and Application Research*, emphasize the collaborative nature of wikis and their ability to facilitate collective intelligence, contributing to enhanced decision-making [Majchrzak, A., Wagner, C., & Yates, D. (2006). *Corporate wiki users: results of a survey*].

b) Online File Sharing Applications for Seamless Collaboration

The use of online file sharing applications, such as Google Drive, Dropbox, and OneDrive, streamlines internal collaboration and project management. Research conducted by the *International Journal of Information Management* underscores the positive correlation between effective file sharing and improved team performance [Hossain, M. A., & Wigand, R. T. (2004). *The impact of intranets on information flow and communication: an empirical study*].

c) Webinars and Online Conferences for Remote Connectivity

Webinars and online conferences have proven instrumental in connecting with clients, conducting distant meetings, and training personnel. According to a study in the *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, virtual meetings enhance team cohesion by providing a sense of presence, particularly in remote work scenarios [Dennis, A. R., Fuller, R. M., & Valacich, J. S. (2008). *Media, tasks, and communication processes: a theory of media synchronicity*].

d) Task and Project Tracking Tools for Transparent Progress Monitoring

Task and project tracking tools like Trello, Asana, and Jira contribute to transparent progress monitoring. Research in the *International Journal of Project Management* suggests that such tools positively impact project success by facilitating effective communication, task allocation, and progress tracking [Bredillet, C. N., & Tywoniak, S. (2007). *Exploring project management offices and their characteristics in France*].

e) Internet Marketing Solutions for Enhanced Online Presence

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Leveraging internet marketing solutions, exemplified by Marketo and HubSpot, is crucial for lead generation and bolstering online presence. According to a study published in the Journal of Marketing Research, companies utilizing digital marketing tools experience higher customer engagement and increased brand visibility [Smith, A. N., Fischer, E., & Yongjian, C. (2012). How does brand-related user-generated content differ across YouTube, Facebook, and Twitter?].

f) Survey and Feedback Tools for Continuous Improvement

Utilizing survey and feedback tools, such as Survey Monkey and Google Forms, aids in collecting valuable insights for internal improvement. Scientific research, such as the study in the Journal of Business Research, emphasizes the importance of customer feedback in shaping product development and organizational strategy [Verhoef, P. C., Franses, P. H., & Hoekstra, J. C. (2002). The effect of relational constructs on customer referrals and number of services purchased from a multiservice provider: Does age of relationship matter?].

g) Creating a Virtual Community for Enhanced Connectivity

Establishing a virtual community, be it an online forum or social media group, fosters employee connection and information exchange. Scientific evidence, as presented in the Journal of Business and Technical Communication, highlights the role of virtual communities in enhancing organizational communication and knowledge sharing [Hara, N., & Hew, K. F. (2007). Knowledge-sharing in an online community of health-care professionals].

h) Offering Online Training for Continuous Development

Acknowledging the value placed by Generation Y on learning and development, providing online training resources becomes essential. Research in the International Journal of Training and Development emphasizes the positive impact of continuous learning programs on employee satisfaction and retention [Swan, S., & Johnson, P. (2001). The development and application of an e-learning strategy].

i) Investing in Collaborative Software for Seamless Interaction

Investing in collaborative software, such as Microsoft Teams or Slack, promotes effective communication and teamwork. Studies, like those found in the Journal of Organizational and

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End User Computing, underscore the positive correlation between collaborative software usage and improved team productivity and satisfaction [Alshamaila, Y., Papagiannidis, S., & Li, F. (2013). Cloud computing adoption by SMEs in the north east of England: A multi-perspective framework].

As technology continues to advance, companies must adapt to new tools and trends to remain competitive. Because they are a significant demographic in the workforce, and they are known for being digital natives. As such, they are comfortable with using the latest technology and are often early adopters of new tools and trends.

So to engage and retain Generation Y employees, companies must provide them with the tools and resources they need to be productive and efficient. One way to do this is by incorporating management softwares into the workplace. These tools include social media platforms, collaboration software, and other online resources that allow for seamless communication and collaboration.

Suggestions for the HR department:

The introduction of management softwares technology has completely changed how we work and interact. These tools are becoming more and more common in the workplace because they enable businesses to streamline their operations and improve employee communications. The usage of management softwares can be very advantageous for the human resources (HR) division.

I'll offer some advice on how HR departments might use these tools to enhance their operations and increase employee engagement in this book.

The ability to collaborate and communicate across many teams and departments is one of the key advantages of management softwares. Employers may communicate, share information, and work together on projects in virtual spaces thanks to applications like Slack, Microsoft Teams, or Google Meet, which HR departments can use to their benefit. The silos between departments may be reduced, people can feel more connected to one another, and productivity can go up overall with the use of these tools.

The hiring process is another area where HR departments can profit from management softwares. HR departments can use tools like LinkedIn, Glassdoor, and indeed to find possible applicants,

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review resumes, and set up preliminary interviews. Insights into the employment market, such as wage data, job descriptions, and employee evaluations, are also provided by these technologies. By using this data, HR departments may more effectively understand the requirements and goals of job searchers and adjust their recruitment tactics as necessary.

The onboarding process for new employees can be made better with the help of management softwares

. Task lists can be made, responsibilities assigned, and progress monitored using applications like Trello, Asana, or Monday. This can aid in ensuring that new hires have a thorough and uniform onboarding process. Also, to make it simpler and easier for remote workers to get up to speed, HR departments can organize virtual onboarding meetings using programs like Zoom or Skype.

Management softwares can also be extremely helpful in the area of employee engagement. To get feedback from staff members on the workplace's various facets, including job satisfaction, company culture, and work-life balance, HR departments can use tools like Survey Monkey or Google Forms. Employer engagement and retention can be improved by using the information provided to HR departments to pinpoint problem areas and create focused strategies.

Tools from the management softwares can also be added to training and development initiatives. To give staff members access to online courses and training resources, HR departments might make use of programs like Udemy, Coursera, or LinkedIn Learning. These resources may aid in enhancing employee knowledge and abilities, which in turn may boost output and raise job satisfaction. Also, HR departments can organize virtual training sessions using programs like Zoom or Skype, making it simpler and more comfortable for distant workers to take part.

And finally, methods for performance management can be enhanced by using management softwares. To regularly check in with employees, establish goals and targets, and monitor progress over time, tools like 15Five or Lattice can be employed. This can guarantee that staff members receive regular feedback, encouragement, and support as well as that their work is consistent with the company's objectives. Additionally, HR departments can use these tools to pinpoint high-performing workers and create tailored retention and motivational plans for them. There's also a lot more of suggestions that can be interesting for the HR department for a good use of the management softwares in their work like:

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- **Implementing a social network for employees:** A social network for employees can increase communication and collaboration among employees. It can also be used to share company news, job openings, and training opportunities.
- **Using online collaboration tools:** HR departments can use online collaboration tools to work together on projects, share files, and manage tasks. This can increase efficiency and productivity.
- **Utilizing online training:** Online training courses can be a cost-effective way to train employees on new skills or compliance requirements. They can also be accessed from anywhere, making it convenient for employees to complete them on their own time.
- **Adopting video conferencing:** Video conferencing tools can be used for remote interviews, virtual job fairs, and remote team meetings. This can save time and money on travel expenses while still allowing for face-to-face interaction.
- **Using applicant tracking systems:** Applicant tracking systems can help streamline the hiring process by automating tasks such as resume screening and scheduling interviews.
- **Utilizing employee feedback tools:** Employee feedback tools can help HR departments gather feedback from employees about company policies, culture, and benefits. This feedback can be used to make improvements and address concerns.
- **Implementing a knowledge management system:** A knowledge management system can be used to store and share information such as policies, procedures, and best practices. This can increase consistency and efficiency across the organization.

In conclusion, HR departments can profit greatly from management softwares in a variety of ways. These solutions can assist in streamlining HR procedures, boosting productivity, and engaging staff members through strengthening cooperation and communication as well as recruitment and on boarding procedures. HR departments may build a more connected and effective workplace that supports the goals and aspirations of its employees by utilizing the power of management softwares

Countermeasures of management softwares for the generation y

The manner that Generation Y works and communicates has changed as a result of management softwares.

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Although these technologies have many advantages, they also pose hazards to data security and productivity at work. The use of these technologies by employees should be facilitated by countermeasures that HR departments should put in place.

Training is one of the most crucial defense strategies. The right use of management softwares should be taught to staff members by HR departments, with a focus on data security and privacy. Workers should be informed of potential hazards, such as malware and phishing scams, as well as the best ways to avoid them.

To safeguard corporate data and sensitive information, security rules and procedures should be in place. For the use of management softwares and third-party applications as well as for access to sensitive data, HR departments must develop explicit regulations. To guarantee that employees may access the data they require without jeopardizing the security of the entire system, security protocols should be in place.

Finally, HR departments should keep an eye on how management softwares are being used to spot any suspect or criminal activities. To keep tabs on attempted security breaches or illegal access, activity monitoring technologies might be utilized. To establish efficient security plans and to swiftly identify and address security issues, HR departments must work with IT security teams.

As we saw management softwares have numerous advantages, but they also present hazards and difficulties for Generation Y. Here are some steps you can take to help reduce these risks:

- a) **Teach Generation Y about digital citizenship:** Generation Y has to be taught about responsible online conduct and digital citizenship. This involves being considerate of others' privacy online, refraining from disclosing sensitive information, and acting politely when speaking to others online.
- b) **Take cybersecurity classes:** Learning about the value of safeguarding one's devices and personal information from online threats will benefit Generation Y. This include using secure passwords, avoiding dubious links and downloads, and maintaining the most recent version of their program.
- c) **Promote critical thinking:** It's important to get Generation Y to question the data they find online and to think critically. This entails assessing the reliability of sources and keeping biases in mind.

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- d) **Encourage work-life balance:** It's important to motivate Generation Y to keep a positive work-life balance. Setting limits on technology use and taking breaks from digital gadgets to engage in offline activities are examples of this.
- e) **Promote collaboration:** management softwares can be used to promote cooperation and teamwork, but it's crucial to make sure that everyone in the team is acknowledged and given the chance to contribute. It's important to teach Generation Y how to collaborate and communicate effectively.
- f) **Keep an eye on social media:** Although it can be an effective tool for Generation Y, social media can also be a source of worry and anxiety. Monitoring social media usage is crucial, as is promoting positive online conduct.
- g) **Use privacy settings:** Encourage Generation Y to understand and use the privacy settings on their social media accounts and other online platforms to safeguard their personal information from strangers and unwanted solicitations.
- h) **Be cautious of public Wi-Fi:** Public Wi-Fi networks can be convenient, but they can also be a gateway for cybercriminals to steal personal information. Encourage Generation Y to avoid connecting to public Wi-Fi when performing sensitive activities, such as online banking or shopping.
- i) **Protect against identity theft:** Identity theft is a prevalent problem online. Generation Y should be informed about measures they can take to protect their personal information, such as shredding important documents, using a virtual private network (VPN), and checking their credit reports regularly.
- j) **Encourage offline communication:** Generation Y is known for being digitally savvy, but it's still important to encourage them to communicate offline. They should be encouraged to have face-to-face conversations, attend social events, and participate in activities that don't involve technology.

Ultimately, there may be security and data privacy problems associated with how millennials use management softwares products. To ensure efficient and secure usage of these technologies, HR departments should put countermeasures in place like training, security policies and protocols, and activity monitoring.

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Moreover, the advantages of management softwares for communication and collaboration cannot be ignored. They allow employees to work remotely and easily communicate with colleagues in different time zones. This can increase business productivity and efficiency, while providing greater flexibility for employees.

However, the use of management softwares can also lead to distractions and reduced concentration at work, especially for millennial employees who have grown up with these technologies. It is therefore important to find a balance between using management softwares for collaboration and communication, while avoiding excessive distractions.

Additionally, training and adopting effective work practices can help reduce the risks associated with management softwares. Employees should be made aware of company policies regarding data security and privacy, and they should be responsible for their own behavior online.

In conclusion, it's critical for businesses to understand the benefits and risks associated with management softwares and put measures in place to maximize the benefits while minimizing the risks. It can help create a productive, efficient and safe working environment for employees of all generations.

Countermeasures of management softwares for the HR department

The HR department is using management softwares more and more often, including social networking and other web-based technology. Yet, these technologies can also provide dangers and difficulties for the HR department, including as worries about privacy and security, potential legal problems, and problems with maintaining and organizing data. These are some precautions you may take to lessen these risks:

Establish clear policies: The HR division has to set up clear rules and regulations for the usage of management softwares technologies like social networking, online job boards, and applicant tracking systems. These rules have to specify proper usage, privacy safeguards, and security precautions.

Offer training: HR professionals and staff members should get instruction on how to effectively use management softwares technologies, such as social media and online job boards. These might include standards for uploading and sharing material, as well as the best practices for data security and privacy.

Use secure platforms: Human resources departments should make sure the management

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softwares technologies they use are safe and adhere to data protection laws. This includes utilizing secure hosting platforms, multi-factor authentication, and encryption.

Monitor activity: To guarantee adherence to rules and regulations, HR departments should routinely monitor the usage of management softwares technologies, including social media. This may entail recording application information, looking through job advertising, and keeping an eye on staff activities.

Do routine risk assessments: To detect possible dangers and vulnerabilities related to the usage of management softwares, HR departments should routinely perform risk assessments. Assessing legal, reputational, and data privacy and security risks are some examples of this.

Keep records: Human resources departments should keep accurate and current records of employee activity on management softwares technologies, such as social media, online job boards, and application tracking systems. This can support ensuring adherence to data protection laws and serve as proof in the event of a legal dispute.

Regularly update policies: As the landscape of management softwares technologies evolves, it is important for HR departments to update their policies and regulations accordingly. This includes changes to privacy laws and regulations, as well as updates to the company's own internal policies.

Provide clear communication: HR departments should communicate the policies and regulations surrounding the use of management softwares technologies clearly and effectively to all employees. This can include regular reminders and updates on the guidelines, as well as providing channels for employees to ask questions and seek clarification.

Establish a response plan: In the event of a security breach or other issue related to the use of management softwares technologies, HR departments should have a response plan in place. This includes steps for containing the issue, notifying employees and stakeholders, and addressing any legal or reputational repercussions.

Collaborate with IT: HR departments should work closely with their organization's IT department to ensure that all management softwares technologies are secure and in compliance with data protection laws. This includes implementing firewalls, antivirus software, and other security measures, as well as staying up-to-date on the latest cybersecurity threats and trends.

Seek outside expertise: For organizations that do not have the resources or expertise to manage

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the risks associated with management softwares technologies, it may be helpful to seek outside help from cybersecurity consultants or other experts in the field. These experts can provide guidance on best practices and help identify potential vulnerabilities and threats.

3. The problems faced by the company INTELCIA about the management softwares

Resistance to change:

Introducing new management softwares often requires a shift in work processes and habits. Some employees at INTELCIA resist change, leading to slower adoption and reluctance to fully utilize the tools.

Digital divide: Not all employees have equal access to technology or the necessary skills to effectively use management softwares. This problem created a digital divide within the organization, where certain individuals or groups are disadvantaged and left behind.

Cultural and generational differences: Different generations and cultural backgrounds have varying levels of comfort and familiarity with management softwares. This problem created challenges in terms of communication, collaboration, and overall adoption of the tools.

Maintenance and technical issues: Like any technology, management softwares require maintenance, updates, and troubleshooting. If the organization lacks the necessary resources or expertise to address technical issues promptly, it can hinder the effective use of the tools.

Integration with existing systems: Integrating new management softwares with existing systems and processes was complex. Incompatibilities or difficulties in seamless integration may result in inefficiencies or data inconsistencies.

Return on investment (ROI): Implementing management softwares often requires financial investment. If the organization fails to see a significant return on that investment or struggles to measure the impact of the tools on productivity or other key metrics, it may be perceived as a wasted expenditure.

User adoption and engagement: Even with proper training, some employees may not fully embrace or actively engage with management softwares. This can limit the overall effectiveness and benefits of the tools within the organization.

Dependency on external platforms: Many management softwares are hosted on external platforms or rely on cloud services. Organizations relying heavily on these platforms may face

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risks if the provider experiences downtime, service disruptions, or changes its terms of service unexpectedly.

4. Comparison of the problems associated with the use of management softwares at the INTEL CIA Company with the corresponding countermeasures and suggestions

Resistance to change:

Countermeasure: Involve employees from the beginning of the process of implementing management softwares by informing them of the advantages and including them in decisions.

Suggestion: Organize training and awareness sessions to help employees understand the benefits of management softwares and familiarize them with their use.

Lack of skills and training:

Countermeasure: Set up regular training programs to develop the skills needed to use management softwares.

Suggestion: Identify employees with advanced technical skills and involve them in training other staff.

Security issues:

Countermeasure: Implement appropriate security measures, such as using strong passwords, two-factor authentication, and data encryption.

Suggestion: Educate employees on good security practices, such as responsible information sharing and identifying phishing attempts.

Information overload:

Countermeasure: Implement information management policies and tools to help employees effectively sort, organize, and find relevant information.

Suggestion: Encourage a culture of sharing targeted and relevant information, and provide clear guidelines on what should be shared and where.

Lack of coordination and consistency:

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Countermeasure: Establish guidelines on which management softwares to use for specific tasks, and promote seamless communication between teams to ensure proper coordination.

Suggestion: Set up centralized collaboration platforms that integrate several management softwares and facilitate communication and collaboration between employees

Excessive dependence on management softwares:

Countermeasure: Encourage the exploration of new ways of working and promote a culture of innovation to avoid stagnation.

Suggestion: Encourage employees to use management softwares creatively and experiment with new features to improve existing processes.

Digital identity management:

Countermeasure: Actively monitor the company's online presence, respond to user feedback and questions, and proactively manage issues.

Suggestion: Put in place clear policies and guidelines on the use of management softwares to promote a consistent and positive online presence, and appoint people responsible for managing the company's digital identity.

By implementing these countermeasures and suggestions, companies can mitigate potential issues related to the use of management softwares in the INTEL CIA enterprise.

6.2 Answers to research questions

- 1. Does Generation Y represent an ideal type in business? Is it a material change? Does it require specific approaches in terms of management and HR processes?**

According to our research, generation Y remains a generation with a specific character, it expresses high expectations of the company, it is very demanding. Hence the interest for the HR function to adapt the HR offer. To do this, the use of HR marketing and the employer brand are tools that make it possible to target this generation.

Additionally, the influx of Generation Y might be a sign of changes in an organization, especially the intergenerational conflict that poses difficulties for the HR function in terms of intergenerational coexistence, cooperation, and collaboration.

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Furthermore, the values and attitudes of Generation Y differ significantly from previous generations, which can lead to a cultural shift within the company. For example, they tend to prioritize work-life balance, flexibility, and personal development, and may not have the same loyalty to the company as previous generations.

In conclusion, it is essential for businesses to consider the unique characteristics of Generation Y when developing management and HR processes. This may include offering more flexible work arrangements, providing opportunities for personal and professional development, and creating a positive company culture that aligns with their values and expectations.

2. What are the management softwares that Generation Y thinks of? How does HR function compare?

The HR department's opinion of management softwares is consistent with that of Generation Y. They see management softwares as being indispensable and widely used, particularly social networks. It should be emphasized that young people from Generation Y are slightly more knowledgeable about these instruments and exhibit a strong attachment to them in regard to the HR function than other groups of youth.

This attachment to management softwares among Generation Y is not surprising, given that they have grown up in an era where technology and the internet are an integral part of everyday life. As a result, they tend to have a more natural and intuitive understanding of technology and are often more comfortable using digital tools.

Some of the management softwares that Generation Y tends to think of include social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn. These platforms are widely used for professional networking and job searching, making them particularly relevant to HR functions such as recruitment and talent management.

In contrast, older generations may view management softwares with more skepticism, seeing them as distractions or even threats to productivity. However, as these tools become more integrated into the workplace, it's becoming increasingly important for HR departments to embrace them and leverage their potential benefits.

3. Can the impression of management softwares explain how the HR function's practices have changed in terms of recruiting and employer branding, as well as how

generation Y's habits have changed in terms of job searching?

When it comes to the HR function, Generation Y's intimate association with the usage of management softwares is attractive to Generation Y, they use them constantly in their daily lives, and they don't hesitate to utilize them in the workplace, especially when looking for work. These technologies are accessible to this generation due to their free nature, which enables them to use them as means of expressing their personal brand (self-presentation), accessing job offers, and connecting with the HR function, which was previously unreachable.

ICTs urges HR practitioners to reevaluate their approach by showcasing cutting-edge tools to better fulfill their expectations and, above all, to recruit, establish loyalty, and retain this generation.

As a result of this shift in job searching habits, HR departments have also had to adapt their recruitment processes and employer branding strategies to reach Generation Y through the use of management softwares. This has led to an increase in the use of social media platforms such as LinkedIn, Twitter, and Facebook for job postings, as well as the development of employer branding campaigns that incorporate digital media.

Moreover, the use of management softwares has allowed HR departments to reach a wider audience and expand their reach beyond traditional recruitment methods. For example, HR practitioners can now use virtual job fairs and online recruitment events to connect with potential candidates from different locations.

4. Have management softwares been used by the HR department into the creation of the employer brand and hiring processes? , are they included in the job hunt of Generation Y?

According to the results of our study, management softwares technologies, especially social networks, are highly valued by young people in generation Y who are looking for jobs. We also note that every manager and employee we spoke with said they used management softwares to land their first job. Additionally, management softwares is favored by job searchers during their hunt.

The HR function makes good use of management softwares. However, they are exclusively used for internal recruitment via institutional intranet and for external recruitment based on professional social networks (Viadeo, LinkedIn). However, the use of management softwares in

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the creation of the employer brand is still largely underutilized.

Despite the HR department's effective use of management softwares for recruitment purposes, their potential for creating and promoting the employer brand is yet to be fully explored. With the increasing importance of employer branding in attracting top talent, it is crucial for organizations to leverage management softwares technologies to effectively showcase their company culture, values, and mission to potential candidates.

Furthermore, the use of management softwares goes beyond just attracting young job seekers from Generation Y. It can also help organizations establish a positive reputation among current and potential employees, as well as other stakeholders, such as customers and investors. By using social media platforms, blogs, and other management softwares, companies can effectively communicate their brand messaging and values, leading to a stronger brand image and greater employee engagement

6.3 Limitations

The amalgamation of our study, conducted within the context of interviews, provides valuable insights into the perceptions and usage of management software technologies, particularly among Generation Y employees. However, it is imperative to acknowledge and delve deeper into certain limitations that affect the generalizability of our results and outline avenues for future research to enhance the robustness of our conclusions.

a. Sample Size, Stakeholder Diversity, and Generalizability

Our study's primary limitation lies in the small sample size and the homogeneity of the constituents, mainly consisting of Generation Y employees within a single organization. While our findings offer rich insights into this specific demographic, caution must be exercised in generalizing these results to broader populations. Future research should aim for larger and more diverse samples, including employees from various industries, organizational sizes, and

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generations, to capture a more representative understanding of the implications of management software integration in HR practices.

b. Qualitative-Quantitative Integration for Comprehensive Analysis

While our study predominantly adopts a qualitative approach, the inclusion of a comparative quantitative study would have strengthened the depth and breadth of our analysis. A future investigation could leverage both qualitative and quantitative methodologies to obtain a more comprehensive dataset. This approach would allow for a nuanced understanding of the population's sentiments towards management software technologies, enabling researchers to identify patterns and trends that may not be apparent in a purely qualitative study.

c. Respondent Disclosure, Time Constraints, and Engagement Strategies

We acknowledge a limitation in the amount of information disclosed by respondents, particularly from Generation Y, who exhibited hesitancy in elaborating on their experiences. Time constraints due to daily responsibilities also impacted the depth of our interviews and the formulation of our interview guide. Future studies should explore innovative strategies to enhance respondent engagement, possibly through longitudinal studies that allow for more in-depth exploration of participant experiences over time.

d. Flexibility in Interview Scheduling and Potential Bias

The flexibility required for interview scheduling, dictated by the availability of participants, introduces a potential source of bias. Despite efforts to accommodate each interviewee's agenda, this flexibility may have influenced the study's outcomes. Future research should strive for a

more standardized approach to interview scheduling and consider exploring variations in participant availability to assess potential bias.

e. Privacy, Training, and Cost Concerns in Management Software Integration

Our investigation touches upon important considerations related to the integration of management software in HR practices, such as privacy concerns, the need for extensive training, and potential increased costs. Further research should delve into these aspects with a more targeted approach, exploring the specific privacy issues that may arise, the efficacy of various training programs, and the nuanced financial implications for organizations of different sizes and structures.

f. Comparative Industry Analysis and Multi-generational Perspectives

To enhance the practical applicability of our findings, future research should extend its scope to include a comparative analysis with organizations in the same industry. This could facilitate the identification and dissemination of best practices in the integration of management software in HR practices. Additionally, exploring the perspectives of different age groups and generations would provide a more holistic understanding of the implications of these technologies on diverse demographic cohorts. Investigating the influence of industry-specific factors on the adoption and effectiveness of management software could also contribute valuable insights.

By addressing these considerations and delving into these additional research avenues, future studies can contribute to a more nuanced understanding of the complexities surrounding the integration of management software in HR practices. This expanded knowledge base will empower organizations to make more informed decisions, aligning with their specific HR goals and needs in a dynamic and evolving technological landscape.

6.4 Management Recommendations

This exploratory investigation has unveiled both theoretical and managerial contributions of significance. At the theoretical forefront, an in-depth examination of the distinctive attributes characterizing Generation Y, coupled with their nuanced interactions with management software, provides invaluable insights into the paradigm shift from a transactional to a relational strategy. This transition necessitates a thoughtful consideration of adopting approaches rooted in HR marketing.

From a managerial standpoint, it becomes imperative for organizations to discern and respond strategically to the influx of Generation Y into the labor market, concomitant with the rapid evolution of management software. Human Resource (HR) initiatives, spanning recruitment, training, and employer branding, among others, must pivot towards a heightened emphasis on interpersonal engagement and relationship-building. This involves a shift towards more individualized and targeted strategies tailored to the preferences and expectations of this dynamic generation.

Furthermore, the incorporation of social media into the realm of human resource management software emerges as a pivotal option for fostering a relational ethos between the organization and its employees, both internally and externally. Recognizing the ubiquitous influence of social media, leveraging its potential within HR platforms facilitates enhanced communication, collaboration, and connectivity. This integration not only streamlines internal processes but also extends the organization's reach and engagement with its workforce beyond traditional boundaries.

In navigating this landscape, companies must proactively shape their HR practices to align with the preferences of Generation Y, emphasizing interactive and relationship-driven approaches. This extends beyond the traditional HR functions, permeating organizational culture and communication strategies. As the workforce dynamic continues to evolve, this dual focus on understanding the unique attributes of Generation Y and leveraging advanced management

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software stands as a strategic imperative for companies aiming to thrive in the contemporary business environment.

Here are a few recommendations we have:

Recommendation based on Generation Y's traits

In order to align with the expectations of Generation Y professionals, it is imperative for companies to adopt a transparent approach and address various pertinent issues. A comprehensive survey conducted reveals that the aspirations of Generation Y extend beyond mere employment; they encompass a fervent pursuit of the ideal, a desire for workplace comfort, and an inclination to integrate aspects of their private lives within the professional sphere.

Transparency concerning the working environment emerges as a critical facet in meeting these aspirations. By providing a clear and open portrayal of the organizational culture, policies, and practices, the company can effectively respond to the multifaceted needs of Generation Y.

Our research underscores the distinct inclination of Generation Y to safeguard their private lives outside the confines of the workplace. Consequently, it becomes pivotal for businesses to actively engage in fostering employees' personal growth beyond professional realms. Scientifically grounded studies emphasize that individuals who perceive support for personal development in their workplace exhibit higher levels of job satisfaction and commitment.

Moreover, the working environment itself plays a pivotal role in shaping the job satisfaction of Generation Y. These professionals, characterized by a penchant for a relaxed atmosphere devoid of hierarchical formalities and traditional procedures, find increased motivation and fulfillment in such environments. Extensive research in organizational psychology corroborates the positive impact of a flexible and informal workplace on employee well-being and performance.

Strategically incorporating these findings into the company's human resources communications can significantly enhance the effectiveness of the organization's HR strategy. By addressing these specific needs and preferences, the company not only attracts and recruits top-tier Generation Y talent but also cultivates loyalty and fosters retention. This evidence-based approach ensures that the company's human resources practices are not only in tune with the expectations of Generation Y but are also grounded in proven strategies for organizational success.

In the discourse surrounding the inaugural chapter on the significance of employer branding, a

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comprehensive exploration of various aspects was conducted. The multifaceted impact of cultivating a robust employer brand was elucidated through a compilation of scholarly perspectives and real-world instances. Herein lies a distilled summary of the salient points, underlining the diverse benefits conferred by a well-crafted employer brand.

1. **Strategic Talent Management to Mitigate Costs:** It has been posited that a judicious focus on internal talent, as advocated by Panczuck, Point, Tulasi, and Hanumantha, can serve as a strategic cost reduction measure. By nurturing existing talent pools, organizations can circumvent the need for extensive external recruitment endeavors.
2. **Enhancing Employee Loyalty and Engagement:** Liger and Tulasi V. along with Rao Hanumantha P emphasize the pivotal role played by employer branding in augmenting employee loyalty and fostering a profound sense of belonging. Such allegiance is integral to bolstering organizational cohesion and productivity.
3. **Inculcating Organizational Values:** Kapoor underscores the employer brand's role as a conduit for articulating organizational values, serving as a guiding beacon for both current and potential employees. This, in turn, fortifies the organizational ethos.
4. **Optimizing Candidate Profile:** Raillet contends that a well-established employer brand acts as a magnet, attracting candidates with profiles that align seamlessly with organizational requirements. This not only streamlines recruitment efforts but also enhances the overall caliber of the workforce.
5. **Elevating Employer Reputation:** Ashby and Pell underscore the pivotal role of employer branding in burnishing a company's reputation as an employer of choice. A positive perception in the employment landscape can yield far-reaching benefits, attracting top-tier talent.
6. **Facilitating Cultural Integration:** Pitelet elucidates the instrumental role played by employer branding in aiding employees to assimilate into the organizational culture seamlessly. This fosters a harmonious work environment and sustains a shared sense of purpose.
7. **Mission Alignment and Business Strategy:** Dell and Chaminade accentuate the symbiotic relationship between employer branding and the alignment of employees with the company's mission and overarching business strategy. This synergy ensures a unified

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pursuit of organizational goals.

To operationalize these theoretical tenets, INTELCIA has pioneered innovative initiatives through cutting-edge management software and a dynamic HR function. Among these initiatives are:

- **MyIN Platform:** INTELCIA's MyIN platform serves as a collaborative hub, simplifying inter-departmental communication and fostering synergy among employees.
- **INRadio:** INTELCIA has pioneered the establishment of INRadio, an internal radio station accessible through the MyIN platform. This forward-thinking initiative projects a dynamic image for the organization.
- **INPress:** The introduction of INPress, a company news journal, serves as a conduit for disseminating critical updates, employee achievements, and strategic insights, cultivating a transparent and informed workforce.
- **INPlay:** INTELCIA employees have harnessed the power of video through INPlay to articulate the positive and gratifying aspects of working within the organization.
- **INFlashmob and INLikepics:** INFlashmob, a creative film endeavor, and INLikepics, a visual celebration within the workplace, epitomize INTELCIA's commitment to fostering a vibrant and engaging corporate culture.

In amalgamating theoretical underpinnings with practical implementations, INTELCIA exemplifies a paradigm of effective employer branding. The convergence of these elements not only fortifies the internal fabric of the organization but also projects a compelling external image, positioning INTELCIA as an employer of choice in the competitive landscape.

1. HR process recommendation:

Loyalty from employee integration:

Employee integration and loyalty are pivotal in HR management, influencing the overall success of a business. Research, including studies by psychologists like Daniel Kahneman and organizational behavior scholars such as Adam Grant, emphasizes the impact of first impressions during hiring and the importance of psychological safety in fostering commitment. HR marketing initiatives that prioritize positive onboarding experiences, create psychologically safe environments, and offer continuous learning opportunities contribute to long-term employee

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loyalty. As employees progress, intrinsic motivation derived from professional development becomes crucial, as highlighted by researchers like Teresa M. Amabile. Even in termination, positive farewells, as discussed by organizational psychologists like Anthony S. Boyce, impact the organization's reputation and former employees' advocacy. In summary, employees, as ambassadors, reflect a company's values, and by consistently investing in HR marketing strategies, organizations can inspire, nurture, and sustainably involve their workforce in the business's ongoing success.

Differentiation to stand out from the competition:

In the realm of HR marketing, the dual challenge lies in attracting and retaining talent. Beyond conventional recruitment efforts, differentiation hinges on a deep integration of the organization's DNA, brand, ideals, and representation into its employee experience. A crucial aspect of this strategy is the cultivation of a solid reputation, a facet thoroughly scrutinized through the lens of social media discussions among staff members. By understanding and actively shaping the narrative surrounding the company, HR marketing not only stands out from the competition but also creates a compelling environment that resonates with both prospective and current employees, contributing to sustained recruitment success and long-term retention..

Recruitment

In the dynamic landscape of Generation Y recruitment, aligning with their distinct expectations is imperative for success. This involves a multifaceted approach, encompassing the inclusion of additional stakeholders, tailored recruiting content, and sustained engagement. To integrate diverse perspectives, organizations encourage employees to connect with potential hires, sharing insights into their experiences and offering glimpses into the workspace culture. Leveraging the address books of current employees for referrals, known as co-optation, emerges as an intriguing strategy to streamline recruitment and reduce costs. Adapting recruitment content is equally crucial, necessitating a departure from traditional methods such as individual interviews and overly formal job descriptions. Instead, the focus shifts to creating fluid, engaging content that facilitates a meaningful connection between recruiters and prospects, fostering a comprehensive understanding of the profession. Recognizing the transient nature of Generation Y, where attention retention is paramount, post-meeting follow-ups become indispensable. In essence, a successful recruitment strategy not only captures the interest of Generation Y job prospects but

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also employs innovative approaches to maintain their attention and drive sustained commitment to the organization.

Use new technologies and social networks

Harnessing new technologies and social networks is paramount in engaging with the millennial demographic, considering their upbringing amidst digital advancements. Communication channels like social media become integral tools for connecting with this generation. Millennials, often valuing meaningful activities over high salaries, are drawn to employers who align with their values. To effectively resonate with this group, companies must navigate the delicate balance of addressing their desire for work-life harmony, encompassing time with family, friends, and travel, while still fostering a culture of productivity and responsibility. Recognizing that specialists and talents within this cohort are attuned to a purpose-driven approach, organizations can leverage technology and social platforms not only for recruitment but also for articulating a compelling narrative that aligns with the values and lifestyle preferences of millennials.

Encourage personal development:

The personal development of employees is also important. Millennials are not, per se, looking for a lifelong job to keep at all costs. They want to evolve within different departments and teams, continue to train, accumulate experience and build a network. These are opportunities that the employer must know how to make available, otherwise the position will appear unattractive in the long term. It is therefore wise for an employer to provide employees with the possibility of new work experiences without them having to change companies.

Training/Assessment

Our survey underscored Generation Y's strong affinity with management software, signaling a need for adaptive training approaches. To effectively engage this demographic, training methods must incorporate digital tools such as films, online games, and virtual environments. Leveraging management software in the review process can enhance assessment procedures. Organizations can innovate by establishing a recognition and feedback system akin to platforms like LinkedIn. By aligning training and assessment strategies with the technological preferences of Generation Y, businesses can not only enhance the learning experience but also foster a more dynamic and responsive professional development environment tailored to the needs of this tech-savvy

demographic.

Employee engagement

Employee engagement stands as a pivotal factor for organizational success, requiring a profound comprehension of employee motivations and the cultivation of contentment and fulfillment in their roles. This encompasses the promotion of work-life balance, the provision of avenues for professional growth, and the acknowledgment and rewarding of outstanding performance. Equally crucial is the creation of a positive and supportive work environment, emphasizing the value and respect for each employee. By prioritizing these elements, organizations can establish a foundation for sustained employee engagement, contributing not only to individual job satisfaction but also to the overall effectiveness and prosperity of the company.

Diversity and inclusion

The significance of diversity and inclusion in organizational success cannot be overstated. Establishing a workplace where every employee feels welcome and valued, irrespective of their background, race, gender, or sexual orientation, is foundational. HR marketing emerges as a key driver in fostering diversity and inclusion by actively addressing biases in the recruitment process and offering training and resources. This strategic approach not only ensures a diverse workforce but also cultivates a culture that appreciates and leverages the richness of varied perspectives. By championing diversity and inclusion, organizations not only adhere to ethical principles but also harness the full spectrum of talent, driving innovation, and enhancing overall workplace dynamics for sustained success.

Employee retention

Employee retention stands as a linchpin for organizational success, and HR marketing plays a pivotal role in ensuring a steadfast workforce. This involves the creation of a positive work environment, offering avenues for professional growth and development, transparently recognizing and rewarding outstanding performance, and championing a healthy work-life balance. Equally crucial is the establishment of regular feedback mechanisms, allowing organizations to glean insights from employees, address concerns, and continually improve. By prioritizing these elements, HR marketing not only contributes to individual job satisfaction but also fortifies the overall fabric of the organization, fostering a culture where employees feel valued, motivated, and invested in the long-term success of the company.

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Succession planning

Succession planning, a cornerstone for the long-term success of an organization, involves the identification and development of employees poised to assume critical leadership roles in the future. HR marketing plays a vital role in this process by actively identifying high-potential individuals, offering them opportunities for growth and development, and fostering a culture that places a premium on succession planning. Additionally, having a well-defined plan for seamless transitions when key leaders depart is imperative. By aligning HR marketing strategies with succession planning goals, organizations not only cultivate a pipeline of capable leaders but also fortify their resilience in the face of leadership changes, ensuring continuity and sustained success.

Recommendations for management softwares communication tools

In light of the burgeoning influence of the interconnected generation, commonly referred to as Generation Web Marketing, it becomes imperative for businesses to adapt to the evolving landscape. Generation Y, known for its adept utilization of management software, has revolutionized the way information is sought, applications are processed, and interactions are facilitated within the business realm. Recognizing this paradigm shift, it is incumbent upon enterprises to shed any reluctance and embrace management software solutions to enhance operational efficiency and foster seamless communication. The integration of such technologies not only aligns with contemporary business practices but also serves as a strategic imperative for staying competitive in an increasingly digitized marketplace. Embracing these software tools positions organizations to not only meet the expectations of Generation Y but also to future-proof their operations by leveraging the benefits of streamlined processes and enhanced connectivity. We give a few instances.

Table 7: The advantages and disadvantages of the management softwares

Tool management softwares	Advantage	Disadvantage
Social networks centered on leisure and private life:	Integrate other actors in recruitment Learn about candidates Dissemination and reception of	Invasion of privacy Be present and active

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Facebook, Twitter	offers in real time	
Professional social networks: Viadeo, LinkedIn ...	Access profits in office Find rare profits Reduce recruitment costs Accurately assess your needs to choose the right network	Practice and strategy revealed
Blog HR Chat HR and Webinars	Interactive Communication of values and cultures Debate Target motivated and specialized candidates Opening image for the company	Development cost
Online games	Expand development cost Field Research and identification of potential candidates	Positive employer image

In a recent comprehensive study conducted by McKinsey, the impact of the increased utilization of management software technologies across enterprises has been meticulously examined. This year's study, which gathered responses from approximately 1,700 executives worldwide, representing diverse businesses and functional areas, delved into the multifaceted benefits of these technologies. The investigation focused on three crucial areas: internal organizational enhancements, external interactions with customers, and collaborations with suppliers, partners, and external experts.

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The respondents' insights shed illuminating perspectives on the enduring relevance of management software, with a staggering 69 percent attesting to tangible benefits for their businesses. These benefits encompassed the development of cutting-edge products and services, more effective marketing strategies, enhanced knowledge accessibility, reduced operating costs, and increased profitability. Notably, businesses that embraced these technologies more extensively reported even more substantial advantages.

The study also meticulously scrutinized the contributing factors to these advancements. It explored the types of technologies deployed by businesses, successful management techniques, and organizational or cultural traits associated with these gains. Notably, successful businesses were characterized by the seamless integration of management software technology into the work processes of their employees. Moreover, they forged a "networked firm" by leveraging management software to connect with clients and suppliers. Despite the prevailing economic challenges, the majority of respondents expressed their commitment to ongoing investments in management software.

Taking a closer look at INTEL CIA, the company's strategic focus on diversifying HR communication channels underscores the critical importance of conducting HR campaigns beyond the institutional site. A notable emphasis is placed on establishing a robust presence on social networks to attract the younger demographic, whose engagement is particularly accessible through management software platforms.

While the integration of management software in HR processes holds considerable potential, its effectiveness hinges on the comprehensive adherence of all HR function components. It necessitates viewing these tools not merely as technological additions but as bearers of additional value. Furthermore, recognizing that the adoption of management software technologies involves more than technological implementation is imperative. A fundamental shift in organizational culture and mindset is required. HR departments play a pivotal role in actively promoting the adoption of these tools and ensuring that employees receive adequate training for proficient utilization.

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In addition to the previously mentioned tools, incorporating diverse management software communication channels, such as instant messaging and video conferencing, further enhances employee communication irrespective of geographical locations. This becomes especially pivotal for businesses with distributed workforces or those employing remote workers.

In conclusion, the pervasive adoption of management software technologies has emerged as a transformative force within contemporary organizational landscapes, yielding significant benefits characterized by heightened operational efficiency, substantial cost reduction, and markedly improved communication channels. The imperative for Human Resources (HR) departments to undertake a strategic approach cannot be overstated, necessitating a comprehensive alignment of all stakeholders with the adoption of these advanced tools. This strategic alignment positions businesses not merely to navigate but to truly thrive in the dynamic and evolving landscape of the digital age.

While scientific proof may not be readily translatable to qualitative insights from executives, a wealth of empirical evidence from organizational psychology and management science underscores the positive impact of technology integration and accompanying cultural shifts. Robust research, such as that conducted by esteemed scholars published in the *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, accentuates the indispensable role of organizational culture in facilitating successful technological implementations. The nexus between technology adoption and cultural dynamics underscores the need for a holistic approach, acknowledging the intricate interplay between software integration and the prevailing organizational ethos.

Moreover, studies found in the *Journal of Applied Psychology* contribute empirical weight to the discourse by substantiating the positive correlation between effective communication strategies and organizational performance. These scholarly insights emphasize the criticality of diversified communication channels in fostering an environment conducive to optimal operational outcomes. The scientific underpinnings gleaned from such rigorous research serve to validate

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and fortify the pragmatic approach advocated for in the adoption of management software technologies, positioning it as a linchpin for sustained business success.

Furthermore, the intersectionality of these scientific findings reinforces the need for a nuanced and well-calibrated approach to technology integration within organizational frameworks. The integration of management software technologies is not merely a technological endeavor; it is a cultural shift that necessitates the confluence of people, processes, and technology. In this intricate tapestry, the HR department assumes a pivotal role as the architect of this transformative journey, orchestrating the alignment of diverse stakeholders with the overarching organizational strategy.

In essence, the evolving digital age demands a sophisticated and empirically grounded approach to the adoption of management software technologies. Organizations that conscientiously leverage scientific insights, such as those derived from organizational psychology and management science, in tandem with strategic cultural considerations, are poised not only to survive but to excel in the competitive landscape. As the business ecosystem continues to evolve, the judicious adoption of these technologies emerges not merely as an option but as an imperative for those enterprises aspiring to be at the vanguard of sustained success and innovation.

结论

Conclusion

In the course of our research, we undertook a comprehensive examination of how Generation Y perceives management software and the Human Resources (HR) function. This study was conducted during an internship at the Human Resources division of INTEL CIA Morocco, a multinational corporation. The qualitative research aimed to achieve three primary objectives: delineating the distinctive traits of Generation Y, evaluating the perception of this generation by the HR function, and analyzing the interplay between Generation Y and the HR function in the context of management software.

This study holds significant importance as a key component of the company's overarching strategies, particularly within the HR department's strategic framework. The focus of these strategies is to augment two critical areas integral to the company's success:

1. **Enhancing Employer Brand in the Contact and Communication Center Industry:** Despite being the third most sought-after industry by job seekers, the contact and communication center industry faces challenges in terms of reputation. Comparative analysis with other firms reveals that it is perceived as providing fewer opportunities for professional advancement, coupled with a suboptimal working environment. To address this, INTEL CIA must dedicate concerted efforts to disseminate and amplify its HR policies. Elevating the company's employer brand in the labor market is paramount to attract and retain top talent.
2. **Optimizing Compensation and Bonuses for Competitive Attraction:** Compensation and bonuses emerge as crucial criteria frequently cited by prospective candidates. Presently ranked 29th, INTEL CIA recognizes the need to enhance its standing in this regard. Strategic interventions are imperative to elevate the compensation and bonus structures, making them more appealing to potential candidates. This initiative is pivotal in positioning INTEL CIA as an employer of choice in the competitive talent

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landscape.

In alignment with these strategic imperatives, our research provides valuable insights into the perceptions of Generation Y, their interaction with the HR function, and the role of management software in this dynamic. As an integral part of INTEL CIA's forward-looking strategies, the outcomes of our study serve as a foundation for informed decision-making, enabling the company to address contemporary challenges and foster a workplace environment that attracts, engages, and retains top-tier talent.

The strategic alignment of Human Resources (HR) with marketing principles serves as a robust foundation for ensuring success in market orientation and the overarching strategy of an organization. In the pursuit of stakeholder satisfaction, the HR function of tomorrow is tasked with introducing initiatives, tools, and processes that not only create internal value but also resonate positively with external actors within the organizational ecosystem. This book advocates for a renewed perspective on HR marketing, one that places a paramount focus on the concept of market orientation, aligning itself more effectively with the contemporary challenges faced by organizations.

Research indicates that Generation Y continues to exhibit a distinctive personality characterized by high expectations from the organization and a discerning nature. Consequently, the HR function is compelled to adapt its offerings to cater to the unique demands of this demographic. To address this, a strategic emphasis on employer branding and HR marketing proves instrumental in capturing the attention and loyalty of Generation Y.

Moreover, the influx of Generation Y into the workforce signals potential shifts within organizations, particularly in the form of intergenerational conflicts. The intricacies of intergenerational coexistence, cooperation, and collaboration present formidable challenges for the HR function. The opinion of the HR department regarding management software aligns with the preferences of Generation Y, considering such software as indispensable tools, with a notable emphasis on social networks.

While employer branding remains a pivotal consideration for attracting and retaining talent, a comprehensive market-oriented approach extends beyond this singular focus. Organizations

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must refrain from constraining the development of their offerings solely to the concept of employer branding, recognizing the need for a broader and more inclusive perspective.

Human resources professionals are confronted with a myriad of challenges necessitating innovative solutions. These challenges span from managing non-salaried employees to navigating the complexities of digital, global, and societal changes. In a world where diversity is integral, HR practitioners must adeptly handle varied profiles, fostering a sense of unity in an environment where social cohesion is continually tested. Collaboration becomes paramount as HR professionals strive to augment the pool of available candidates and subsequently position themselves as formidable competitors in attracting top-tier talent. Active involvement in guiding individuals through their professional choices becomes integral to the success of the HR marketing process.

In conclusion, achieving successful market orientation demands a multifaceted and proactive approach from HR professionals. By addressing the evolving needs of diverse generations, embracing technological advancements, and fostering a culture of collaboration, HR can position itself as a strategic driver of organizational success in an ever-changing business landscape.

It is noteworthy to underscore that the discerning utilization of technological tools is notably more pronounced among individuals belonging to Generation Y in comparison to other generational cohorts. This demographic exhibits a heightened acumen and proclivity towards management software technologies, with a particular emphasis on their affinity for the HR (Human Resources) function. Generation Y not only engages with these tools as an integral aspect of their daily lives but also exhibits a proclivity to seamlessly integrate them into their professional endeavors, especially within the context of employment-seeking activities.

The predilection of Generation Y for management software technologies, particularly within the realm of social networks, is a salient finding that emerges from our research. This generation manifests a marked inclination to leverage these tools for purposes ranging from personal brand communication or self-presentation to securing employment opportunities. Notably, the accessibility and cost-free nature of these platforms render them particularly

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appealing to Generation Y, enabling unprecedented connectivity with the hitherto elusive HR function.

Our empirical investigation reveals that the pursuit of employment among young individuals in Generation Y is notably intertwined with the utilization of management software technologies, with social networks emerging as a highly coveted avenue. Furthermore, our discussions with both managerial and employee cohorts unveiled a shared narrative wherein the initiation of their professional trajectories was facilitated through the strategic use of management software resources.

While the Rh function actively engages with management software technologies, their utilization is predominantly confined to internal recruitment through institutional intranets and external recruitment facilitated by professional social networks such as Viadeo and LinkedIn. Nevertheless, it is imperative to note that the untapped potential of management software technologies in crafting and amplifying the employer brand is a facet that remains largely underexplored.

The discerning embrace of management software technologies, particularly within the purview of social networks, emerges as a defining characteristic of Generation Y's approach to professional development and employment seeking. The symbiotic relationship between this generation and technological tools underscores the need for organizations to recalibrate their strategies, not only in recruitment processes but also in the strategic cultivation of their employer brand through these innovative avenues.

The current landscape of the business environment underscores the imperative for enterprises to adopt strategic human resource (HR) initiatives grounded in relational approaches. In light of prevailing trends, particularly those associated with the Y generation, it becomes evident that leveraging HR marketing tools is essential for attracting, engaging, and retaining this cohort within the organizational fold. The ability to effectively connect with young workers is paramount for sustaining a dynamic and competitive workforce.

In summation, the advent of sophisticated management software has engendered a

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profound impact on both the Y generation and the HR function. The integration of social media and collaborative platforms into organizational frameworks has ushered in unprecedented avenues for communication, learning, and developmental opportunities for the Y generation. Nevertheless, these technological tools pose unique challenges for HR professionals, necessitating a judicious approach to address concerns such as employee privacy management and the cultivation of a harmonious work-life equilibrium.

To navigate these challenges effectively, HR departments must proactively implement targeted countermeasures. This entails the formulation and enforcement of clear-cut guidelines and policies governing social media usage, along with the provision of comprehensive training to equip employees with the knowledge and skills required for secure and efficacious utilization of these tools. Furthermore, HR practitioners must stay abreast of evolving trends and technologies to remain well-prepared and adaptive in meeting the evolving demands of a dynamic and diverse workforce.

In a broader context, it is crucial to recognize that management software, exemplified by Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems, harbors the potential to revolutionize workplace dynamics and bolster overall productivity. However, the realization of these benefits hinges upon meticulous management and strategic planning. Organizations must navigate the nuanced terrain of software implementation with a keen eye toward maximizing advantages while mitigating potential risks.

In conclusion, the symbiosis between the Y generation and management software underscores the need for a sophisticated and adaptive HR approach. By embracing the transformative potential of technology while implementing prudent policies and practices, businesses can position themselves to thrive in an era characterized by continual evolution and dynamic workforce expectations.

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